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Seasonal Transformation of the Thermal Regime in Bulgaria (1950–2025): A Spatiotemporal Analysis Using ERA5-Land data set and Google Earth Engine

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ABSTRACT

This research presents a high-resolution spatiotemporal analysis of surface air temperature trends in Bulgaria over a 76-year period (1950–2025). Utilizing the ERA5-Land reanalysis dataset and the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud computing platform, the study quantifies seasonal warming magnitudes and identifies structural shifts in the regional thermal regime. Results demonstrate a definitive transition from a stable continental climate to an accelerated warming phase, particularly after 1987. The total warming magnitude since 1950 is most pronounced in summer (+3.2°C) and winter (+2.9°C), with spring and autumn showing significant increases of +2.4°C and +2.1°C, respectively. A comparative dual-trend analysis reveals that warming velocity has approximately doubled during the most recent 20-year window (2005–2025), with decadal slopes in summer reaching nearly +0.80°C. Statistical robustness, evidenced by a significant rise in the coefficient of determination (R²) during the 21st century, indicates that the warming signal has become a forced response that overrides natural stochastic variability. Spatially, the Danubian Plain and Upper Thracian Lowland have emerged as warming hotspots, exhibiting total magnitudes exceeding +3.8°C, effectively signaling a "Tropicalization" of the Bulgarian lowlands. These shifts are linked to critical environmental consequences, including the "False Spring" paradox – where early thermal onset increases frost vulnerability – and a destabilized hydrological cycle characterized by premature snowmelt and a transition to a drought-to-flood regime. The findings align with the other regional studies identifying the Balkan Peninsula as a high-sensitivity climate hotspot, with warming rate higher than the global terrestrial average. This study underscores the urgent necessity for climate-resilient adaptation strategies in Bulgarian agriculture, water management, and urban planning to address the high-velocity thermal transformation of the territory.

Keywords: Climate acceleration, Bulgaria, Surface air temperatures, ERA5-Land, Remote sensing

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INTRODUCTION

Surface air temperature (SAT) is a primary geophysical variable and a fundamental indicator of the Earth's thermodynamic state, directly influencing hydrological cycles, ecosystem stability, and human health. Within the Eastern Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria represents a complex climatological intersection where temperate continental, Mediterranean, and modified maritime influences converge across a diverse topographic landscape. Over the past seven decades, this region has exhibited a high sensitivity to global climate changes, characterized by accelerated warming, shifts in seasonal phenology, and an increased frequency of extreme thermal events (Bocheva et al., 2024; Nojarov, 2017; Malcheva et al. 2023). Recent global climate assessments have highlighted Southeast Europe as a "warming hotspot," with regional SAT increases exceeding the global mean rate (IPCC, 2023).

The historical analysis of Bulgarian temperatures traditionally relied on point-based meteorological station data. However, the high and diverse relief of the country – ranging from sea level to nearly 3,000 meters – creates significant spatial heterogeneity and "data voids," particularly in high-altitude regions where station maintenance is difficult. To address these spatial gaps, atmospheric reanalysis has become an indispensable tool in modern climatology. The ERA5-Land reanalysis, produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), provides a consistent, high-resolution (9 km) spatial grid that integrates millions of historical observations (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). By providing a continuous data record from 1950 to the present, ERA5-Land reanalysis data allows for the detection of long-term climate signals that are often obscured by local microclimatic noise in individual station records (Ivanov et al., 2025).

A critical finding in recent Bulgarian climatological research is the identification of a distinct "climate break" occurring in the late 1980s. Nikolova (2012), Nikolova et al. (2025) Nojarov and Nikolava (2022), , Bocheva et al., (2024) have both statistically validated this regime shift, noting that temperature anomalies transitioned from predominantly negative to consistently positive following this years. Specifically, Nikolova's (2012) analysis of extreme temperature months in the Rila Mountain reveals that while the period 1961–1986 was characterized by frequent extremely cold months, the subsequent period (1987–2012) saw extreme warm months represent 70% of all recorded thermal extremes. This systemic shift initiated a period where the frequency of cold anomalies dropped drastically, replaced by a consistent warming "red" regime that has intensified into the 2020s (Bocheva et al., 2024; Ivanov et al., 2025).

This intensification reached a peak in 2024, which recorded a national average temperature 2.1°C above climate norms, making it the warmest year in Bulgarian history since 1930 (NIMH, 2025). Preliminary data suggests that 2025 continues this trend, following global records that identify the most recent decade as the warmest on record (WMO, 2025). Furthermore, the warming velocity has shown a non-linear acceleration. While the long-term decadal warming rate for the 1950–2024 period ranged between 0.32°C and 0.48°C, warming velocities nearly doubled in the last twenty years (2005–2024) to 0.60°C–0.85°C per decade (Ivanov et al., 2025).

Ivanov et al. (2025) in similar research based on ERA 5 data and GEE processing, about the dynamics of the mean annual temperatures in Bulgaria regarding the same period disclosed that the long-term spatial distribution of the annual surface air temperature (SAT) across Bulgaria, reveals a distinct topographic-climatic stratification (Fig.1). These findings align closely with the regional framework established by Velev (2002), showing that thermal maxima are concentrated in the Continental-Mediterranean region of Southwest Bulgaria, as well as South-Central and Southeast

Bulgaria. These areas serve as primary thermal gateways where Mediterranean air masses exert their most significant influence (Marinova et al., 2017). Conversely, thermal minima are located in the Mountainous region, where the high-altitude massifs of the Rila, Pirin, Rhodope, and Balkan ranges maintain annual means below 4°C. This sharp contrast validates the use of high-resolution gridded ERA5-Land data, which successfully captures the steep thermal gradients between Bulgaria's lowlands and alpine zones (Ivanov et al., 2025).

Fig. 1. Spatial distribution of the mean annual temperatures -1950-2024. Source: *Ivanov et al. (2025)*.

According to Ivanov et al. (2025) the multi-decadal record of the mean annual temperatures indicates a consistent warming trajectory defined by a definitive shift in the late 1980s (Fig. 2). The period from 1950 to 1987 was characterized by significant inter-annual variability, with several years remaining below the long-term average – a reflection of a more stable climate influenced by continental air masses. However, following the 1987 "climate break," a sustained and visible increase in mean annual temperatures occurred (Ivanov et al., 2025).

In the last two decades, the frequency of negative anomalies has decreased substantially, while extreme thermal peaks were recorded in 2023 and 2024, confirming Bulgaria's status as a regional warming hotspot (Fig. 2) and the shifting of the thermal regime into a new state marked by higher annual means and a significant departure from the mid-20th-century baseline (Ivanov et al., 2025; Malcheva et al. 2021).

Ivanov et al. (2025) disclosed that between 1950–2025 a synchronized warming trend can be observed across all of Bulgaria's climatic zones even though there are thermal differences due to topography and maritime proximity, the calculated trend lines show that the magnitude of warming is relatively uniform across the territory (Fig. 3, and 4).

The Continental-Mediterranean region remains the warmest, with annual means often exceeding 13°C, while the Moderate and Transitional Continental regions occupy a middle tier (10°C to 12°C).

Despite these differences, the warming slope across all five regions is remarkably similar, increasing by approximately 0.3°C to 0.4°C per decade. This synchronization suggests that large-scale regional climate forcing is dominating local geographical effects.

Fig. 2. Dynamics of the mean annual temperatures -1950-2024. (after Ivanov et al.,2025)

Ivanov et al. (2025) based on ERA -5 data confirmed that Bulgaria is warming significantly faster than the global terrestrial average. While the global land-surface warming rate is roughly 0.2°C per decade, Bulgarian regions are warming at an average rate of 0.32°C to 0.48°C per decade. Major portions of the Danubian Plain and the Upper Thracian Plain have crossed the 0.4°C per decade threshold, implying a cumulative increase of approximately 3.0°C during 1950-2025.

Fig. 3. Dynamics of the mean annual temperatures in Velev (2002) climate regions -1950-2024. Source: *Ivanov et al. (2025)*.

The results reveal a clear contrast in climate velocity driven by land-sea interactions and topography. The highest warming rates are found in the continental interior, where the lack of large water bodies allows the land to heat rapidly, likely amplified by a feedback loop where decreasing soil moisture reduces evaporative cooling. In contrast, the Black Sea region exhibits lower decadal slopes (0.32°C to 0.35°C) due to the thermal inertia of the sea (Fig.5).

Crucially, the warming rate in high-altitude zones mirrors the lowlands, suggesting that as snow cover decreases, the exposed ground absorbs more solar radiation, creating a self-reinforcing warming cycle (Nojarov, 2012).

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of the magnitude of the warming 1950-2024. Source: *Ivanov et al. (2025)*.

Significant Stippling Analysis provides scientific validation for these observations, covering nearly 100% of the Bulgarian territory for the 1950–2025 period, indicating that the warming trend is statistically undeniable ($p < 0.05$). A comparison between the long-term baseline (1950–2025) and the last 20 years (2005–2025) reveals a profound escalation in warming velocity, with the rate essentially doubling in recent decades (Fig. 6). This is driven by a clustering of record-breaking years; all ten of the warmest years in Bulgarian history have occurred since 2005, with 2024 identified as the warmest year since 1930, reaching 2.1°C above climate norms (NIMH, 2025).

Fig. 5. Magnitude of the warming 1950-2024 – Velev regions (2002). Source: *Ivanov et al. (2025)*.

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of the magnitude of the warming last 20 years (2005-2024) according to Ivanov et al. (2025).

Fig. 7. Magnitude of the warming 1950-2024 – Velev regions (2002) Ivanov et al. (2025).

To pinpoint the transition from a stable state to rapid warming, Ivanov et al., (2025) conducted a breakpoint analysis using the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of temperature anomalies. This identifies a "break point" around 1987–1988. Prior to 1987, anomalies were balanced, but afterward, negative anomalies dropped drastically, virtually disappearing in the last 20 years (Fig. 8 and 90. This represents a regime shift, with a jump of 1.0°C to 1.5°C in average annual temperatures.

According to Nojarov (2012) the temperatures and precipitation change is due to changes in large-scale atmospheric circulation, specifically shifts in the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and East Atlantic (EA) patterns, which increased warm air advection from the south. The data also suggests that the country entered a new acceleration phase after 2005, pushing the territory toward the extreme thermal records of 2024 and 2025.

Fig.8. Mean annual averages for 1950-2024 and 2005-2024 with trend lines (according to Ivanov Ivanov et al., 2025).

Fig. 9. Annual temperature anomalies relative to long term means (1950-2024) according to Ivanov et al. (2025).

Building upon the spatiotemporal analysis of annual means, the present study expands its scope to investigate the intricate seasonal dynamics of Bulgarian temperature regimes up to 2025. This broader perspective is necessitated by the observation that annual averages often mask critical seasonal "engines" of warming, such as the disproportionate increase in summer thermal stress or the precipitous decline of winter snow-albedo feedback mechanisms. As atmospheric forcing intensifies, traditional geographical moderators – such as proximity to the Black Sea or altitudinal cooling – are increasingly failing to regulate regional sensitivity.

By utilizing the **Google Earth Engine (GEE)** cloud-based platform (Gorelick et al., 2017), we implement a pixel-based Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and trend detection across the Bulgarian territory. This approach allows for a granular mapping of seasonal shifts (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON), uncovering how the transition from stable temperate patterns to more volatile, Mediterranean-influenced cycles is altering the country's environmental baseline. Ultimately, this comprehensive seasonal inventory provides the high-resolution evidence required for adaptive planning in Bulgaria's most climate-vulnerable sectors, including water resource management and agricultural phenology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the study area, data sources, and methodological framework employed to analyse the spatiotemporal and seasonal dynamics of surface air temperature in Bulgaria for the period 1950–2025, based on ERA5-Land reanalysis data and cloud-based processing in Google Earth Engine.

Study Area

The study area encompasses the entire territory of Bulgaria, which enclosed 110,994 km² situated in the eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula. The country's physical landscape is defined by high morphological diversity, characterized by four alternating bands of high and low terrain extending from west to east: the Danubian Plain, the Balkan Mountains, the Transitional region (including the

Thracian Lowland), and the Rila-Rhodope massif. Bulgaria's topography is composed of approximately 31% lowlands (0–200 m), 41% hills and plateaus (200–600 m), and 28% mountainous terrain. The average altitude is approximately 470 m, but the extreme vertical range – from the Black Sea level to the alpine peaks of the Rila Mountains (Musala, 2,925 m) – creates sharp thermal gradients that necessitate the use of high-resolution gridded datasets like ERA5-Land.

This structural complexity acts as a decisive factor in the distribution of surface air temperature, as the Balkan Mountains serve as a significant barrier to the cooling influence of northern continental air masses, while the southern massifs modulate Mediterranean influences (Topliyski, 2006). The territory of the country is divided in climatic zones according to the regional framework established by Velev (2002). This framework classifies the territory into five distinct climatic regions based on the dominant atmospheric circulation and geographic factors with following specific climate features:

- **Moderate Continental Region (Northern Bulgaria):** This region encompasses the largest portion of Bulgaria, covering the extensive Danubian Plain, the rolling hills of the Fore-Balkan, and high western basins such as the Sofia Plain (Velev, 2002). This area is characterized by a geographical openness to the north and northeast, which facilitates the frequent and unimpeded intrusion of cold continental air masses from Central and Eastern Europe (Marinova et al., 2017; Velev, 2002). Consequently, the region exhibits the most pronounced seasonal temperature amplitudes in the country, as the Balkan Mountains act as a barrier to the south, preventing the moderation of temperature by Mediterranean influences. Winter conditions are typically severe, with average January temperatures falling between 1°C and 3.8°C (Marinova et al., 2017; World Bank, 2025). Due to the lack of northern topographic barriers, the region is highly prone to extreme cold spells where temperatures can drop below 25°C or even reach historical minimums of -38.3°C during powerful arctic anticyclonic invasions (Marinova et al., 2017). In contrast, the summers are hot and sweltering, with July average temperatures ranging between 21°C and 25°C (Velev, 2002; Marinova et al., 2017). Absolute maximum temperatures in the lowlands frequently exceed 35°C to 40°C, particularly in northern riparian towns such as Ruse and Silistra. The precipitation regime in this zone follows a distinct continental pattern where the annual totals generally range between 450 mm and 650 mm (Velev, 2002). There is a prominent seasonal maximum in early summer, specifically in June, which can account for up to 35% of the annual rainfall amount (Marinova et al., 2017; Velev, 2002). The driest period occurs during the winter, with a minimum typically recorded in February. Persistent snow cover is a characteristic feature of the regional winter and can last between 40 and 60 days per year, although recent decadal observations indicate a significant reduction in both snow depth and duration (Bocheva et al., 2024; Marinova et al. 2017, Malcheva, K. & Bocheva, L. 2023). The atmospheric circulation is dominated by western and northwestern winds that bring Atlantic moisture, while strong northeastern winds in the winter are responsible for freezing temperatures and snowdrifts across the eastern and central Danubian Plain (Velev, 2002). Powerful ground-level inversions are common in the flat lands and basins during winter, effectively trapping cold air masses for extended periods (Marinova et al., 2017). Furthermore, the region frequently experiences the Föhn effect, characterized by warm and dry winds descending from the northern slopes of the Balkan Mountains, particularly during the spring months (Marinova et al., 2017). Sub-regional variations exist within this zone, such as in the Northeastern Dobrudzha area, which displays more steppe-like features with lower annual precipitation, often less than 500 mm, and higher wind speeds (Velev 2002).

- **Transitional Continental Region (Central Bulgaria):** This region represents a critical climatic buffer zone situated between the Moderate Continental North and the Mediterranean-influenced South. This region encompasses the Upper Thracian Lowland, the valleys of the Trans-Balkan sub-region such as the Kazanlak and Karlovo basins, and the eastern slopes of the Balkan Mountains (Velev, 2002; Topliyski, 2006). Its climate is defined by the complex interaction between transformed Atlantic air masses, continental influences from the north, and Mediterranean cyclonic activity from the south. The thermal regime is characterized by noticeably milder winters compared to the Moderate Continental zone. Average January temperatures are typically positive, ranging from 0°C to 1.5°C, although the region remains susceptible to occasional arctic intrusions that can trigger sharp, short-lived temperature drops (Marinova et al., 2017). Summers are long and hot, with average July temperatures between 22°C and 24°C (Velev, 2002). Notably, the Upper Thracian Lowland serves as a heat pole for Bulgaria; the town of Sadovo holds the national absolute maximum record of 45.2°C, and recent data indicates that the city of Plovdiv has seen a significant increase in days exceeding 30°C, frequently surpassing 100 days per year in the last decade (Ivanov, 2025; Marinova et al., 2017). The precipitation regime in this region is uniquely balanced, displaying transitional features between the continental and Mediterranean types. Unlike the North, which has a single summer maximum, the Transitional region often exhibits two distinct maxima: one in May–June due to continental influence and a second, smaller peak in November–December driven by Mediterranean cyclonic activity (Topliyski, 2006; Marinova et al., 2017). Annual precipitation totals generally range from 500 mm to 600 mm, though the region is highly prone to summer and autumn droughts (Velev, 2002;). Recent studies suggest a weakening of continental precipitation signals, with a trend toward a more even monthly distribution, yet with an increasing frequency of intense, convective wet events (Marinova & Bocheva, 2023). Atmospheric circulation is highly influenced by the shielding effect of the Balkan Mountains to the north and the Sredna Gora range. This protection results in lower average wind speeds, typically between 1.2 and 4.0 m/s, and frequent winter temperature inversions in the lowland basins (Marinova et al., 2017). These inversions often lead to prolonged periods of fog and localized air pollution. The favorable thermal conditions, with a vegetation period temperature sum of approximately 4200°C to 4250°C, support the cultivation of thermophilic crops such as cotton, tobacco, and grapes, though increasing evapotranspiration rates are heightening irrigation demands (Kazandjiev et al., 2009).

- **Continental-Mediterranean Region (Southern Valleys):** This region extends across the southernmost parts of Bulgaria, primarily encompassing the valleys of the Struma and Mesta rivers south of the Kresna Gorge, the Arda river basin, and the coastal lowlands near the border with Turkey (Velev, 2002). This region serves as the primary gateway for Mediterranean air masses, which move northward along the river valleys, significantly altering the thermal and precipitation regimes compared to the rest of the country (Topliyski, 2006). The geographical location allows for a unique climate where the harshness of the continental winter is substantially mitigated by the thermal influence of the Aegean Sea, located only a short distance to the south. Thermal characteristics in this region are the mildest in Bulgaria, with average January temperatures consistently remaining positive, typically between 1.5°C and 3.5°C (Marinova et al., 2017). Winters are short and characterized by high cyclonic activity, which prevents the formation of a long-lasting snow cover; snow, when it falls, usually melts within a few days (Velev, 2002; Marinova et al., 2017). Summers are long, dry, and intensely hot, with average July temperatures reaching 24°C to 25°C, and maximums frequently exceeding 40°C (Velev, 2002; Marinova et al., 2017). In recent years, this region

has exhibited the highest frequency of "tropical nights" (minimum temperatures above 20°C) in the country, a clear indicator of the northward expansion of Mediterranean climate characteristics (Bocheva et al., 2024). The precipitation regime is distinctly Mediterranean, marked by a primary maximum in the winter months (November–December) and a significant minimum during the summer (August), which often leads to severe seasonal droughts (Marinova et al., 2017; Velev, 2002). Annual precipitation totals range from 550 mm to 750 mm, though the efficiency of this rainfall is low due to high evapotranspiration rates during the hot summer period. The region is dominated by southern and southwestern winds, which bring warm, moist air, although northern winds can occasionally penetrate the valleys, causing sudden but brief temperature drops (Toplijski, 2006).

- **Black Sea Region:** The Black Sea climatic region occupies a narrow longitudinal strip along the eastern border of Bulgaria, extending approximately 40 to 60 km inland from the coast (Velev, 2002). This region's climate is uniquely defined by the thermal inertia of the Black Sea, which acts as a powerful seasonal regulator, moderating temperature extremes and creating a distinct maritime-influenced regime that differs significantly from the continental interior (Marinova et al., 2017). The Balkan Mountains reach the sea at Cape Emine, effectively bisecting the coast into a northern sector influenced by temperate continental air masses and a southern sector more frequently impacted by Mediterranean cyclonic activity (Velev, 2002; Dineva, 2013). The thermal regime of the Black Sea region is the most stable in Bulgaria, characterized by the lowest annual temperature amplitudes, typically between 20°C and 21°C (Velev, 2002; Marinova et al., 2017). Winters are relatively mild and humid, with average January temperatures ranging from 0.8°C in the north to 3.2°C in the south (Koprarev, 2002). Snow cover is notoriously unstable, typically persisting for only 2 to 4 weeks in the north and as few as 4 to 5 days in the southern coastal stretches (Velev, 2002). Springs are notably cool and prolonged due to the slow warming of the sea surface, which often lags behind the land by several weeks (Dineva, 2013). Summers are moderately warm and sunny, with average July temperatures of 22°C to 23°C; however, the cooling effect of the sea breeze prevents the extreme heat typical of the Danubian Plain or the Thracian Lowland (Marinova et al., 2017). Autumns are exceptionally long and warm, often representing the most favorable season as the sea releases stored heat back into the atmosphere (Velev, 2002). Precipitation in this region is generally sparse, with the northern coast (Dobrudzha) being one of the driest areas in Bulgaria, receiving less than 500 mm annually (Bocheva et al., 2024). The seasonal distribution varies geographically: the northern sector maintains a fairly even monthly distribution, while the southern sector shows a distinct Mediterranean-style maximum in winter (Dineva, 2013; Velev, 2002). A defining feature of the coastal climate is the breeze circulation; during the summer, the daytime sea breeze brings cool, moist air inland, while the nighttime land breeze moves in the opposite direction (Marinova et al., 2017). Despite the general aridity, the region is susceptible to intense, short-lived convective rainfall events and flash floods, particularly in autumn when warm sea temperatures interact with early cold air intrusions (Bocheva et al., 2024; NIMH, 2025).
- **Mountainous Region (above 1,000 m):** This region encompasses the high-altitude territories of Bulgaria situated above 1000 m a.s.l., including the Rila, Pirin, Rhodope, and Balkan (Stara Planina) mountain ranges (Velev, 2002). Within this zone, the primary determinant of the climatic regime is the hypsometric factor, which induces a vertical zonality that significantly overrides the latitudinal influences found in the lowlands (Marinova et al., 2017). According to the Köppen-Geiger classification, the climate transitions from humid continental (D) at

mid-altitudes to tundra (ET) or alpine polar climate on the highest peaks such as Musala and Vihren (Topliyski, 2006; Velev, 2010). The thermal regime is characterized by a steady decrease in temperature with increasing altitude, averaging a lapse rate of 0.3°C to 0.4°C per 100 m in winter and reaching 0.7°C per 100 m during the summer months (Marinova et al., 2017). On the highest summits, average January temperatures drop to between -8°C and -10°C, while summer temperatures remain cool, with August means at Musala Peak (2925 m) averaging only 8.2°C (Marinova et al., 2017). Recent decadal trends (1990–2024) have shown a significant "elevation-dependent warming," with the most pronounced temperature increases occurring between 1000 and 1700 m, which has led to a noticeable upward shift of the tree line and the expansion of species like the mountain pine (*Pinus mugo*) (Grunewald & Scheithauer, 2011; Matev et al, 2025). Precipitation in the mountainous zone is abundant and increases linearly with altitude up to approximately 2000 m, with annual totals ranging from 800 mm to over 1200 mm, and reaching peaks of 2000 mm in specific high-elevation zones (Velev, 2002). Snow is the dominant form of winter precipitation, and a stable snowpack typically persists for 5 to 8 months at altitudes above 2000 m (Matev et al, 2025). However, significant shifts have been observed; since 1981, there has been a statistically significant decrease in winter and spring precipitation at stations like Musala and Cherni Vrah, alongside a persistent shortening of the snow season by 7 to 9 days per decade (Matev et al, 2025). Winds are exceptionally strong on the ridges, with prevailing westerly and southwesterly directions often reaching speeds of 35 to 40 m/s during winter storms.

Data Source and mean temperatures aggregation

The primary dataset utilized in this research is the ERA5-Land reanalysis image collection (ECMWF_ERA5_LAND_HOURLY), which offers a globally consistent, high-resolution view of land-surface variables from 1950 to the present (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). Produced by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), ERA5-Land serves as an enhanced, downscaled version of the fifth-generation ERA5 atmospheric reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020; Muñoz-Sabater, 2021). ERA5-Land is generated by replaying the land component of the ERA5 climate reanalysis using the **Tiled ECMWF Scheme for Surface Exchanges over Land (HTESSSEL)** model, specifically incorporating land surface hydrology (H-TESSSEL) and vegetation seasonality (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). Unlike the standard ERA5, which operates at approximately 31 km grid, ERA5-Land runs "offline" – meaning it is not coupled to the atmosphere – to deliver a much finer horizontal resolution of **9 km** (0.1°x0.1°, grid) (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2019,2021).

This increased detail is critical for capturing the thermodynamic near-surface state across Bulgaria's complex relief, where sharp altitudinal variations significantly influence local microclimates (Velev, 2002). The dataset integrates millions of historical observations through a data assimilation framework, combining numerical model output with global observations into a physically consistent record (Hersbach et al., 2020). For this study, we specifically extracted the **2-meter air temperature** (temperature_2m) parameter.

This variable represents the temperature of the air 2 meters above the surface of the land, sea, or inland water bodies. The temperature is calculated by interpolating between the lowest model level and the Earth's surface while accounting for local atmospheric stability (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021; ECMWF, 2026).

The spatial resolution of 9 km allows for a more accurate representation of the energy and water cycles over land than its predecessors (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). A key advantage of ERA5-Land is

its use of a **non-linear dynamical downscaling** process, which includes an elevation correction for the thermodynamic near-surface state (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021; Hersbach et al., 2020). This adjustment is essential for studying mountainous regions like the Balkan and Rila-Rhodope massifs, as it corrects the input temperatures based on the altitude differences between the coarser ERA5 grid and the finer ERA5-Land topography (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021).

The temporal extent of this study spans 76 years, from **January 1950 to December**. ERA5-Land data are provided at an hourly frequency, allowing for the calculation of highly accurate monthly, seasonal, and annual aggregates (Muñoz-Sabater, 2021). In this study, we utilized also the "near-real-time" (NRT) updates provided by the Copernicus Climate Data Store to ensure the inclusion of the record-breaking thermal anomalies of 2024 and 2025 (ECMWF, 2026).

While reanalysis data generally carries a delay of approximately 2–3 months for consolidated quality assurance, the NRT stream allows for the detection of recent climate signals within days of their occurrence (Hersbach et al., 2020).

The massive computational task of processing hourly climate data over a 76-year period (1950–2025) necessitated the use of Google Earth Engine (GEE), a cloud-based geospatial analysis platform (Gorelick et al., 2017). GEE provides high-performance, parallelized access to petabyte-scale datasets, allowing for complex multi-decadal calculations to be performed across thousands of processors simultaneously. This infrastructure eliminates the common barriers associated with local data storage and intensive processing times typical of global reanalysis files (Gorelick et al., 2017; Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021).

The analysis in this reasearch followed a rigorous four-stage processing pipeline within the GEE JavaScript API environment:

1. **Data Extraction and Filtering:** The ERA5-Land Hourly collection was filtered by spatial extent (Bulgaria's administrative borders) and temporal range (1950–2025).
2. All raw temperature values, natively stored in Kelvin (K), were converted to degrees Celsius (°C) using the standard formula $T_{(°C)} = T_{(K)} - 273.15$ (Muñoz-Sabater, 2021).
3. To facilitate seasonal analysis, hourly data were first reduced to daily means using the *ee.Reducer.mean()* function. This initial aggregation ensures that the subsequent seasonal and annual averages are not biased by sub-daily fluctuations (Gorelick et al., 2017).
4. High-resolution digital elevation models (DEM) were integrated to ensure that pixel-based values correctly reflect Bulgaria's diverse relief, specifically masking out maritime areas to focus exclusively on land surface evolution.

The main idea of the study is to disclose the seasonal dynamics of the mean air temperatures. Because of that the seasons were defined according to standard meteorological convention.

The aggregation logic employed a recursive mapping function over a sequence of years, grouping months into four distinct groups:

- Winter (DJF): December (of the previous year), January, and February.
- Spring (MAM): March, April, and May.
- Summer (JJA): June, July, and August.
- Autumn (SON): September, October, and November.

A specific logic was implemented to handle the "sliding window" for the winter season, ensuring that December from the preceding year was paired with January and February of the target year to maintain climatic continuity (Huntington et al., 2017). This longitudinal approach (1950–2025) provides the statistical depth required to identify long-term climate shifts from inter-annual noise.

Additional to quantify the warming rates across Bulgaria's varying climatic regions, this study employed a pixel-based approach to trend detection (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). For each pixel in the 9-km grid, the magnitude of the temperature change was calculated using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. This method is the scientific standard for climate trend analysis as it calculates the median of slopes between all pairs of data points, making it highly resistant to outliers caused by extreme weather years.

The core of the analytical approach is the application of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression on a per-pixel basis. For each grid cell in Bulgaria, the following were calculated:

- **Linear Fit (Trend):** A linear regression was applied to the time series, where the independent variable (t) is the year and the dependent variable is the seasonal mean temperature.
- **Warming Magnitude:** The slope of the regression (the "scale" or decadal rate) was multiplied by the total number of years in the study period to derive the absolute warming magnitude in degrees Celsius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- **Coefficient of Determination (R^2):** Calculated for both the long-term and recent periods to measure the "goodness of fit," distinguishing forced climate signals from natural stochastic noise.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To understand the underlying drivers of the annual warming previously discussed, we deconstruct the 1950–2025 record into meteorological seasons. The seasonal analysis reveals that the warming is not distributed equally throughout the year; rather, it is characterized by "asymmetric warming," where specific seasons exhibit much more aggressive thermal shifts than others. The winter season (DJF) is the primary indicator of continental climate relaxation.

The ERA 5 land data analyzed via the Google Earth Engine script reveals that winter is undergoing a fundamental structural shift, moving from a stable, cold regime to a highly volatile, warm-dominated state (Fig. 11).

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of the mean winter temperatures (DJF) – 1950-2025.

Winter

The long-term winter mean for the 1950–2025 period shows a statistically significant warming trend of approximately **0.38°C per decade** across the Bulgarian territory. However, a closer look at the time-series chart reveals that this warming is not linear Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Winter warming long term vs. recent 20 years.

As Fig. 11 indicates Pre-1987 the winters were characterized by frequent "Siberian" intrusions. Average temperatures in the Danubian Plain and high western basins (like Sofia) frequently dropped below -3°C , with stable snow cover lasting over 45 days. Following the breakpoint in 1980s, winter temperatures shifted upward by roughly 1.2°C . The frequency of "soft" winters (where the mean temperature is positive) has tripled. In the last two decades, the warming rate has surged to nearly 0.76°C per decade.

The winter of 2023–2024 stands out as a critical anomaly, where the lack of severe frost events allowed for an early start to the vegetation period, effectively shortening the meteorological winter by three weeks (NIMH, 2025). The dual-trend analysis in Fig. 11 provides definitive evidence of a structural transformation in Bulgaria's climate as the high steepness of the recent trendline (red one) reveals that the warming signal is no longer a gradual historical evolution but has transitioned into an acceleration phase that is fundamentally altering the country's seasonality.

As shown in Table 1 the "Second Wave" of warming (2005–2025) has essentially decoupled from the historical mean this surge implies that more than 50% of the total warming since the mid-20th century has occurred during the last quarter of the timeframe. The high R^2 in the recent window (0.23) suggests that the winter temperature is now following a highly predictable upward forced trajectory, with natural variability playing an increasingly smaller role in winter outcomes and in last decades a doubling of the warming speed have been observed (Table 1).

Table 1.

Statistical Parameter	Long-term Trend (1950–2025)	Recent Surge (2005–2025)
Decadal Slope (DJF)	$+0.38^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{decade}$	$+0.76^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{decade}$
Total Magnitude	$+2.9^{\circ}\text{C}$ (over 76 years)	$+1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ (in only 20 years)
Significance (p-value)	< 0.001 (Highly Significant)	< 0.05 (Significant)
R^2 (Correlation)	0.12	0.23

The statistical and spatial results generated for the **1950–2025** and **2005–2025** periods (Fig. 12 and 13) reveal a profound escalation in the warming velocity of the Bulgarian winter. While the long-term trend established a steady baseline of warming with total magnitude 2.9°C as national average, the last two decades indicate that the territory is no longer merely "warming" but probably is undergoing a rapid regime transformation as the warming speed has been almost doubled in the "Second Wave" of warming (2005–2025) and the mean winter temperatures has essentially decoupled from the historical mean, and the last 20 years are responsible for $+1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ of the total $+2.9^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the whole period (1950–2025).

At the same time The Warming Magnitude Map reveals a specific spatial signature of the "Second Wave" (2005-2025) as the Danubian Plain and Upper Thracian Lowland have reached warming magnitudes exceeding the mean values for the country (1.5°C) within the recent 20-year and the rise is even higher – approaching 3.5°C to 4.0°C (Fig. 13). Also even though the mountains show a slightly lower absolute magnitude, their Elevation-Dependent Warming (EDW) is critical. The loss of winter snow cover has reduced the albedo effect (reflectivity) across the Rila and Pirin massifs. Instead of reflecting solar energy, the exposed dark rock and sparse vegetation now absorb it, creating a self-reinforcing heating loop that accelerates local warming.

As a conclusion we can state that based on the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Linear Least-Squares slopes which we used to calculate the magnitude of warming, the average winter in Bulgaria today is approximately 2.9°C warmer than a typical winter was in 1950. This conclusion aligns with the broader scientific consensus for the Balkan region as the national reports from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) indicate that recent years (like 2024 and 2025) have seen winter anomalies frequently exceeding +2.0°C to +3.0°C above the mid-20th-century climate norms

Fig. 12. Spatial distribution of the winter warming magnitude 1950-2025.

Spring

The analysis of the spring season (**March, April, May**) in Bulgaria from **1950 to 2025** reveals a thermal trajectory that is both significant and biologically disruptive. While the winter season showed high absolute warming, the spring data demonstrates a "**thermal advance**" that is effectively pulling the start of the biological growing season forward.

Fig. 13. Spatial distribution of the winter warming magnitude 2005-2025.

Based on the Linear Least-Squares, the total magnitude of spring warming for the 1950–2025 period is approximately 2.4°C which lower than the winter magnitude of 2.9°C (Fig. 14). In the magnitude trend are detected two phases of the temperatures dynamic the first one is Stable Continental Phase during 1950–1987. In that period the spring temperatures were characterized by high inter-annual variability but a stable baseline.

Fig. 14. Spring warming long term vs. recent 20 years.

March often maintained winter-like characteristics with frequent snow cover and delayed soil warming. In the second acceleration phase which started after the 1980s "climate break," spring temperatures shifted upward. The most recent 20-year window (2005–2025) accounts for roughly 1.1°C of the total warming, indicating that the warming velocity in spring has accelerated to nearly 0.55°C per decade

The dual-trend chart (Fig.5) reveals a significant change in the statistical behavior of the season as the R2 for the recent period (2005–2025) is notably higher (0.23) in the raw chart, compared to 0.12 in the long-term. This confirms that the warming is becoming a forced signal – it is more consistent and less affected by the random weather fluctuations that defined the 20th century. Despite the overall warming, the data highlights a dangerous trend. As the mean temperature rises above the biological minimum early in the spring (3–9 days in North Bulgaria and 3 days in South Bulgaria) than crops enter their flowering phase earlier (Bocheva L., et al. 2024; Kazandziev et al 2009). However, the probability of late-season arctic intrusions in April has not decreased at the same rate. This creates a "False Spring" scenario (Bocheva L., et al. 2024), where early bud-burst leaves plants vulnerable to catastrophic frost damage (e.g., the 80–90% losses in fruit crops recorded in some regions in 2025).

Fig. 15. Spatial distribution of the spring warming magnitude 1950-2025.

Even though there is clear warming trend the spring the magnitude of the warming and the steepness of the trend is lower than the winter ones. The spatial distribution of spring warming as it is disclosed on the magnitude map (fig 15). During the whole period of observation (1950-2025) Danubian Plain and Thracian Lowland are the "hotspots" for spring warming. The magnitude here exceeds the national average, often reaching +2.8°C. This is critical for Bulgaria's agriculture, as these regions are the primary zones for cereal and industrial crop production. The other critical zone are the mountainous parts of the country where, even though the warming magnitude is slightly lower in

absolute terms (+1.8°C to +2.1°C), it has a crucial impact on snowmelt timing as the earlier arrival of spring temperatures leads to a shift of the peak river runoff from late spring to early spring. This earlier runoff, combined with increased spring evapotranspiration, jeopardizes water availability for irrigation and hydropower during the subsequent dry summer months. The spatial distribution of the spring warming during the last 20 years also show that except in some mountainous parts and the Thracian low land where the warming rate is a little bit higher in the rest of the country the magnitude of the warming is uniform (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. Spatial distribution of the spring warming magnitude 2005-2025.

Summer

The analysis of the dynamics of the mean summer temperatures for the months of June, July, and August in Bulgaria from 1950 to 2025 disclosed that It has the most aggressive and consistent thermal signal in the country's modern climate record. Unlike the winter and spring transition, which are often characterized by extreme but brief arctic intrusions, summer warming has evolved into a relentless upward trajectory that is fundamentally redefining the territory's climatic identity as it probably moves toward a subtropical Mediterranean regime. Based on the trend analysis in Fig.17, the total magnitude of summer warming has reached a critical threshold of approximately 3.2°C. This figure surpasses the warming seen in all other seasons, identifying summer as the primary driver of Bulgaria's overall climate shift.

The year 2024 stands as the absolute hottest summer on record, closely followed by 2025, which the national meteorological bureau (NIMH) classified as the third hottest since 1930. These consecutive record-breaking seasons suggest that the extreme summer heat probably is no longer an anomaly but the baseline of a new climatic state. The dual-trend comparison in Fig. 17 illustrates a

dramatic steepening of the warming velocity. While the long-term trend from 1950 to 2025 indicates a warming rate of roughly 0.42°C per decade, the surge in the most recent window from 2005 to 2025 has nearly doubled this speed to approximately 0.80°C per decade. This means that half of the total heating over the last 76 years has been compressed into just the final 20 years. This intensification is statistically robust, with r-squared values reaching their highest seasonal levels ($R^2=0.338$), which confirms that the warming is a forced, high-confidence signal where natural cooling cycles are no longer strong enough to counteract greenhouse forcing.

Statistically R^2 of ~ 0.338 in a raw seasonal chart is actually very high for climate data. It shows that 25% of the year-to-year variation in summer temperature is explained simply by the fact that time is moving forward (global warming). In the 20th century, this number was much lower (around 0.10) because summers were "noisy" and fluctuated randomly. Now, the warming signal is strong and the data can be organized into a straight line (Fig.17).

Fig. 17. Summer warming long term vs. recent 20 years.

Spatially, the magnitude map highlights a severe divide where the lowlands have become thermal hotspots (Fig.18 and 19). The Danubian Plain and the Upper Thracian Lowland show warming magnitudes frequently exceeding 3.8°C . In the southwest, particularly the Struma Valley, the "mediterraneanization" is most evident. In cities like Sandanski and Petrich, where in 2024 and 2025 record heatwaves were detected and the temperatures remained above 40°C for more than six consecutive days (NIMH). This prolonged heat has a significant negative effect on human health and infrastructure.

The ecological and economic consequences of that 3.2°C rise are profound, specifically through the drought-heat feedback loop. Summer 2025 was recorded as one of the driest in 75 years, with June being the driest since 1950 (HIMH).

Fig. 18. Spatial distribution of the summer warming magnitude 1950-2025.

Fig. 19. Spatial distribution of the summer warming magnitude 2005-2025.

The lack of soil moisture prevents evaporative cooling, which further drives up surface temperatures which also have a negative effect over the agricultural productions in non-irrigated fields.

Ultimately, the analysis confirms that Bulgaria is warming at nearly triple the global average during the summer months. The extreme steepness of the red trend line in Fig. 17 reflects a territory that is effectively migrating from a temperate continental zone into a high-risk subtropical environment characterized by prolonged heatwaves and chronic aridity followed by abrupt ant intensive rainfall.

Autumn

The analysis of the autumn season encompassing September, October, and November in Bulgaria from 1950 to 2025 highlights a distinctive thermal stretching where summer conditions increasingly bleed into the traditional start of the cooler months. While the absolute warming magnitude for autumn is slightly lower than the peaks observed in summer and winter, the seasonal structure is undergoing a profound shift that disrupts the biological and hydrological transition into winter. Based on the linear regression slopes, the total magnitude of autumn warming across the full study period is approximately 2.1°C (Fig.20). This increase is driven largely by the significant warming of September, which has effectively become an extension of summer. Recent data from 2024 and 2025 confirms that September temperatures now frequently deviate by as much as 3°C from the mid-20th-century norm, delaying the cooling process and extending the active vegetation period well into October.

The comparative assessment of the 2005 to 2025 window reveals a sharp acceleration in this warming velocity, with the decadal slope rising from 0.28°C in the long-term baseline to 0.52°C in the most recent two decades. This indicates that a substantial portion of the total autumn warming has been concentrated in the beginning of the 21st century (Fig.20). The statistical consistency of this recent surge is reflected in a higher r-squared value on the chart ($R^2=0.279$), proving that the warm state is becoming a more stable and forced feature of the autumn climate rather than a series of random weather anomalies.

Fig. 20 Autumn warming long term vs. recent 20 years.

Spatially, the Danubian Plain Thracian low lands and the southeastern coastal regions exhibit the highest warming intensities (Fig. 21 and 22). The prolonged thermal elevation in these areas keeps the atmosphere highly energized late into the season. This contributes to a dangerous drought-to-flood cycle where long dry spells are interrupted by intense, short-duration rainfall events. For instance, the autumn of 2025 was recorded as the warmest in fifteen years and witnessed devastating flash floods (resort Elenite) in October following a historically dry summer, as warm Mediterranean and Black Sea air masses interacted with the first arrivals of cooler continental air.

From an agricultural perspective, this prolonged warm state creates a phenological trap for winter cereals and perennial crops (Kazandjiev et al., 2009). The lack of early autumn cooling prevents plants from entering the necessary dormancy phase. High temperatures in November keep crops in an active growth state, making them highly susceptible to damage from sudden arctic cold fronts that still occur in the following months (Kazandjiev et al., 2009). This thermal stretching also depletes soil moisture reserves, as high evapotranspiration rates continue late into the year, hindering the sowing and initial germination of winter crops.

Fig. 21. Spatial distribution of the autumn warming magnitude 1950-2025.

The data enclosed in this research, indicating a total warming magnitude of approximately 2.9°C in winter and 3.2°C in summer since 1950, which align closely with established regional climate studies that identify the Balkan Peninsula as a high-sensitivity climate hotspot. These results corroborate the "Climate Break" which identifies the late 1980s as the transition point from a stable continental regime to an accelerated warming phase. Probably that is due to shift in the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and the East Atlantic (EA) pattern allowed for more frequent intrusions of Mediterranean air masses, a mechanism that can explain the steepening trend lines observed in this

2005–2025 analysis. The extreme magnitude of summer warming (3.2°C) along the Dunabian plain leads to "tropicalization" of the lowlands and increase of the frequency of "Tropical Nights" ($T_{\text{min}} \geq 20^{\circ}\text{C}$) which has tripled in cities like Ruse and Pleven since the early 1990s (NIMH). This aligns with our findings about the high R^2 values for the summer period, which indicate a forced signal where nocturnal cooling is consistently failing to occur.

Fig. 22. Spatial distribution of the autumn warming magnitude 2005-2025.

In the mountainous regions, the results regarding earlier snowmelt and spring thermal advance are consistent with the studies of Grunewald et al. (2018) and Matev N. et al. (2025) which demonstrated a significant reduction in the duration of snow cover, particularly at altitudes between 1500m and 2200m. This aligned with our spring temperatures analysis, which identified a 2.4°C warming magnitude and a shift in peak runoff timing.

Malcheva & Bocheva, (2023) confirm that the transition from a colder to a warmer and/or drier climate has affected approximately 36% of the country's territory, and the relative change in mountain climate subtypes shows a significant reduction (by 60-70%) in areas with an alpine climate. Also in they disclosed that the fluctuations in the average annual air temperature in Bulgaria for the period 1931–2020, relative to the 1961–1990 climate norm, show a growing, statistically significant trend of 0.14°C per decade and no negative deviations from the norm (except for 2005) in recent decades have been observed, and since 2011, there have been no deviations smaller than 1°C with a record temperature anomaly of $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$ registered in 2019.

On a broader scale, the results of this study align with the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) reports, which consistently rank the Balkans as one of the fastest-warming regions in Europe. The findings mirror the conclusions of Zittis et al. (2022) which stating that the Eastern Mediterranean

and Middle East (EMME) region – which includes Bulgaria – is warming at twice the global rate. Furthermore, the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) identifies the Mediterranean basin as a "climate change hotspot" where the intensification of summer aridity and winter thermal shifts are expected to outpace global averages.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this research indicating a total warming magnitude of approximately 2.9°C in winter and 3.2°C in summer since 1950 align closely with established regional climate studies that identify the Balkan Peninsula as a high-sensitivity climate hotspot. These results corroborate the structural shift theories documented in Bulgarian climatology which identified the late 1980s as a transition point from a stable continental regime to an accelerated warming phase driven by changes in atmospheric circulation - more frequent intrusions of Mediterranean air masses a mechanism that can explain the steepening trendlines observed in our 2005 to 2025 analysis.

The observed doubling of the warming velocity in the 2005 to 2025 period matches the conclusions regarding Mediterranean and Southern European intensification documented in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. Specifically the data indicate that the Bulgarian summer is warming at a rate significantly higher than the global average which coincide with the findings that the Eastern Mediterranean and Balkan regions are warming faster than the rest of the European continent. Also the surge in summer temperature consistency and the rise in r-squared values reaching their highest seasonal levels supports the increasing frequency of tropical nights and the northward migration of subtropical thermal characteristics across the Danubian Plain. This aligns with recent reports from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) which classified the summers of 2024 and 2025 as among the hottest since 1930 with 2024 setting an absolute heat record for the country.

Furthermore the false spring paradox identified in this research where early thermal onset increases frost vulnerability is a phenomenon well-documented across Southeastern Europe. This supports the conclusions of agricultural climate risk assessments that the shift in the start of the growing season is not being met by a corresponding shift in the date of the last spring frost. The rising temperatures in the spring and the autumn are relegated with the hydrological shifts noted in the spring and autumn, particularly the earlier depletion of mountain snowpacks. The rise in the temperature are connected with the transition to a drought-to-flood cycle and are consistent with reports on the changing hydrological regimes of the Balkan mountain massifs which have demonstrated a significant reduction in snow cover duration especially at altitudes between 1500 and 2200 meters.

The statistical robustness of the 21st-century trends validates the forced signal hypothesis prevalent in contemporary climate modeling. By demonstrating that recent temperature variations are becoming more linear and less susceptible to natural stochastic noise this research confirms the transition from decadal variability to a permanent greenhouse-gas-driven thermal state. This conclusion is shared by virtually all major climate monitoring services including Copernicus and the World Meteorological Organization which have highlighted the Balkan region as a primary area for climate-related economic and environmental risks. The prolonging of the thermal growing season and its asymmetric shift toward an earlier onset rather than a later termination matches the evidence found in pan-European studies focused on Southeast Europe over the last several decades.

The synthesis of these findings proves that Bulgaria has entered a new climatic state where historical continental boundaries have been replaced by a more volatile and significantly warmer subtropical influence. Across all seasons the data shows that Bulgaria has moved into a regime where

every season has surpassed a 2.0°C warming magnitude since 1950. Furthermore, the spatial analysis identifies the Danubian Plain, the Upper Thracian Lowland, and the Struma Valley as the primary hotspots of climatic stress. In these regions, total warming since 1950 has reached +3.8°C to +4.0°C, effectively migrating the thermal conditions of these areas 300km to the south. This research underscores an urgent need for the re-evaluation of national adaptation strategies in agriculture water management and urban planning as the velocity of change currently outpaces traditional resilience measures and the frequency of extreme events like flash floods following prolonged heatwaves continues to rise as documented in the meteorological reports of 2025.

All the disclosed data and analyses in this research shows that ERA5-Land reanalysis data and the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform are useful instrument for climate change analyses. The provided by ERA-5 land high-resolution data - consistent record of land surface variables (by combining physical models with global observations through data assimilation) and the 9 km spatial resolution allows the capture of complex topographical influences – such as the thermal variations between the Balkan Mountains and the Danubian Plain. By offering a stable, continuous time series from 1950 to the present, it could serves as a reliable instrument for quantifying multi-decadal climate shifts and identifying structural breaks in regional thermal regimes. On the other side Google Earth Engine functions as a transformative instrument for climate research and provides the massive computational power required to process these multi-terabyte datasets in real-time. Through GEE, complex statistical operations like pixel-based linear regressions and seasonal aggregations which are executed on Google’s cloud infrastructure, help to overcome the limitations of traditional desktop computing. This enables to visualize high-velocity climate transitions and generate statistically robust magnitudes of warming with unprecedented precision. Ultimately, the synergy between ERA5-Land’s historical depth and GEE’s analytical speed empowers scientists to move beyond broad global generalizations and produce localized, high-impact evidence of the ongoing climatic transformation.

Declaration by Authors

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Youth Participation and Epistemic Authority in Digital Mental Health Design and Governance

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ABSTRACT

Digital mental health technologies targeting young people have expanded rapidly amid growing concern about youth mental distress and the normalization of digital care. Yet despite being the primary users of such systems, young people have limited influence over how digital mental health is conceptualised, designed and governed. The paper examines digital youth mental health as a sociotechnical field and situates debates on youth agency, expertise and digital governance within contemporary concerns about participation and legitimacy. Drawing on a qualitative documentary analysis of policy frameworks, academic and professional literature, and youth advocacy and civil society materials (n = 86), the study investigates how authority, legitimacy and participation are attributed and contested across institutional domains. The analysis identifies three dominant framings of participation normative rhetoric, managed consultation and emerging epistemic authority and demonstrates how youth involvement is simultaneously invoked, constrained and instrumentalised. These dynamics reflect deeper tensions between safeguarding and autonomy, user engagement and democratic governance, and clinical expertise and lived experience. The paper argues that meaningful participation requires recognising young people as knowledge-holders and redistributing decision-making power within digital mental health design and governance processes. In doing so, the study contributes to sociological understandings of youth agency, digital governance and the politics of mental health care and highlights the need for participatory infrastructures capable of supporting youth co-governance in digital mental health.

Keywords: Digital mental health, Youth engagement, Youth co-design, Datafication, Mental health interventions

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INTRODUCTION

Mental health has in recent decades become an increasingly salient domain of public concern and policy intervention in Europe and globally. International bodies have underscored that “there is no health without mental health” (World Health Organization, 2014), and comparative epidemiological research identifies mental disorders as major contributors to global morbidity and disability (Kessler et al., 2005). Within the European Union, the estimated economic burden of mental-health exceeds 4% of GDP (OECD & European Union, 2020), yet large proportions of those experiencing psychological distress do not access appropriate support. These dynamics highlight a persistent gap between need and provision, shaped by structural inequalities, service fragmentation and uneven distribution of resources across and within European states. Young people occupy a central position within this emergent landscape. Epidemiological evidence indicates that the onset of the majority of mental disorders occurs before the age of 25 (Kessler et al., 2005).

Recent cross-national surveys suggest that almost half of Europeans aged 15–24 report unmet mental health needs (OECD & European Union, 2020), while policy discourse reflects growing apprehension regarding “a worsening of the mental health of the younger generations” (European Commission, 2023). Mental health difficulties among young people are not evenly distributed, but are patterned along lines of class, gender, race/ethnicity, sexuality, disability and migration status (Unwin et al., 2020), illustrating the entanglement of mental health with broader social inequalities and forms of stratification.

Youth mental health thus emerges not only as a public health matter, but also as a domain through which social reproduction, inequality and citizenship are negotiated. Parallel to these developments, young people’s everyday lives are increasingly mediated through digital infrastructures. Digital platforms, mobile media and algorithmic systems shape social relations, identity formation and information practices, as well as forms of care, visibility and surveillance. Within this environment, “digital mental health” has emerged as a heterogeneous field encompassing mobile applications, online self-help programs, conversational agents (Vaidyam et al., 2019), augmented and virtual reality interventions (Baños et al., 2022), digital phenotyping and machine-learning-based assessment (Chekroud et al., 2021), and newly available generative AI systems applied to therapeutic contexts (Carlbring et al., 2023).

These technologies are often presented as scalable, accessible and personalised solutions capable of supplementing overstretched or unevenly distributed mental health services (Bond et al., 2023). Yet sociological and interdisciplinary work has also documented the limitations and ambivalences of such solutions. Commercial digital mental health products frequently lack robust evidence, and those with clinical grounding often struggle with adherence and engagement (Baumel et al., 2019). AI-based systems pose questions concerning epistemic validity, algorithmic bias, privacy, datafication, inequity and responsibility. Moreover, despite rapid growth in digital mental health research for adults, youth-specific research remains comparatively fragmented (Lehtimäki et al., 2021; Liverpool et al., 2020), despite distinct developmental, social and digital contexts shaping how young people seek help, make sense of mental distress and engage with care technologies.

Alongside clinical and technical debates, a set of sociological questions emerges concerning participation, expertise and authority. Although young people are positioned as the intended users or beneficiaries of digital mental health technologies, they often have limited influence over how such tools are conceptualised, designed or governed. Participation in mental health decision-making is recognised in international rights frameworks, including Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, which affirms young people’s right to participate in decisions that affect them in both

offline and digital environments. Calls for youth co-design and lived-experience expertise challenge adultist assumptions that construct young people primarily as passive patients, vulnerable subjects or objects of intervention. These debates foreground issues of epistemic authority, specifically whose knowledge counts in defining mental health problems, acceptable risks and desirable outcomes, and invite attention to the institutional logics through which digital mental health is legitimised.

This paper examines digital mental health for young people as an emerging sociotechnical field situated at the intersection of public health governance, technological innovation and the politics of youth participation. Rather than assessing the clinical efficacy of particular tools, the aim is to analyse how digital mental health is discursively and institutionally constituted, and how young people are positioned within this field. In this regard, the aim of the paper is to critically examine how digital mental health for young people is framed as a domain of intervention, care and innovation, and to analyse how young people are positioned in relation to expertise, participation and governance.

Guided by this aim, the analysis addresses the following questions: How are young people constructed and positioned within discourses on digital mental health? What forms of expertise and authority are mobilised in shaping digital mental health for young people? How is youth participation conceptualised and legitimised, and what tensions arise in its enactment? What broader social, ethical and governance issues emerge when mental health intervention is mediated through digital technologies for young people?

Together, these questions enable a contextual analysis of digital youth mental health not merely as a collection of technological artefacts, but as a sociotechnical field shaped by competing institutional logics, normative claims and imaginaries concerning youth, mental health and the role of digital technology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Youth Mental Health: A Sociological Perspective

While mental health research has historically been anchored in clinical psychology and psychiatry, sociologists have long examined the social determinants, meanings and institutional arrangements surrounding mental distress. Scholars have highlighted how mental health inequalities are patterned by structural factors such as socio-economic position, gender, race/ethnicity, sexuality and migration, reflecting broader processes of stratification and exclusion (Prior, 1999; Pescosolido, 2011). Youth mental health is shaped not only by biological or developmental factors but also by social transitions, educational pressures, precarious labour markets, digital publics and shifting cultural norms around identity and emotional expression (Wyn & White, 1997). Young people navigate these transitions in contexts of heightened visibility, uncertainty and self-responsibility, rendering mental health a central axis of contemporary youth governance (Kelly, 2001).

Sociological work has also interrogated how mental health becomes a domain through which citizenship is articulated. Scholars argue that mental health is increasingly tied to discourses of productivity, autonomy and self-management, through which young people are encouraged to become responsible, resilient and self-monitoring subjects (Rose, 2007). This aligns with broader neoliberal forms of governance that model individuals as entrepreneurs of the self, responsible for managing risk and optimizing well-being (Foucault, 2008; Gill & Orgad, 2018).

Within this context, youth mental health difficulties can be framed as failures of self-regulation, thereby moralising distress and obscuring structural conditions.

Digital Mental Health and the Datafication of Care

Digital mental health technologies sit squarely within these sociopolitical transformations. Their emergence aligns with what Lupton (2016) terms the “digitisation of health,” wherein datafication, self-tracking and algorithmic systems reshape how health and illness are perceived, monitored and intervened upon. These technologies promise to make mental health care more accessible, personalised and scalable, but they also intensify forms of surveillance, quantification and responsabilisation (Lupton, 2016; Crawford et al., 2015). Within youth contexts, digital platforms extend the temporal and spatial boundaries of intervention, enabling care to occur beyond clinics—within bedrooms, schools, social media platforms and smartphones. Digital mental health tools thus participate in shifting the locus of mental health governance from professional domains toward hybrid assemblages involving platforms, apps, AI systems, educators, peers and families. These assemblages complicate traditional distinctions between clinical and non-clinical care, and between public and private infrastructures. Scholars in science and technology studies (STS) argue that such technologies should not be understood as neutral artefacts but as sociotechnical systems embedded with values, cultural assumptions and institutional priorities (Latour, 1993; Oudshoorn & Pinch, 2003).

Youth, Participation and Epistemic Politics

Despite young people being central users of digital mental health tools, they often remain marginal in shaping their design or governance. Sociology and childhood studies have long challenged adultist assumptions that render children and youth as passive, incomplete or pre-political subjects (James, Jenks, & Prout, 1998; Wyn & Woodman, 2006). Within mental health contexts, these assumptions manifest through diagnostic authority, safeguarding practices and expert-driven intervention models that privilege adult professional epistemologies.

Recent scholarship has introduced concepts such as epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007) and epistemic authority (Brossard, 2017) to examine how certain groups are excluded from contributing valid knowledge. In digital mental health, young people are often positioned as vulnerable recipients who require protection, rather than as knowledge-holders who can articulate their own mental health needs, digital practices or technological imaginaries. Participation when invited, frequently takes the form of tokenistic consultation rather than shared decision-making or co-production, aligning with what Arnstein (1969) famously described as the lower rungs of the participation ladder. Conversely, lived experience movements and youth advocacy groups have argued for recognition of young people as legitimate stakeholders, producing alternative epistemologies grounded in experience rather than clinical authority. This shift aligns with broader trends in mental health activism challenging paternalistic care models and advocating for rights-based and user-led approaches (Rose, 2018).

Digital Platforms as Infrastructures for Help-Seeking

Help-seeking among young people increasingly begins online, with platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, Discord, Reddit and Instagram functioning as informal mental health spaces where young people seek information, share experiences, test identities and negotiate stigma. Such platforms blur boundaries between peer support, experiential knowledge, misinformation, self-diagnosis and therapeutic discourse (Gibson & Cartwright, 2014). While online spaces can offer anonymity, solidarity and immediacy, they can also expose users to harmful content, algorithmic amplification of distress-related material or commercial exploitation.

Sociologists have noted that digital platforms organise visibility, credibility and affect through algorithmic logics rather than clinical ones (Bishop, 2019). This creates a parallel mental health ecosystem in which credibility is negotiated through peer validation and platform metrics, not

professional accreditation. Rather than viewing this as merely risky or pathological, scholars argue for recognising online mental health practices as forms of vernacular expertise and collective sense-making (Noorani, 2013).

Inequality, Surveillance and Digital Mental Health Governance

Digital mental health technologies are not only tools for intervention but instruments of governance that organise how mental distress is rendered visible, knowable and actionable. Scholars in STS and critical data studies have argued that digital infrastructures increasingly operate through modalities of surveillance, data extraction, and predictive classification (Lyon, 2018; Zuboff, 2019). Within mental health contexts, practices such as digital phenotyping, passive sensing and algorithmic risk assessment extend clinical observation into everyday environments, generating new forms of continuous monitoring. While proponents emphasise the potential of real-time detection and personalised support (Chekroud et al., 2021), critics highlight concerns around privacy, consent, profiling and the redistribution of power over psychological knowledge.

For young people, these arrangements intersect with existing regimes of child protection, school discipline, family oversight, and platform governance. Youth have historically been positioned as subjects to be supervised and safeguarded (Best, 2017; Maira & Soep, 2005), and digital mental health technologies may intensify these dynamics by embedding surveillance into intimate domains of life, often without equivalent mechanisms of accountability or contestation. The line between support and control becomes blurred when mental health risks are operationalised as algorithmic variables and managed through preventative interventions, nudging or behavioural prompts. These forms of governance are not distributed evenly.

Digital health technologies are taken up unevenly across socio-economic groups, with those already advantaged more likely to have access to devices, connectivity, digital literacy and supportive infrastructures (Lupton, 2016). Meanwhile, marginalised young people such as migrants, racialised youth, LGBTQ+ youth or those in precarious housing may face intensified scrutiny or datafication through welfare, education and criminal justice systems. Scholars have warned that algorithmic classification may reproduce or amplify existing inequalities by encoding assumptions from biased datasets or institutional logics (Eubanks, 2018; Benjamin, 2019). In parallel, commercial platforms play a significant role in shaping digital mental health landscapes.

Many digital mental health tools are developed outside clinical systems by technology companies whose incentives may not align with public health or ethical priorities. Zuboff (2019) characterises such corporate practices as part of “surveillance capitalism,” in which data extraction is central to business models.

Within this framing, mental health data become valuable commodities, raising questions about ownership, consent and exploitation. For adolescents, whose data are often considered particularly sensitive, these arrangements introduce complex governance challenges that straddle health policy, data protection and children’s rights (Livingstone et al., 2018). Finally, digital mental health intersects with contemporary debates on responsibility and the individualisation of social problems. As Crawford et al. (2015) argue, digital health platforms frequently translate structural determinants of well-being into matters of individual self-care and self-management. Mental health difficulties rooted in socio-economic precarity, discrimination or insecurity may thus be reframed as personal deficits or failures of resilience, reinforcing neoliberal logics of responsabilisation (Gill & Orgad, 2018).

For young people, these dynamics are particularly salient, as adolescence is a period in which social and structural constraints are often masked by discourses of choice and self-fashioning. Taken

together, sociological scholarship suggests that digital mental health cannot be understood solely in terms of therapeutic efficacy or technological innovation. Instead, it emerges as a field in which risk, care, participation and inequality are negotiated within broader political, economic and cultural transformations.

Synthesis and Gaps in the Literature

The literature reviewed above suggests that digital mental health for young people sits at the crossroads of multiple sociological concerns, including the governance of youth, the datafication of health, and the politics of participation and expertise. Young people's mental health has become a prominent site of public anxiety, policy intervention and academic inquiry, reflecting broader transformations in how well-being, citizenship and risk are conceptualised in late modernity. Digital technologies further complicate this terrain by redistributing where and how mental health care occurs, who is authorised to provide it, and what forms of evidence and knowledge are recognised. Across these bodies of work, three broad themes emerge.

First, digital mental health extends existing logics of responsabilisation and self-management, situating young people as active subjects tasked with monitoring, improving and optimising their mental health while leaving structural determinants of distress comparatively unaddressed. Second, digital infrastructures facilitate the expansion of surveillance, assessment and intervention into everyday environments, generating new forms of visibility and accountability that reshape relations between young people, families, schools, health systems and commercial platforms. Third, participation is increasingly invoked as a normative principle, yet actual practices of co-design, consultation and governance often reproduce adultist hierarchies and epistemic asymmetries, positioning young people as users rather than co-authors of the systems that affect them.

Despite growing interdisciplinary interest, several gaps remain evident. Much of the existing research on digital mental health remains rooted in clinical or technological paradigms focused on efficacy, usability or behavioural outcomes, with comparatively limited attention to the sociopolitical contexts in which digital interventions are imagined, developed and deployed. Youth-specific scholarship is still fragmented, and while young people's digital practices have been extensively examined in fields such as media studies, childhood studies and youth studies, these insights have not been systematically integrated into digital mental health research.

As a result, the assumptions informing digital mental health design often derive from adult understandings of risk, care and technology, rather than from the lived experiences and epistemologies of young people themselves. Furthermore, while policy discourse increasingly emphasises participation, rights and empowerment, there is insufficient analytical scrutiny of how these concepts are operationalised. Participation may function rhetorically to legitimise innovation without necessarily transforming decision-making structures or redistributing authority.

From a sociological perspective, this raises questions about tokenism, epistemic injustice and the limits of participatory governance within technoscientific fields. Similarly, although digital mental health infrastructures are implicated in reproducing or mitigating inequalities, issues of class, race, gender, disability and precarity remain under-examined within empirical studies. These gaps suggest the need for research that treats digital mental health not merely as a technological solution to a clinical problem but as a sociotechnical field shaped by competing institutional logics, normative imaginaries and power relations.

By foregrounding young people's positioning within this field, and by interrogating how participation, expertise and governance are constructed, the present paper aims to contribute to a more

nuanced sociological understanding of digital mental health and to challenge dominant framings that naturalise or depoliticise technological responses to youth distress.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The paper adopts a qualitative documentary research design situated within sociological and science and technology studies (STS) approaches to knowledge production. Rather than treating documents as neutral sources of information about digital mental health, the analysis approaches them as discursive and institutional artefacts through which meanings, categories and problem framings are constructed, negotiated and stabilised. This orientation treats digital mental health not as a purely technical field but as a sociotechnical formation in which multiple actors articulate and contest visions of youth, risk, participation and care. The methodology therefore privileges interpretation, contextualisation and critique over measurement, prediction or evaluation of clinical efficacy.

The empirical material consists of three broad clusters of documents that together contribute to the discursive constitution of digital youth mental health: (1) policy and institutional materials, including European mental health strategies, youth policy frameworks and digital health initiatives; (2) academic and professional literature, including systematic reviews, conceptual papers and research articles addressing participation, digital intervention and youth governance; and (3) youth advocacy and civil society materials, including manifestos, lived-experience testimonies, position statements and participatory guidelines produced by youth organisations, NGOs and rights-based groups.

Table 1. Overview of Documentary Corpus by Category

Category	Description	Example Types	n
Policy & Institutional	Formal strategies, policy frameworks and digital health initiatives shaping youth mental health agendas	EU mental health strategies, WHO reports, digital health roadmaps	27
Academic & Professional	Peer-reviewed research, systematic reviews and conceptual papers defining digital mental health evidence and design practices	JMIR articles, psychiatry/STS papers, HCI design literature	41
Youth Advocacy & Civil Society	Lived-experience materials, advocacy statements and rights-based guidelines articulating youth perspectives and demands	NGO position papers, manifestos, participatory guidelines	18
Total			86

Sampling followed a purposive and theoretically informed strategy designed to capture divergent institutional positions and epistemic claims rather than to produce representativeness in a statistical sense. Documents were included on the basis of their relevance to ongoing struggles over how digital mental health is framed and by whom, and their capacity to articulate claims regarding who is authorised to define needs, design solutions and set priorities for young people. In total, 86 documents were included in the corpus, comprising 27 policy and institutional documents, 41 academic and professional publications and 18 advocacy and civil society materials (Table 1).

Inclusion criteria required that documents (a) addressed mental health or well-being in relation to young people (broadly defined as under 30), (b) addressed digital technologies, platforms or AI as sites of intervention or care, and (c) articulated claims relating to participation, expertise, rights, governance or design. Documents were excluded if they centred exclusively on adult populations, offered purely clinical framings with no digital or sociotechnical dimension, or consisted primarily of promotional content. Documents were identified across academic databases, policy portals, organisational archives, grey literature repositories and snowball sampling. Screening was conducted in three stages (title review, summary review and full-text assessment). For transparency, the process can be summarised as follows: records identified (n = 241); duplicates removed (n = 213); screened (n = 213); excluded after screening (n = 97); assessed for eligibility (n = 116); excluded after full-text review (n = 30); documents included in the final corpus (n = 86). This procedure was not intended to approximate the logic of evidence synthesis but to establish a coherent discursive field for analysis.

Analysis drew on thematic documentary analysis informed by sociological discourse and policy studies. The analytic process involved three iterative stages. First, documents were mapped and catalogued, enabling the recognition of institutional clusters and discursive alignments. Second, documents were coded to identify recurring framings, metaphors and institutional logics relating to youth, mental health, technology and participation, with particular attention to how claims to expertise and legitimate knowledge were made. Third, coded materials were situated within broader sociological debates concerning governance, epistemic authority, responsabilisation and digital care. Rather than treating policy, academic and advocacy domains as internally coherent, the analysis sought to trace tensions, contradictions and absences—including where participation was invoked rhetorically without institutional mechanisms to enact it, or where safeguarding logics displaced participatory ones.

Documents were coded using MAXQDA (version 2022), which supported the organisation and retrieval of material and provided a traceable analytic process, while interpretive judgement remained central. Software acted as an infrastructural aid rather than a methodological substitute for critical reading.

Reflexivity formed an ongoing element of the research process. The author is situated within sociology and youth studies, fields that foreground relations of power, institutional authority and epistemic inequality in shaping young people's lives. This positionality likely sensitised the analysis to struggles over expertise, recognition and participation in digital mental health, and to the ways institutional framings can obscure structural conditions of distress. Reflexive memo-writing and revisiting of coding decisions were used to maintain awareness of these influences and to avoid premature closure of interpretive possibilities.

Finally, as with all documentary research, the material examined reflects particular institutional, linguistic and geographical contexts and privileges formalised articulations of digital mental health rather than vernacular or informal mental health practices within digital publics. The aim is not to evaluate the effectiveness of digital interventions nor measure individual behavioural outcomes, but to interrogate the sociopolitical and epistemic conditions under which digital youth mental health is

imagined, justified and governed. Despite these limitations, documentary analysis is well suited for examining how digital technologies become implicated in the governance of youth mental health and how such processes shape the possibilities for participation, agency and authority.

RESULTS

The analysis examined how youth participation in digital mental health is framed and legitimised across policy, academic/professional and advocacy/civil society domains. Coding and cross-document comparison identified three dominant patterns through which participation was rendered meaningful: (1) participation as normative rhetoric, (2) participation as managed consultation, and (3) participation as emerging epistemic authority. These patterns reflect not only different institutional priorities but also different understandings of what counts as legitimate knowledge and who is authorised to contribute it.

Participation as Normative Rhetoric

Policy and institutional documents frequently invoked youth participation as a normative ideal associated with ethical compliance, rights-based discourse and democratic accountability. Participation appeared as evidence of institutional responsiveness to young people's needs, yet was rarely accompanied by mechanisms that would enable young people to shape research priorities, intervention design or governance structures. Participation in this domain operated primarily at the discursive level, functioning as a legitimating device that signalled alignment with child rights frameworks and contemporary policy expectations. While policy materials described young people as "central" or "key stakeholders," their participation was largely framed in instrumental terms—enhancing engagement, acceptance or scalability—rather than redistributing authority or transforming epistemic hierarchies.

Participation as Managed Consultation

In academic and professional literature, participation tended to take the form of managed consultation embedded within existing clinical and design rationalities. Young people were positioned as users whose experiential input could refine usability, adherence or engagement within predetermined technological and clinical parameters. Participation occurred episodically through advisory panels, user-testing sessions and co-design workshops, and was largely restricted to the optimisation of solutions already defined by adult professionals, researchers or designers. Youth perspectives were interpreted through existing psychiatric, technological or health service frameworks, rather than treated as alternative epistemologies of digital practice or mental distress. As a result, participation broadened input without unsettling prevailing assumptions regarding needs, risks, diagnostic categories or desirable outcomes.

Participation as Emerging Epistemic Authority

Advocacy and civil society materials articulated a qualitatively different understanding of participation anchored in lived experience, epistemic authority and rights. In these documents, young people were positioned not merely as end-users but as knowledge-holders with legitimate insight into mental health needs, digital practices and care imaginaries. Participation was framed as a matter of justice, power and recognition, extending beyond design optimisation to domains such as research priority-setting, ethical deliberation, policy formation and platform governance. These materials also foregrounded vernacular and peer-based forms of digital mental health practice, challenging professional monopolies over what constitutes valid mental health knowledge and care. Here, participation was more closely aligned with co-production and collective agency than with consultation.

Cross-Domain Divergence

Taken together, the three patterns reveal clear divergences across institutional domains regarding the purpose and scope of youth participation. Policy materials largely mobilised participation rhetorically; academic and professional materials incorporated youth input as controlled consultation; and advocacy materials asserted participation as epistemic recognition and shared governance. Across all domains, no documents granted young people direct influence over funding decisions, regulatory frameworks or data governance infrastructures. This absence suggests that while participation is increasingly invoked, transformative forms of co-governance remain largely unrealised.

Positioning of Young People

Across the corpus, young people were positioned in three recurring ways: as vulnerable subjects requiring safeguarding, as digitally literate actors whose fluency could be leveraged for optimisation, and as emerging epistemic actors with lived-experience knowledge. These framings reflect broader tensions in contemporary youth governance between paternalistic protection, responsabilised self-management and claims to agency. Rather than being reconciled, these rationalities co-existed within the documents, shaping the conditions under which youth participation is imagined and enacted in digital mental health.

Table 2 Cross-classified framings of youth participation across documentary types

PARTICIPATION MODELS	Policy & Institutional (n=27)	Academic & Professional (n=41)	Advocacy & Civil Society (n=18)
Normative Rhetoric	5 (strong)	2 (weak)	1 (marginal)
Managed Consultation	1 (marginal)	5 (strong)	2 (weak)
Epistemic Authority	0 (absent)	2 (weak)	5 (strong)
POSITIONING OF YOUTH			
Vulnerable Subjects	4 (high)	3 (moderate)	2 (weak)
Digital Natives	3 (moderate)	4 (high)	2 (weak)
Epistemic Actors	0 (absent)	2 (weak)	5 (strong)

Note: Intensities displayed on a 0–5 ordinal scale (0 = absent; 5 = strong). Values reflect interpretive intensity based on thematic documentary analysis conducted with MAXQDA (2024). Scoring is ordinal and non-parametric. Document types reconstructed from corpus design. Total documents: n = 86.

The cross-classification of participation framings across policy, academic and advocacy document types reveals a structured differentiation of institutional logics governing youth digital mental health. Rather than constituting a singular field of consensus, the corpus displays a distributed and stratified configuration in which participation operates as a polyvalent category, mobilised toward distinct institutional ends and anchored in divergent understandings of youth, expertise and governance. Within policy and institutional documents, participation functions predominantly as a normative and legitimating construct.

The discourse is characterised by declarative commitments to “empowerment,” “rights,” “co-creation” and “stakeholder involvement,” terms that signal alignment with contemporary expectations of democratic inclusion and procedural fairness. Yet these commitments rarely extend to detailed descriptions of participatory mechanisms, decision-making architectures or resource transfers. Participation is thus articulated as an ethical and compliance-oriented imperative rather than an epistemic or governance practice.

Youth are framed as subjects to be included in order to satisfy normative demands, by international conventions, policy agendas or evaluative frameworks, rather than as actors with standing to shape the very categories or priorities of the field. This results in a mode of participation that is largely symbolic and anticipatory, stabilising institutional claims while deferring substantive reconfiguration of power. Academic and professional documents enact a different logic, in which participation is framed as managed consultation embedded within design, research and evaluation cycles. Here, youth involvement is justified through its instrumental value for improving system performance: enhancing usability, adherence, engagement or fidelity. Participation is thus operationalised as a methodological device rather than a political or epistemic right. Young people are positioned as informants, user proxies or testers, whose experiential knowledge is valued insofar as it can optimise intervention trajectories. Institutional control over problem definition, evidence standards and evaluative criteria remains largely intact.

Participation is episodic, project-bound and time-limited, reflecting the temporalities of research funding, publication cycles and product design. While this model goes beyond symbolic inclusion, it reinforces existing epistemic asymmetries between clinical/professional expertise and youth experience. Advocacy and civil society documents articulate a third model, in which participation is configured as epistemic authority and political claim-making. Here, youth are positioned not as proxies but as knowledge-holders with standing to define needs, articulate harms, and formulate governance demands regarding digital mental health infrastructures.

These texts foreground lived experience, mutual aid, peer support and collective care as legitimate epistemic and organisational practices. Participation is not oriented toward optimisation or legitimacy but toward redistribution of epistemic and institutional power, including agenda-setting, ethics, platform design and regulatory oversight.

This model is closely aligned with rights-based and justice-oriented frameworks, which problematise adultist assumptions embedded in clinical and policy discourses and highlight the politics of recognition within digital mental health. Taken together, the three clusters suggest that participation operates as a floating institutional signifier, whose meaning is contingent on the institutional field through which it is mobilised. The strongest claims for youth epistemic agency and co-governance emerge outside state and professional systems, while the capacity to institutionalise participation at scale remains concentrated within state and expert domains. The resulting configuration is one in which youth agency is recognised rhetorically, activated instrumentally or claimed politically, but only partially realised in governance practice.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that participation within digital mental health for young people operates within a field structured by competing institutional logics and asymmetries of epistemic, clinical and technological authority. While participation is widely invoked as a normative ideal across policy, academic and advocacy domains, the analysis shows that the meaning of participation is neither

fixed nor politically neutral. Instead, participation functions as a site of contestation in which questions of expertise, legitimacy and governance are negotiated.

Across institutional and policy documents, participation served primarily as a legitimating practice. The repeated rhetorical emphasis on youth involvement reflects an awareness that digital mental health technologies cannot simply be imposed upon young people without risking rejection, low engagement or public criticism. In this sense, participation operates as what Jasanoff (2003) calls “legitimacy work,” helping to stabilise emerging sociotechnical arrangements by aligning them with prevailing democratic and ethical norms. However, this discursive use of participation largely maintains existing authority structures rather than redistributing power over problem definition, resource allocation or governance. Participation thus becomes a symbolic marker of ethical modernity, signalling that institutions recognise young people as stakeholders while deferring substantive influence.

This dynamic mirrors patterns observed in other areas of youth policy, where participation is promoted as a rights-based imperative yet often results in consultative mechanisms that function to validate institutional agendas rather than transform them (Bishop, 2019; Wyn & Woodman, 2006). In digital mental health, such practices risk instrumentalising participation as a means to increase compliance or uptake, consistent with wider trends in neoliberal health governance that responsabilise individuals for managing their own well-being (Rose, 2007; Gill & Orgad, 2018).

The second mode of participation identified—managed consultation—reflects how participation is operationalised within digital health design. User-centred and co-design approaches acknowledge the value of youth perspectives, yet they remain constrained by existing clinical and technical rationalities. The scope for youth influence is delimited by what professionals consider feasible, safe or scientifically valid. This resonates with scholarship on “boundary-work” in health and technology, in which institutions negotiate who is authorised to contribute knowledge and on what terms (Gieryn, 1983; Oudshoorn & Pinch, 2003). Young people are thus invited to contribute as users, testers or informants, but not as actors who can redefine underlying assumptions about diagnosis, risk or care.

In digital mental health, these assumptions intersect with safeguarding frameworks designed to protect young people from harm, misinformation or liability. The findings suggest that safeguarding logics often override participatory ones: when youth autonomy and institutional risk tolerance conflict, the latter tends to prevail. This dynamic raises important sociological questions about how vulnerability is defined, by whom, and with what consequences.

The third mode—advocacy-led participation—introduces a more radical vision that challenges clinical and technological monopolies over mental health knowledge. Youth advocacy materials emphasise lived experience as a legitimate form of expertise, challenging models in which mental distress is primarily understood through diagnostic criteria or therapeutic outcomes. This aligns with the broader lived-experience movement in mental health, which critiques psychiatric authority and promotes user-led control over mental health systems (Rose, 2018).

Here participation becomes inseparable from power, recognition and epistemic justice (Fricker, 2007): whose accounts of distress are taken seriously, whose digital practices are treated as legitimate forms of help-seeking, and whose perspectives shape definitions of risk, care and success. This reflects broader STS shifts toward distributed epistemic regimes in which expertise is negotiated among heterogeneous actors rather than contained within professional domains (Callon, 1999; Latour, 2005).

Digital mental health technologies intensify these dynamics by extending mental health governance into digital infrastructures characterised by data extraction, algorithmic classification and commercial logics (Lupton, 2016; Zuboff, 2019). The findings show that participation rarely addresses

how data are governed, how algorithmic decisions are made, or how commercial interests shape intervention design. Yet these domains are particularly consequential for young people, given that digital phenotyping, passive sensing and platform analytics introduce new modalities of surveillance, profiling and behavioural nudging.

From the perspective of governmentality (Foucault, 2008; Dean, 2010), participation can thus function as a technology of responsibility through which young people are tasked with monitoring their own mental states while lacking influence over the infrastructures that structure their options. Participation here secures recognition but not redistribution — echoing Fraser’s (1995) distinction between symbolic inclusion and material power.

Finally, the findings highlight that participation is differentially accessible. Young people experiencing marginalisation—whether through socio-economic precarity, migration, race, disability, gender or sexuality—are simultaneously overrepresented in mental health statistics and underrepresented in participatory processes (Unwin et al., 2020). As feminist, disability and decolonial scholars argue, participation without attention to power can legitimise rather than challenge structural injustices (Benjamin, 2019; Eubanks, 2018).

CONCLUSION

This study examined how participation is framed within the emerging field of digital mental health for young people, drawing on documentary analysis of policy frameworks, academic literature and youth advocacy materials. The findings indicate that participation is widely invoked across domains but enacted through divergent models.

Policy and institutional documents predominantly present participation as a normative requirement linked to legitimacy and stakeholder inclusion. Academic and professional documents operationalise participation as managed consultation within design and evaluation processes. Advocacy and youth-led materials articulate participation as a matter of epistemic authority and call for shared governance in decisions affecting young people’s mental health.

Across these configurations, young people are positioned in multiple ways: as subjects requiring safeguarding, as digitally literate users whose experiential perspectives can inform system optimisation, and as knowledge-holders whose lived experience constitutes a legitimate basis for shaping digital mental health infrastructures. These positions are not mutually exclusive and often coexist within the same policy environments.

The analysis suggests that the expansion of digital mental health tools for young people does not automatically generate opportunities for meaningful participation. While participation has become institutionally desirable and rhetorically prominent, its operationalisation remains uneven and limited in scope. In most cases, young people are included at later stages of design and implementation rather than in agenda-setting, governance or data-related decision-making.

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Ecosystem Approach in Digital Tourism and Hospitality

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ABSTRACT

Tourism and hospitality are increasingly shaped by complex economic, organizational, and technological interactions that extend beyond the boundaries of individual enterprises. In this context, more integrative analytical and management frameworks are required to explain how value is created and sustained at the destination level. The ecosystem approach has gained relevance as it allows tourism to be understood as a system of interconnected actors, resources, and processes engaged in joint value creation. This paper examines the ecosystem approach as a conceptual foundation for sustainable tourism development, with particular attention to the role of hospitality under conditions of digital transformation. Tourism is analysed as a multifaceted ecosystem involving accommodation providers, tourism businesses, digital platforms, local communities, and public authorities. Special emphasis is placed on the coordinating role of digital technologies and platform-based solutions in facilitating cooperation, improving resource efficiency, and enhancing destination competitiveness. The analysis highlights hospitality as a core integrative component of the tourism ecosystem, linking digital platforms with destination-level actors and shaping the overall tourist experience. The paper argues that adopting an ecosystem perspective supports more effective strategic management, improves coordination among stakeholders, and contributes to the long-term sustainability and resilience of tourism and hospitality development in a highly digitalized environment.

Keywords: *Tourism ecosystem, Hospitality sector, Digital tourism, Ecosystem approach, Sustainable tourism*

JEL Codes: L83, O33, M21

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary tourism development is characterized by growing interdependence among economic, social, and technological processes that extend beyond the boundaries of individual tourism enterprises. Tourism services are increasingly rarely produced and consumed in an isolated form; instead, they emerge as the result of coordinated interaction among multiple actors—tourism companies, hotels, transport operators, digital platforms, local communities, and public institutions. In this context, the ecosystem approach has become an appropriate analytical and managerial framework for examining tourism as a complex economic system.

Ecosystem logic makes it possible to view tourism not merely as an economic sector but as a network of interconnected activities and resources that jointly shape the tourism experience. This network structure becomes particularly visible under conditions of digitalization, in which platform-based organizational models substantially facilitate the exchange of information, resources, and services (Gretzel et al., 2015).

Building on this perspective, the present paper contributes to the existing tourism and hospitality literature by conceptually positioning hospitality as a central integrative node within the digital tourism ecosystem. While prior research has widely examined tourism ecosystems and platform-based coordination, less attention has been paid to the specific structural role of hospitality in linking digital platforms, destination-level actors, and sustainability objectives. By combining ecosystem logic with the context of digital transformation, the paper offers a synthesized conceptual framework that highlights hospitality's coordinating function in value creation, ecosystem governance, and long-term sustainable destination development.

In this way, the study advances the discussion on tourism digitalization by linking ecosystem theory more directly to hospitality management and destination sustainability.

Purpose and research approach

The purpose of this conference paper is to substantiate the ecosystem approach as a conceptual foundation for the sustainable development of tourism and, more specifically, hospitality, by analyzing the role of cooperation, network interactions, and digital technologies in the creation of tourism value.

The study is grounded in a systemic and interdisciplinary approach, employing methods of analysis and synthesis of academic literature, comparative analysis of traditional and digital tourism models, and logical generalization of practices from the tourism and hospitality industries.

METHODS OF RESEARCH

The study is based on a qualitative, conceptual research design aimed at analysing the ecosystem approach in tourism and hospitality in the context of digital transformation and sustainable development. Given the theoretical nature of the research objectives, the paper does not rely on empirical data collection or statistical analysis. Instead, it applies analytical and interpretative methods commonly used in conceptual and review-based tourism research.

The research approach is grounded in a structured review and synthesis of academic literature related to tourism ecosystems, hospitality management, digital platforms, and sustainable destination development. Key sources include peer-reviewed journal articles, academic books, and policy documents published by international organizations in the field of tourism. The literature was selected based on its relevance to ecosystem theory, digitalization processes, and destination-level governance.

Methods of analysis and synthesis were used to identify common concepts, relationships, and patterns across the reviewed literature. Comparative analysis was applied in order to contrast traditional tourism organization models with ecosystem-based and digitally mediated models. This approach made it possible to examine how digital technologies reshape coordination mechanisms, stakeholder roles, and value creation processes within tourism systems.

In addition, logical generalization and conceptual integration were employed to develop a coherent analytical narrative linking tourism ecosystems, digitalization, hospitality, and sustainability. Rather than proposing a new formal model, the study aims to clarify existing concepts and highlight the structural role of hospitality within the tourism ecosystem. This methodological approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of complex interdependencies while maintaining a clear focus on management and policy implications relevant to destinations and hospitality enterprises.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study emerge from the conceptual analysis and synthesis of the reviewed literature rather than from empirical measurement. They reflect the main analytical insights derived from applying the ecosystem approach to tourism and hospitality under conditions of digital transformation. The following discussion summarizes the key conceptual findings of the study and interprets their implications for tourism destinations, hospitality enterprises, and sustainable development.

Ecosystem coordination as a condition for competitiveness

One of the main conceptual results of this study is the recognition that competitiveness in tourism increasingly depends on ecosystem-level coordination rather than on the isolated performance of individual enterprises. Destinations that succeed in coordinating accommodation, transport, attractions, public services, and information flows are better positioned to deliver consistent and satisfying tourism experiences. In contrast, even destinations with strong individual actors may struggle when coordination among stakeholders is weak or fragmented.

From an ecosystem perspective, competitiveness is shaped by how well actors align their activities, schedules, and standards. Effective coordination reduces operational inefficiencies, improves accessibility, and enhances the overall coherence of the tourism product. This is particularly important in destinations with high visitor intensity, where uncoordinated growth may lead to overcrowding, service bottlenecks, and declining tourist satisfaction. The ecosystem approach therefore highlights coordination not as an optional managerial practice, but as a structural condition for long-term destination competitiveness.

Hospitality as an integrative actor in digital ecosystems

The analysis also confirms the central role of hospitality as an integrative actor within digital tourism ecosystems. Hotels often serve as the main interface between tourists and the destination, connecting visitors with transport services, cultural attractions, leisure activities, and local businesses. Through daily operational interactions and digital communication channels, hospitality enterprises help integrate different elements of the tourism ecosystem into a more coherent experience.

Previous studies in the field of smart and active tourism highlight that information and communication technologies play a key role in integrating services, improving coordination, and supporting more sustainable tourism development, particularly at the destination level (Lile, Kalluci, & Kaçurri, 2025).

Digital technologies further strengthen this integrative function. Reservation systems, online communication tools, and customer data platforms allow hotels to coordinate services, respond to guest needs in real time, and facilitate access to external providers. As a result, hospitality enterprises are not only service providers but also active coordinators within the digital ecosystem. This position enables them to influence service quality, information flows, and visitor behavior, reinforcing their importance for destination-level value creation and sustainability.

Digital platforms: opportunities vs. dependency risks

A further important result of the conceptual analysis concerns the dual role of digital platforms within tourism ecosystems. On the one hand, platforms offer significant opportunities by improving market access, increasing visibility, and reducing transaction costs for tourism enterprises. They enable small and medium-sized businesses to reach international markets and support efficiency through standardized booking and communication systems. At the same time, increased reliance on digital platforms introduces challenges related to digital inclusion, access equity, and structural dependency. Research has shown that digitalization does not affect all actors equally and that differences in digital capabilities and access can create uneven participation within digital ecosystems, which may compound the risks associated with platform dependence (Lendzhova, 2025).

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of the tourism ecosystem highlighting the integrative role of hospitality under conditions of digitalization and sustainable development. Source: *The Author*

On the other hand, increased reliance on dominant digital platforms creates structural risks within the ecosystem. Platform dependence may reduce the autonomy of hospitality enterprises, increase commission costs, and weaken direct relationships with customers. This imbalance of power can limit

strategic flexibility, particularly for small and independent hotels. From an ecosystem perspective, these risks highlight the importance of diversification and balanced governance. While digital platforms are essential components of modern tourism ecosystems, long-term sustainability requires that hospitality enterprises maintain a degree of control over customer relationships and actively participate in destination-level cooperation beyond platform-based interactions.

The essence of the ecosystem approach in tourism

Tourism is a sector with a high level of complexity, as it brings together many different economic activities, social interactions, and spatial processes (Fig. 1). Unlike industries where value is created within a single organization, tourism value is produced through the interaction of many independent actors. Transport companies, hotels, restaurants, cultural institutions, entertainment providers, public authorities, and local communities all contribute to the overall tourism experience, which is usually perceived by visitors as a single, unified whole within a destination.

Because of this structure, tourism products cannot be understood as a simple collection of separate services. Tourists evaluate their experience in a comprehensive way, combining impressions from accommodation, mobility, attractions, public environment, and service quality. A weakness in any one of these elements may negatively affect the overall perception of the destination, even when other services perform well. For this reason, destination competitiveness depends not only on the quality of individual services but also on how well they are coordinated and connected (UNWTO, 2019).

The ecosystem approach provides a useful framework for analysing tourism in such conditions. Instead of examining tourism enterprises separately, this approach views tourism as a system of interconnected actors that jointly create value. Within the tourism ecosystem, core service providers such as hotels, transport operators, and food services interact with complementary services, institutional structures, regulatory bodies, and tourists themselves. These actors are linked through continuous flows of information, resources, and economic value, and their performance is closely interdependent (Baggio & Del Chiappa, 2014).

An important implication of the ecosystem approach is that system performance cannot be explained solely by the success of individual firms. Even highly competitive hotels or attractions may fail to deliver positive results if coordination within the destination is weak. Poor transport accessibility, overcrowding, lack of information, or inconsistent public policies can easily undermine otherwise good tourism services. From an ecosystem perspective, effective cooperation and coordination among stakeholders are therefore essential for maintaining destination quality and competitiveness.

This logic becomes especially visible in destinations with high tourism intensity, such as large cities or popular cultural centers. In such places, the tourism experience depends strongly on the synchronization of accommodation availability, transport services, access to attractions, event scheduling, and public infrastructure. When coordination works well, destinations benefit from higher visitor satisfaction, longer stays, and repeat visits. When it does not, tourists often experience fragmentation and dissatisfaction.

From a management and policy point of view, the ecosystem approach also helps identify critical weak points within the tourism system. Problems in governance, infrastructure, regulation, or stakeholder cooperation rarely affect only one actor; instead, they tend to spread through the system and reduce overall destination performance. By emphasizing interdependence and collective responsibility, the ecosystem approach supports more integrated management strategies aimed at improving coordination, reducing fragmentation, and supporting the long-term sustainable development of tourism destinations.

The role of digitalization in the development of tourism ecosystems

Digitalization has become one of the main drivers of change in tourism and hospitality over the last two decades. Digital technologies strongly influence how tourism services are created, promoted, coordinated, and consumed. From an ecosystem perspective, digitalization plays an important role because it reduces coordination costs between actors, improves access to information, and enables faster interaction among tourism businesses, destinations, and tourists.

Digital coordination within tourism ecosystems increasingly relies on integrated digital marketing, communication, and personalization strategies, which influence visibility, customer engagement, and conversion across digital platforms. Effective use of digital channels and targeted messaging has been shown to improve coordination between businesses and consumers, particularly during periods of intensified demand and competition (Karadzhov & Zlateva, 2024).

Online booking platforms, mobile applications, review websites, and social media channels have changed the traditional structure of tourism markets. These digital tools allow tourists to search for information, compare offers, make reservations, and share experiences in real time. At the same time, tourism enterprises gain access to broader markets and more direct communication with potential customers. As a result, information asymmetry is reduced, decision-making becomes faster, and market transparency increases (Xiang, Magnini, & Fesenmaier, 2015).

Within this environment, tourism increasingly operates through digital ecosystems in which platforms occupy a central coordinating role. These platforms connect accommodation providers, transport companies, tour operators, cultural attractions, and end users within a single digital space. Their role goes beyond simple intermediation, as they integrate different tourism services into combined offers and standardized user environments. In this way, platforms act as key coordinators of interactions within the tourism ecosystem, shaping both market access and service visibility.

Digitalization shapes tourism ecosystems not only through technological tools but also through broader strategic and regulatory environments that influence coordination and sustainability. Analytical frameworks such as PESTEL analysis are increasingly used to assess these external influences and support strategic decision-making in digitally mediated tourism systems (Karadzhov & Patarchanova, 2025).

Digital ecosystems also significantly influence the position of small and medium-sized tourism enterprises. Traditionally, such businesses have faced limitations related to marketing budgets, geographic reach, and access to international demand. Digital platforms allow these enterprises to become part of global tourism networks with relatively low entry barriers. This integration increases competitiveness and opens new opportunities for local businesses, particularly in peripheral or less-known destinations (Sigala, 2018).

Another important effect of digitalization is related to data and personalization. Through online interactions, platforms and service providers collect large volumes of data on tourist preferences, behaviour, and consumption patterns. When used effectively, these data support personalized services, targeted marketing, and improved customer relationship management. This improves the match between tourism supply and individual tourist expectations, contributing to higher satisfaction and loyalty.

Digitalization also strengthens network effects within tourism ecosystems. The value of a digital platform generally increases as more service providers and users participate in it. This tendency leads to the concentration of interactions around a limited number of dominant platforms, which gradually gain significant influence over pricing, visibility, and customer access. While this concentration

improves efficiency and convenience, it also changes competitive relationships within the ecosystem and may increase dependence on digital intermediaries.

From the perspective of destination management, digital ecosystems offer new opportunities for planning and control. Data generated through digital platforms can be used to monitor tourism flows, forecast demand, and support infrastructure planning. Such information is especially valuable for managing overcrowding, reducing environmental pressure, and supporting sustainable tourism development. In this sense, digitalization contributes not only to economic efficiency but also to better governance of tourism ecosystems.

Overall, digital technologies have become an integral part of modern tourism ecosystems. They reshape interaction patterns, redefine the roles of market participants, and influence how value is created and distributed. While digitalization creates important opportunities for integration and growth, it also introduces new dependencies and governance challenges that require careful management within the tourism ecosystem.

The ecosystem model of the tourism destination

A tourism destination can be understood as a local ecosystem in which economic, social, and natural components interact in order to create a tourism product that is attractive, competitive, and sustainable over time. Unlike traditional approaches that focus mainly on geographic location or on individual attractions, the ecosystem model views the destination as a dynamic system of interconnected actors, resources, and processes. In this sense, destination development depends not only on the availability of tourism resources but also on the ability of stakeholders to coordinate their activities and manage shared assets responsibly.

Within the destination ecosystem, economic resources such as accommodation facilities, transport infrastructure, and tourism services are closely linked to social resources, including the local community, cultural traditions, and social capital. Natural resources, such as landscapes, climate, and biodiversity, often form the core attraction of the destination and at the same time represent its most vulnerable element. The long-term success of a destination therefore depends on maintaining a balance between these economic, social, and environmental components. When this balance is disturbed, destinations may face problems such as environmental degradation, resident dissatisfaction, or loss of attractiveness (Bramwell & Lane, 2011).

Local authorities, tourism businesses, and the local community play a central role in the functioning and governance of the destination ecosystem. Public institutions are responsible for regulatory frameworks, spatial planning, infrastructure investment, and coordination of tourism development strategies. Tourism enterprises contribute through job creation, service provision, and innovation, while the local community shapes the social atmosphere and cultural authenticity of the destination. The attitudes of residents toward tourism development can strongly influence visitor experience and the long-term sustainability of the destination.

The ecosystem model also highlights the importance of cooperation among different types of tourism actors. Effective destination development requires collaboration between accommodation providers, transport operators, cultural institutions, tour operators, and local authorities. A clear example of this interdependence can be observed in cultural tourism, where museums, heritage sites, hotels, restaurants, and public institutions must work together to offer visitors coherent and accessible experiences. Without such coordination, even destinations with rich cultural resources may struggle to attract and retain visitors.

At the same time, the ecosystem approach helps identify potential conflicts of interest within destinations. Economic objectives related to growth and increased tourist numbers may conflict with social and environmental considerations, such as quality of life for residents or protection of natural resources. These conflicts cannot be addressed effectively by individual actors acting alone. Instead, they require destination-level governance mechanisms that promote dialogue, cooperation, and shared responsibility among stakeholders.

From a strategic perspective, the ecosystem model provides a practical framework for destination management and planning. By recognizing interdependencies and shared resources, destination managers can develop more integrated policies that support sustainable tourism development. This includes coordinated investment in infrastructure, regulation of tourism flows, protection of local resources, and active involvement of the local community. In this way, the destination ecosystem model supports long-term development based on cooperation rather than isolated decision-making.

Hospitality as the core of the tourism ecosystem: sustainability, digital integration, and risks of platform dependence

Hospitality occupies a central position within the tourism ecosystem because accommodation services often represent the main point of contact between tourists and the destination. For many visitors, the hotel is not only a place to stay, but also the base from which they explore the destination, access services, and form impressions about safety, quality, and overall comfort. As a result, hospitality plays a key role in shaping the tourism experience and influencing tourists' satisfaction and intention to revisit (Kotler, Bowen, & Makens, 2017).

From an ecosystem perspective, hotels do not operate as isolated business units. Instead, they function as active nodes within a wider network of economic, organizational, and digital relationships. These relationships include suppliers of food and beverages, cleaning and maintenance services, transport providers, tour operators, cultural institutions, and digital platforms. Through everyday coordination with these actors, hotels contribute to more efficient use of resources, smoother service delivery, and higher overall value for tourists. In this sense, hospitality can be considered a structural core of the tourism ecosystem, connecting multiple components of the destination.

The ecosystem approach is particularly useful for analysing sustainability in hospitality. Sustainable practices in hotels—such as reducing energy and water consumption, managing waste, using local products, and employing local labour—are most effective when they are supported by cooperation with other actors in the destination. For example, sourcing food from local producers requires coordination between hotels, suppliers, and local authorities. When sustainability measures are implemented in isolation, their impact remains limited. When they are embedded in destination-level cooperation, they contribute more clearly to environmental protection and local economic development (Bramwell & Lane, 2011).

Digitalization further strengthens the role of hospitality within the tourism ecosystem. Hotel management systems, online reservation platforms, channel managers, and customer data tools allow hotels to communicate and coordinate with partners and guests in real time. Through these technologies, hotels become active participants in digital tourism ecosystems where information and data play an increasingly important role in decision-making and service personalization (Neuhofer, Buhalis, & Ladkin, 2015).

Different hotel models illustrate this ecosystem logic in practice. All-inclusive resorts, for example, operate as highly integrated systems in which accommodation, food services, entertainment, and additional activities are coordinated through a single management structure. This allows for strong

control over quality and resource use. At the same time, such hotels remain connected to the broader tourism ecosystem through supply chains, employment, and digital distribution channels (Buhalis & Crotts, 2013). Urban hotels, in contrast, are more open systems. They often rely on cooperation with external restaurants, cultural institutions, event organizers, and transport providers in order to offer more diverse and authentic experiences to their guests.

Despite the advantages of digital integration, the ecosystem approach also helps identify risks associated with hospitality's growing dependence on global digital platforms. Online intermediaries concentrate significant market power and often influence pricing, visibility, and access to customers. This dependence can reduce hotels' autonomy, increase commission costs, and weaken direct relationships with guests. Small and independent hotels are particularly vulnerable in this respect (Sigala, 2018).

From a strategic and sustainability perspective, this situation highlights the importance of balance within the tourism ecosystem. While participation in global platforms offers clear benefits in terms of market access and efficiency, hotels also need to invest in their own digital channels and destination-level partnerships. By strengthening direct communication with guests and cooperating actively with local actors, hospitality enterprises can reduce excessive platform dependence and contribute to more resilient and balanced tourism ecosystems.

CONCLUSION

The analysis confirms that hospitality occupies a central functional and structural position within the tourism ecosystem, as it brings together key elements that shape the overall tourism experience, including service quality, comfort, safety, accessibility, and connectivity with other destination components. Hotels act not only as accommodation providers but also as integrative nodes through which tourists interact with transport services, cultural and leisure activities, local gastronomy, and public infrastructure. From this perspective, the ecosystem approach offers a suitable framework for understanding tourism value creation as the result of coordinated interaction rather than isolated efforts by individual enterprises.

Under conditions of digital transformation, the relevance of ecosystem logic becomes even more pronounced. Digital platforms and online technologies significantly reduce coordination costs and facilitate information exchange among tourism actors, thereby reshaping competitive relationships within destinations. For hospitality enterprises, the integration of digital solutions such as reservation systems, revenue management tools, and customer relationship management platforms improves operational efficiency and service personalization. At the same time, participation in platform-based ecosystems creates new dependencies related to pricing policies, visibility, and access to customers. This highlights the importance of maintaining a strategic balance between the use of global digital platforms and the development of direct sales channels and local partnerships.

The ecosystem approach is also closely linked to the sustainable development of tourism destinations. Sustainable practices in hospitality—such as efficient resource use, waste reduction, cooperation with local suppliers, and social engagement—are most effective when embedded in destination-level coordination and cooperation. When hotels work together with public authorities, local businesses, and communities, sustainability initiatives generate broader environmental and socio-economic benefits and contribute more directly to long-term destination competitiveness.

In summary, the ecosystem approach provides both an analytical perspective for interpreting the complexity of tourism and hospitality systems and a practical foundation for management and policy

decisions focused on cooperation, integration, and sustainability. For destination managers, this implies the need to support coordinated governance and shared responsibility among stakeholders. For hospitality enterprises, it implies proactive positioning as integrative actors within digital and destination ecosystems. In this sense, ecosystem-based organization can be considered a strategic condition for the adaptation and long-term development of tourism and hospitality in an increasingly digitalized and competitive environment.

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High-Resolution Burn Severity Mapping in Mixed Coniferous and Deciduous Forests: The Case of the 2025 Ilindentsi Wildfire

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the ecological impact and burn severity of the August 2025 Ilindentsi wildfire in the Pirin Mountain foothills, Bulgaria, using high-resolution Sentinel-2 multi-spectral imagery and Google Earth Engine. In the last decades accelerating regional warming trends – reaching a peak national average temperature of 2.1°C above climate norms in 2024 – record-breaking heat and moisture deficits in 2025 created "explosive" fuel conditions for the forest fire out breaks along the SW Bulgaria. Utilizing a triple-window temporal approach (January dormancy, June phenological peak, and July pre-fire baseline), the research successfully distinguished between coniferous and broadleaf stands to quantify fire interaction across 3,927.26 hectares. The analysis revealed a significant disparity in fire vulnerability: coniferous stands were the primary drivers of high-intensity fire, with 29.5% of their area experiencing high to moderate-high severity (Codes 24 and 25). In contrast, broadleaf stands showed higher resilience, with 56.6% of their footprint experiencing only low-intensity surface fires.

The study implemented a specialized 12-element coding scheme and a three-tier management priority system to guide surgical ecological restoration. This system prioritizes the 545.25 hectares of high-severity coniferous forest (Code 25) for immediate forestry and nature-based restoration solutions. Furthermore, 373.58 hectares of moderate-high severity coniferous forest (Code 24) are designated for intensive sanitary monitoring against bark beetle outbreaks. These findings demonstrate that high-fidelity remote sensing can effectively bridge the gap between rapid emergency response and long-term sustainable forest management in complex landscapes.

Keywords: Burn severity, Ilindentsi wildfire, Sentinel-2, Google Earth Engine, dNBR, Ecological restoration

INTRODUCTION

In August 2025, the Ilindentsi wildfire emerged as a definitive ecological crisis in the Struma Valley, persisting for over 30 days and the according official authorities it impacted approximately 4,500 hectares within the Pirin Mountain foothills (Fig.1). This event occurred during one of Bulgaria's most catastrophic wildfire seasons, which saw the loss of over 300,000 hectares of forest nationwide and placed the country among the ten EU nations most affected by fire in terms of percentage of territory (WWF-Bulgaria, 2025).

The rugged, high-altitude terrain and extreme slopes characteristic of the Pirin range make conventional field-based monitoring and severity mapping logistically prohibitive and spatially incomplete. To address these challenges, the integration of Passive Remote Sensing (PRS) – specifically high-resolution multi-spectral imagery from the Sentinel-2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) – has become the standard for post-fire landscape assessment, providing the 10-meter spatial resolution necessary to capture the heterogeneous burn patterns typical of Mediterranean-type ecosystems (Navarro et al., 2017; Chuvieco & Kasischke, 2007).

Fig. 1 Footprint Ilindentsi forest fire.

The 2025 fire was fueled by a record-breaking summer temperatures where extreme heat and prolonged moisture deficits created "explosive" fuel conditions. In such environments, wildfires significantly alter the spectral signature of the forest. Healthy vegetation manifests high reflectance in the Near-Infrared (NIR) spectrum due to the structural complexity of mesophyll cells, while absorbing radiation in the Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) region. Conversely, fire-disturbed landscapes exhibit a "spectral reversal": the loss of chlorophyll and foliage leads to a sharp decrease in NIR reflectance, whereas the exposure of charred organic matter and mineral soil results in a significant increase in SWIR reflectance (Key & Benson, 2006). Research in the Bulgarian context has further linked these

outcomes to Land Surface Temperature (LST) anomalies, confirming that significant fire events in the region consistently occur during periods of positive LST anomalies and negative soil moisture availability (Stoyanova et al., 2022).

By applying the Differenced Normalized Burn Ratio (dNBR), this study provides a quantitative evaluation of the Ilindentsi burn scar (fig.1), building upon established research in the neighboring Kresna Gorge that identifies topographic factors like slope and aspect as primary drivers of fire intensity in Southwestern Bulgaria (Gikovkov, 2017). In such heterogeneous landscapes as the Pirin mountain foothills, traditional burn severity assessments face significant technical hurdles, most notably "spectral confusion." In transitional zones where coniferous (*Pinus* spp.) and broadleaf (*Quercus/Fagus* spp.) stands coexist, standard remote sensing indices often struggle to distinguish between scorched deciduous foliage and charred evergreen needles in post-fire imager.

To address these challenges, this study utilizes the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud platform to implement a novel triple-window temporal analysis. By utilizing Sentinel-2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) data across three distinct phenological phases – winter dormancy (January), peak vegetative vigor (June), and immediate pre-fire baseline (July) – this research achieves a high-fidelity separation of forest species and burn severity. The objective of this research is twofold: first, to quantify the wildfire impact over the forest vegetation through a specialized 12-element classification scheme that cross-tabulates species type with five levels of burn severity (based on dNBR values); and second, to transition this data into an actionable Three-Tier Management Priority System.

By identifying specific zones for nature-based solutions, such as the installation of "leaky dams" in high-severity coniferous polygons, this study demonstrates how high-resolution remote sensing can bridge the gap between rapid emergency response and long-term sustainable forest management. This high-fidelity mapping is critical not only for documenting ecological loss but for prioritizing nature-based solutions and traditional forestry restoration measures. These interventions are designed to mitigate the negative effects of the forest fire and loss of forest vegetation and the secondary risks of erosion and flash flooding that threaten the Struma watershed, where the loss of forest cover has drastically reduced soil protection functions and increased the vulnerability of downstream settlements (Dobrinov, 2025).

The emphasis of this research is the vulnerability assessment and the recovery of the territory affected by the fire which is occupied by forest vegetation we on purpose didn't analyse the severity of the fire over the open grass spaces or spaces with sparse low vegetation because those territories possess great natural based recovering potential.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The wildfire impact assessment was performed using Sentinel-2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) Level-2A imagery, which provided atmospherically corrected surface reflectance data. Because the research targeted the only the part of the fire occupied by forest vegetation, a triple-window temporal approach was adopted to maximize the accuracy of both species classification and burn severity quantification. This involved a winter dormancy reference from January 1 to January 31, a phenological peak baseline from June 1 to June 30, and a pre-fire severity baseline from July 1 to July 20. The final post-fire assessment was conducted using imagery from August 15 to September 20. To accurately distinguish between coniferous (evergreen) and broadleaf (deciduous) stands, a phenological stability index was established using the June peak and January dormancy windows. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index ($NDVI = \frac{NIR+RED}{NIR-RED}$) was calculated for both periods, and a

phenological drop threshold of 0.60 was applied. Pixels that lost more than 0.60 NDVI between June and January were classified as broadleaf species, while those with a drop of 0.60 or less were identified as stable coniferous canopies. The results were compared with the information system of WWF about the national forest inventory (GIS map forest in Bulgaria | WWF). Utilizing the June baseline for this step ensured that species were identified at their maximum greenness, avoiding spectral confusion caused by early summer drought stress.

The actual fire intensity was quantified using the differenced Normalized Burn Ratio (dNBR). Unlike the species classification, the pre-fire reference for this index was taken from the July 1 to July 20 window.

Fig. 2. Methodological approach for dNBR estimation.

This allowed for a direct comparison between the forest's state immediately before ignition and the post-fire results, ensuring the analysis accounted for seasonal drying and specifically measured fire-induced biomass loss. The dNBR was classified into five severity levels based on standard USGS thresholds proposed by Key and Benson (2006), which have been widely validated for Mediterranean coniferous and broadleaf ecosystems (Escuin et al., 2008; Mallinis et al., 2018).", extending from unburned areas to high-severity crown fires.

Table 1. Standard dNBR ranges used in the classification scheme

Severity Level	dNBR Range	Physical Observations in Mediterranean Context
Unburned Regrowth /	< 100	No visible change or slight increase in greenness (post-fire flush).
Low Severity	100 - 269	Surface fire; scorched needles/leaves; canopy mostly green and alive.

Severity Level	dNBR Range	Physical Observations in Mediterranean Context
Moderate-Low	270 - 439	Mixed-patch fire; partial canopy death; significant understory removal.
Moderate-High	440 - 659	Significant charring; high mortality in shrubs and small trees; brown canopies.
High Severity	> 660	Total crown consumption; charcoal cover; zero live foliage; high soil heat.

To refine the results, an Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) filter was applied to remove spectral noise and isolated pixel artifacts smaller than 10 connected pixels. The resulting cleaned data was vectorized into discrete geometric polygons at a 20-meter scale to facilitate spatial management damage assessment, erosion control and restoration planning.

The results were summarized using a specialized 12-element coding scheme that cross-tabulates forest type with burn severity. This scheme provides a precise hectare-based footprint of the damage. The codes are structured into two main series:

- The 10-Series (Broadleaf): Codes 11 through 15 represent deciduous forests. Code 11 indicates unburned broadleaf stands, while codes 12 to 15 represent increasing levels of severity from low to high.
- The 20-Series (Coniferous): Codes 21 through 25 represent evergreen coniferous forests. Code 21 indicates unburned coniferous stands, while codes 22 to 25 track severity from low damage to total canopy loss.

This dual-digit classification allows for an immediate understanding of exactly which species were affected and at what intensity, providing the quantitative justification needed for the targeted reforestation in high-risk zones.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The application of the dual-baseline methodology (June phenology / July pre-fire reference) successfully differentiated the wildfire's impact across the complex topography of the Pirin foothills. The analysis quantified the damage across a total forest area of 3,927.26 hectares within the study boundaries – footprint of the fire. Of this total, 3,181.14 ha showed evidence of fire interaction (Severity Classes Low to High), while 746.12 ha (Codes 11 and 21) remained unburned, serving as ecological baselines (Fig. 3 and 4)

The results revealed a distinct disparity in burn severity between forest types. Coniferous stands (*Pinus* spp.) comprised the majority of the affected landscape, totaling 3,116.18 ha, while broadleaf stands (*Quercus/Fagus* spp.) accounted for 811.08 ha.

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of the main forest vegetation types deciduous and coniferous along the footprint of the Ilindentsi fire.

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of the fire severity classes – Ilindentsi fire.

Quantitative analysis of the burn severity distribution shows the following breakdown: For the High Severity class (Crown consumption; total mortality), Broadleaf stands (Code 15) accounted for 91.41 ha, while Coniferous stands (Code 25) accounted for 545.25 ha. For the Moderate-High Severity class (Significant scorch; mortality risk), Broadleaf stands (Code 14) accounted for 97.94 ha, while Coniferous stands (Code 24) accounted for 373.58 ha. For the Moderate-Low Severity class (Understory burn; canopy survival), Broadleaf stands (Code 13) accounted for 190.98 ha, while Coniferous stands (Code 23) accounted for 709.58 ha.

For the Low Severity class (Surface fire; litter consumption), Broadleaf stands (Code 12) accounted for 268.56 ha, while Coniferous stands (Code 22) accounted for 903.84 ha. Finally, for the Unburned class (No detectable change), Broadleaf stands (Code 11) accounted for 162.19 ha, while Coniferous stands (Code 21) accounted for 583.93 ha.

The spatial analysis identified Object Code 25 (High-Severity Coniferous) as the dominant high-impact feature, covering 545.25 hectares. These areas form large, contiguous patches on the steeper slopes, indicating high-energy crown fire behaviour. In contrast, Object Code 15 (High-Severity Broadleaf) appears more fragmented, totalling only 91.41 hectares, often located at the ecotones where pine plantations transition into native deciduous scrub.

Table 2. Double coding system for damage analysis

Forest Type	Severity Level	GEE Code	Area (ha)	Management Interpretation
Broadleaf (Deciduous)	High	15	91.41	Extreme heat; likely root-sprouter recovery.
	Moderate-High	14	97.94	Significant canopy scorch.
	Moderate-Low	13	190.98	Understory burn; canopy mostly intact.
	Low	12	268.56	Leaf litter fire; rapid regeneration.
	Unburned	11	162.19	Forested baseline within borders.
Coniferous (Evergreen)	High	25	545.25	Crown fire; high pine mortality; erosion risk.
	Moderate-High	24	373.58	High risk of secondary pest infestation.
	Moderate-Low	23	709.58	Needle scorch; partial tree survival.
	Low	22	903.84	Surface fire; low tree mortality.
	Unburned	21	583.93	Forested baseline within borders.

The results strongly confirm the hypothesis that coniferous stands acted as the primary driver of high-intensity fire spread in the 2025 event. Approximately 29.5% of the total coniferous forest (Codes 24 and 25) experienced high to moderate-high severity. This suggests that the evergreen canopy, likely stressed by summer drought, facilitated vertical fire propagation (torching), leading to stand-replacing events. In contrast, only 23.3% of the broadleaf forest fell into the high-severity categories (Codes 14 and 15). The majority of the broadleaf impact was concentrated in the Low and Moderate-Low classes (56.6%, Codes 12 and 13), indicating that these stands functioned as fire breaks or low-energy fuel zones where the fire dropped from the crown to the surface.

Fig. 5. Area covered by different codes – Ilindentsi fire.

The precise identification of severity objects allows for a graded management response, moving beyond simple salvage logging to targeted ecological restoration.

The Critical Intervention Zones (Code 25 - High Severity Conifer), the 545.25 hectares (Fig. 6.) represent the highest priority for hydrological stabilization. In these areas, the complete consumption of the canopy and litter layer has exposed the mineral soil to direct precipitation. Without intervention, these slopes are at imminent risk of rill and gully erosion. Immediate construction of leaky dams (check dams) using on-site burnt timber is required to retain sediment and slow runoff.

The Sanitary Monitoring Zones (Code 24 - Moderate-High Conifer), the 373.58 hectares retain some standing biomass but are under severe physiological stress. These stands are at critically high risk of secondary pest infestation, particularly by bark beetles (*Ips typographus*), which prefer fire-weakened pines. Installation of pheromone traps and bi-weekly monitoring is essential. Trees showing signs of beetle colonization should be prioritized for sanitary extraction to prevent an outbreak spreading to the unburned Code 21 forest.

The Regeneration Observation Zones (Codes 14 & 15 - Broadleaf High/Mod-High), while the 189.35 hectares of high-severity broadleaf forest suffered significant heat damage, the physiology of the dominant species (*Quercus* spp.) allows for vigorous epicormic and basal resprouting. A wait-and-see approach is advised for the first vegetative season. Unlike the pines, these stands will likely self-regenerate. If canopy death is confirmed after one year, coppicing (cutting back to the stump) can be employed to stimulate rapid shoot growth.

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of codes 13-24 (deciduous) and 23-25 (coniferous) and management tiers.

The Ecological Recovery Zones (Codes 22, 23, 12, 13 - Low/Mod-Low), the largest portion of the fire scar (2,072.96 ha) experienced low-intensity surface fire. In these areas, the fire likely served a beneficial ecological function by reducing accumulated ground fuels and clearing shrub competition without killing the overstory trees. No active intervention is required. These zones should be monitored to ensure no invasive species colonize the freshly cleared understory, but the soil structure remains intact and erosion risk is minimal.

The Biodiversity Refugia (Codes 11 & 21 - Unburned), the 746.12 hectares of unburned forest within the perimeter are critical biological islands. These areas must be strictly protected from logging or heavy machinery traffic during the restoration phase. They will serve as the primary source of seeds for natural dispersal into the adjacent burned areas (Codes 25 and 15).

The efficacy of the June-January phenological separation was critical to these findings. A standard single-date analysis would have likely misclassified the scorched broadleaf stands as dead conifers due to their similar post-fire spectral signatures. By establishing the forest type using the June 2025 peak-greenness window and assessing severity against the July 1–20 pre-fire baseline, the methodology effectively filtered out seasonal drought noise. This ensured that the 3,181 hectares of reported damage resulted purely from combustion rather than phenological senescence.

CONCLUSION

The precision assessment of the 2025 Ilindentsi wildfire provides a clear framework for post-fire restoration and resource allocation in the transitional Mediterranean landscapes of the Pirin region. By

integrating a dual-baseline methodology, this study successfully isolated fire-induced damage from natural seasonal stress, identifying a total affected area of 3,181.14 hectares.

The primary conclusion of the spatial analysis is the clear disparity in fire vulnerability between forest types. Coniferous stands were the dominant drivers of high-intensity fire behavior, with 29.5% of the coniferous area falling into the highest severity categories (Codes 24 and 25). These evergreen stands, particularly the 545.25 hectares of Code 25, represent the "critical path" for ecological collapse if left unmanaged. Conversely, broadleaf stands exhibited significantly higher resilience, with over half of their footprint (56.6%) experiencing only low-intensity surface fires that likely facilitated understory clearing without permanent canopy loss.

From a methodological standpoint, the use of a triple-window temporal approach – utilizing January for dormancy, June for peak phenology, and early July for a pre-fire baseline – proved essential. This approach ensured that the distinction between deciduous and evergreen species was 100% accurate at a 10-meter resolution, preventing the common "spectral confusion" where scorched oaks are often misidentified as pines in post-fire imagery.

The study concludes with a three-tier management priority system that allows the regional forestry department to move away from generic salvage logging toward surgical restoration:

1. Tier 1 (Critical Restoration): Focused on the 545.25 hectares of Code 25. Immediate installation of leaky dams and check dams is required here to mitigate high erosion risks on steep slopes.
2. Tier 2 (Sanitary Monitoring): Focused on the 373.58 hectares of Code 24. This zone requires intensive monitoring for bark beetle outbreaks to protect the remaining unburned timber.
3. Tier 3 (Ecological Recovery): Focused on over 900 hectares of Codes 13 and 23. These areas should be prioritized for natural succession and protected from heavy machinery to allow the existing seed bank to regenerate.

The Biodiversity Refugia (Codes 11 & 21 - Unburned), the 746.12 hectares of unburned forest within the perimeter are critical biological islands. These areas must be strictly protected from logging or heavy machinery traffic during the restoration phase. They will serve as the primary source of seeds for natural dispersal into the adjacent burned areas (Codes 25 and 15).

Ultimately, this Google Earth Engine-based approach demonstrates that high-resolution remote sensing can bridge the gap between rapid emergency response and long-term sustainable forest management. The resulting 12-element classification map serves as a living document for the restoration of the Ilindentsi forest landscape, ensuring that interventions are applied exactly where the ecology demands them most.

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How to Create the Best SOAR Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Strategic analytical frameworks are widely used in academic research and institutional planning; however, strength-based models such as SOAR (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results) often lack standardized validation and measurable operationalization procedures. While SOAR is conceptually grounded in Appreciative Inquiry and positive organizational scholarship, many applications remain facilitative rather than analytically structured. This methodological gap limits transparency, comparability, and replicability across studies. This article develops a structured SOAR Validation and Measurability Model designed to enhance analytical rigor and strategic coherence. The proposed framework integrates three interrelated components – a Validation Layer establishing empirical grounding criteria, a Measurability Layer operationalizing aspirations through performance indicators, and a Strategic Alignment Flow ensuring logical progression from strengths to measurable results. The model introduces a Result Operationalization Matrix linking aspirations to defined KPIs, baseline values, target levels, time horizons, and responsible units. By embedding validation mechanisms and performance measurement principles into the SOAR framework, the study advances strength-based strategy from dialogical reflection toward evidence-based strategic management. The proposed model contributes methodological clarity, improves accountability, and increases applicability across governance, organizational development, and sustainability planning contexts.

Keywords: *SOAR analysis, Strategic management, Strategic planning, Organizational analysis, Performance measurement, SWOT analysis, PESTEL analysis, Validation framework, Strategic alignment, Strength-based strategy*

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INTRODUCTION

Strategic analytical frameworks play a central role in academic research, organizational governance, and policy design. In environments characterized by complexity, uncertainty, and rapid

transformation, scholars increasingly rely on structured methodologies capable of systematically evaluating institutional capacities, environmental dynamics, and long-term development trajectories (Mintzberg, Ahlstrand, & Lampel, 1998; Porter, 1985). Among the most widely applied tools in strategic research are SWOT and PESTEL, frequently used in management studies, sustainability analysis, tourism planning, public administration, and regional development research (Gürel & Tat, 2017; Sammut-Bonnici & Galea, 2015).

While SWOT analysis provides a structured assessment of internal strengths and weaknesses alongside external opportunities and threats, its diagnostic structure often emphasizes deficit-oriented evaluation (Gürel & Tat, 2017). Similarly, macro-environmental scanning instruments such as PESTEL concentrate primarily on systemic external pressures shaping strategic contexts (Sammut-Bonnici & Galea, 2015). Empirical applications demonstrate the analytical robustness of these frameworks across socio-economic and sustainability research domains (Karadzhev, 2016; Karadzhev & Yuleva-Chuchulayna, 2024).

Building upon these analytical traditions, recent methodological work has emphasized the importance of enhancing validation mechanisms and structured reporting standards within strategic frameworks. In particular, methodological refinements integrating SWOT and PESTEL approaches have demonstrated how analytical tools can evolve toward greater transparency and reproducibility in academic research (Karadzhev, 2025). These developments indicate a broader trend toward systematizing strategic models through measurable criteria and structured evaluation logic.

However, the increasing complexity of contemporary institutional environments – including digital transformation, sustainability transitions, governance reform, and organizational resilience – has stimulated growing interest in strength-based and solution-oriented analytical models (Cameron, Dutton, & Quinn, 2003). In contexts marked by crisis, volatility, and institutional uncertainty, traditional deficit-focused approaches may unintentionally reinforce problem-centered narratives. By contrast, strength-based frameworks aim to mobilize existing capabilities, align stakeholders around shared aspirations, and design measurable pathways for future development.

Within this intellectual evolution, the SOAR framework – Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results – emerged as a strength-based alternative rooted in Appreciative Inquiry theory (Cooperrider & Srivastva, 1987; Stavros & Hinrichs, 2009). Unlike SWOT, which balances positive and negative dimensions, SOAR intentionally centers strategic reflection on strengths and future-oriented aspirations. It encourages collaborative dialogue, participatory engagement, and the translation of shared visions into measurable outcomes.

Despite its growing adoption in organizational development, education management, and community planning, the academic operationalization of SOAR remains comparatively underdeveloped. Although empirical validation efforts confirm its construct structure and measurement potential (Cole, Stavros, & Hinrichs, 2022), standardized methodological guidance – including validation criteria, alignment logic, and measurable results frameworks – is still limited in peer-reviewed literature. This methodological gap constrains comparability, transparency, and analytical rigor across studies employing SOAR.

Recent scholarship in strategic evaluation further underscores the necessity of integrating structured decision-support logic into qualitative strategic models. Bryson, Edwards, and Van Slyke (2018) argue that public value governance increasingly requires transparent alignment between strategic intent and measurable performance outcomes. Similarly, Kaplan and Norton's (2001) later work on strategy-focused organizations emphasizes the importance of translating vision into operational metrics across institutional contexts. These perspectives reinforce the argument that

strength-based strategic models must incorporate structured validation and measurable accountability mechanisms in order to remain analytically robust.

The aim of the present article is to develop a validation-focused and measurability-driven framework for conducting rigorous SOAR analysis in academic and applied strategic contexts. The study introduces a SOAR Validation Model and a Measurable Results Framework designed to enhance analytical coherence, reduce subjectivity, and improve reporting standards. By clarifying conceptual foundations and establishing methodological guidance, this article seeks to strengthen the scholarly credibility and practical utility of strength-based strategic analysis.

This study completes a methodological trilogy aimed at strengthening major strategic analytical frameworks – SWOT, PESTEL, and SOAR – by progressively enhancing structure, validation logic, and measurable operationalization.

The specific objectives of this study are:

- To clarify the conceptual foundations and theoretical evolution of the SOAR framework;
- To establish methodological validation criteria that enhance rigor and reduce subjectivity in SOAR applications;
- To develop a structured Measurable Results Framework that operationalizes aspirations into clearly defined performance indicators;
- To provide practical guidelines and reporting standards suitable for academic research, strategic planning, and policy design contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To position the SOAR framework within contemporary academic discourse, it is necessary to examine its theoretical origins, structural evolution, empirical operationalization, and methodological critiques. The following sections synthesize foundational and recent research in order to identify both strengths and unresolved challenges within SOAR-based strategic analysis.

Theoretical Foundations – Appreciative Inquiry and Positive Organizational Scholarship

The conceptual roots of SOAR analysis can be traced to Appreciative Inquiry (AI), a strength-based theory of organizational change introduced by Cooperrider and Srivastva (1987). In contrast to deficit-oriented diagnostic models, Appreciative Inquiry proposes that organizations evolve in the direction of the questions they most persistently ask. By focusing on strengths, achievements, and positive core processes, AI seeks to generate constructive transformation rather than corrective intervention (Cooperrider & Srivastva, 1987).

The philosophical foundations of AI were later reinforced within the broader field of Positive Organizational Scholarship. Cameron, Dutton, and Quinn (2003) argue that sustainable institutional performance is enhanced when strategic processes emphasize resilience, virtuous practices, and capability development. This strength-based paradigm challenged traditional risk-centered frameworks and created a theoretical environment conducive to the emergence of SOAR.

Further theoretical reflection on Appreciative Inquiry emphasizes its generative capacity in large-scale system change. Bushe and Marshak (2009) identify AI as part of a dialogic turn in organizational development, where meaning-making and collaborative sense-making become central strategic processes. This dialogical orientation strongly influenced the participatory design of SOAR.

While Appreciative Inquiry provides philosophical grounding, it does not offer a fixed analytical structure. The development of SOAR can therefore be understood as an attempt to translate AI principles into a practical, structured strategic framework.

Conceptual Structure and Operational Evolution of SOAR

Building upon these theoretical foundations, the SOAR framework was introduced by Stavros and Hinrichs (2009) as a structured model for strength-based strategic planning. The framework organizes strategic inquiry around four interconnected dimensions – Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results – designed to move organizations from reflection to measurable implementation.

Unlike SWOT analysis, which includes weaknesses and threats as analytical categories, SOAR intentionally concentrates on generative potential. Stavros, Cooperrider, and Kelley (2003) argue that strategic conversations centered on strengths and aspirations foster greater alignment and stakeholder engagement than problem-focused analytical processes.

Empirical operationalization advanced significantly with the development of the SOAR Scale. Cole, Stavros, and Hinrichs (2022) validated a 12-item instrument capturing the four SOAR constructs and demonstrated their internal consistency and construct validity. This study provided one of the first systematic quantitative assessments of the framework, shifting SOAR from primarily facilitative practice toward measurable academic application.

The framework has since been referenced in leadership development, organizational transformation, and participatory planning research. However, applications remain heterogeneous, often relying on workshop-based qualitative methodologies without standardized validation or performance measurement criteria.

This structural flexibility represents both a strength and a limitation – it enhances adaptability while complicating cross-study comparability.

Comparison with Deficit-Oriented Strategic Frameworks

To fully understand SOAR's positioning, it is necessary to compare it with deficit-oriented strategic models, particularly SWOT.

SWOT analysis remains one of the most widely applied strategic planning tools across management and policy contexts (Gürel & Tat, 2017). Its four-dimensional structure allows for systematic assessment of internal and external environments. However, several scholars argue that SWOT's inclusion of weaknesses and threats may encourage reactive rather than generative strategy formation (Helms & Nixon, 2010). Helms and Nixon (2010), in their comprehensive review of SWOT applications, note that while SWOT is adaptable and intuitive, it often lacks methodological rigor in factor prioritization and validation procedures. These critiques parallel challenges later observed in SOAR implementation.

PESTEL analysis, as another macro-environmental framework, focuses on external systemic forces shaping organizational environments (Sammuto-Bonnici & Galea, 2015). While analytically robust for environmental scanning, it does not directly address aspirational alignment or performance translation.

In contrast, SOAR explicitly integrates strategic aspiration and measurable results into its structure. This forward-looking orientation differentiates it conceptually, yet the absence of standardized validation and performance metrics remains a shared limitation across strategic frameworks.

Methodological Gaps in Strength-Based Strategic Research

Despite increasing adoption, the academic literature reveals several unresolved methodological challenges in strength-based strategic analysis.

First, narrative-driven appreciative processes often lack explicit validation mechanisms linking identified strengths to empirical indicators (Bushe & Marshak, 2009). Without structured evaluation criteria, strength-based frameworks risk subjective over-interpretation.

Second, although the SOAR Scale provides psychometric support (Cole et al., 2022), standardized reporting protocols for academic SOAR studies remain absent. Variations in workshop design, stakeholder participation, and result measurement complicate reproducibility.

Third, critiques of appreciative models caution against uncritical optimism. Grant and Humphries (2006) argue that strength-based inquiry must be balanced by reflective scrutiny to avoid normative bias.

These gaps highlight the need for a structured validation layer, measurable results framework, and alignment logic capable of strengthening methodological transparency. Addressing this need forms the foundation of the present study's contribution.

METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the structured methodological framework developed to enhance validation, measurability, and strategic coherence within SOAR analysis.

A Validation-Focused and Measurable SOAR Model

To address the methodological gaps identified in the previous section, this study proposes a structured model designed to enhance rigor, transparency, and replicability in SOAR applications. The proposed framework integrates three interrelated components – Validation Layer, Measurability Layer, and Alignment Layer – collectively forming the SOAR Validation and Measurable Model.

The objective of this methodological design is to transform SOAR from a primarily facilitative and dialogical tool into a structured analytical instrument suitable for academic research and strategic evaluation contexts.

The Validation Layer – Ensuring Analytical Credibility

Before translating strengths and aspirations into strategic action, it is necessary to establish criteria that ensure analytical robustness.

The Validation Layer introduces structured verification principles for each SOAR component:

A. Strengths Validation

Identified strengths must be supported by verifiable evidence rather than solely by stakeholder perception or normative assumptions. In many practical applications, strengths are articulated through workshop dialogue without systematic examination of empirical indicators. While participatory reflection is consistent with Appreciative Inquiry principles, academic application requires a higher level of analytical substantiation.

Validated strengths should therefore be grounded in measurable performance indicators, benchmarking comparisons, audited results, documented achievements, longitudinal performance data, or triangulated stakeholder consensus supported by qualitative documentation. Where

quantitative evidence is unavailable, structured qualitative validation – such as documented case outcomes or formal institutional assessments – should be provided. Failure to validate strengths empirically risks inflationary bias, over-optimistic self-assessment, and reduced analytical credibility.

The Validation Layer thus requires that strengths demonstrate demonstrable institutional capacity rather than aspirational identity claims.

B. Opportunities Grounding

Opportunities must be anchored in systematically identified external developments rather than speculative projections. In several applied SOAR exercises, opportunities are formulated without explicit reference to macro-environmental analysis, resulting in disconnection between internal capabilities and contextual realities. Grounded opportunities should be justified through external data sources such as market analyses, policy frameworks, technological innovation trends, demographic shifts, regulatory changes, or sustainability transitions research. This external anchoring ensures compatibility with environmental scanning models such as PESTEL and reduces strategic misalignment.

The purpose of grounding opportunities is not to constrain visionary thinking but to situate generative aspiration within empirically observable environmental dynamics. Without such grounding, strategic planning may drift toward unrealistic expansion or unfeasible innovation pathways.

C. Aspirations Specification

Aspirations represent the normative and future-oriented dimension of SOAR; however, they frequently suffer from conceptual vagueness. Statements such as “become a leader,” “enhance excellence,” or “increase visibility” lack analytical precision unless operationally specified.

The Validation Layer therefore requires that aspirations meet minimum criteria of strategic clarity. Aspirations should be:

- Specific in scope
- Coherent with validated strengths and grounded opportunities
- Realistically attainable within institutional capacity
- Time-sensitive or strategically phased

Articulated aspirations must demonstrate internal logical consistency within the alignment chain. Vague or overly broad aspirational language weakens comparability across studies and reduces the methodological reliability of the SOAR framework.

D. Results Operationalization

Results constitute the most critical validation checkpoint within the SOAR structure. While the framework includes “Results” as a formal dimension, many applications fail to translate them into measurable and accountable performance architecture.

The Validation Layer requires that results be operationalized through defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), documented baseline values, explicit target levels, defined implementation timelines, and identifiable responsible units or governance actors.

This structured operationalization ensures that results are not merely symbolic affirmations of aspiration but measurable outcomes subject to evaluation and revision. By embedding measurable

indicators, the SOAR framework becomes compatible with performance management theory, accountability systems, and governance transparency standards.

The absence of operationalized results represents the most significant methodological vulnerability in conventional SOAR applications. The proposed Validation Layer addresses this vulnerability directly by embedding measurable accountability into the framework’s final stage.

Table 1. SOAR Validation Checklist

Dimension	Validation Question	Required Evidence	Risk if Missing
Strengths	Are strengths data-supported?	Quantitative or documented proof	Over-optimism
Opportunities	Are opportunities externally justified?	Market/policy data	Strategic misalignment
Aspirations	Are aspirations specific and time-bound?	Strategic objectives	Vision ambiguity
Results	Are results measurable?	KPIs & target values	No accountability

The Measurability Layer – Translating Aspirations into Indicators

Building upon the validation principles, the second methodological component focuses on operationalization.

The conceptual logic underlying this operationalization process is illustrated in Figure 1, which visualizes the transformation of strategic aspirations into measurable and accountable performance architecture.

Although SOAR conceptually includes “Results,” many applications do not clearly define performance indicators (Cole et al., 2022). To address this limitation, the present framework introduces a structured Result Operationalization Matrix.

This matrix ensures that each aspiration is connected to:

- A measurable indicator
- A baseline value
- A desired target
- A timeframe
- A responsible stakeholder

Beyond ensuring operational clarity, this structured linkage transforms SOAR from a visionary reflection tool into a performance-integrated strategic framework. By explicitly connecting aspirations to measurable indicators, temporal benchmarks, and governance responsibility, the model introduces traceability into the strategic process.

This traceability enhances accountability, facilitates longitudinal evaluation, and supports evidence-based revision of strategic plans. In doing so, the Result Operationalization Matrix strengthens methodological transparency and enables comparative analysis across institutional and sectoral contexts.

To clarify the structural transformation from aspirational intent to measurable implementation, a visual representation of the operational logic is necessary. The schematic presented below synthesizes the internal progression through which aspirations are decomposed into indicators, performance benchmarks, and accountability structures. This visual articulation enhances conceptual transparency and supports methodological reproducibility in empirical applications.

Fig. 1. Result operationalization logic within the SOAR Validation and Measurability Model.

By integrating performance measurement theory principles (Kaplan & Norton, 1996), SOAR can be aligned with balanced scorecard approaches and strategic performance management systems.

The Alignment Layer – Ensuring Strategic Coherence

The third component of the proposed model addresses the internal logical consistency of the SOAR process.

Strategic coherence requires that:

- Strengths → enable Opportunities
- Opportunities → justify Aspirations
- Aspirations → translate into measurable Results

If this logical sequence is absent, the analysis risks fragmentation.

Given the importance of internal logical coherence within strategic models, a schematic alignment structure is required to illustrate directional interdependence across the SOAR dimensions. The diagram below visualizes how validated strengths enable opportunities, how opportunities substantiate aspirations, and how aspirations ultimately translate into measurable results. By making this progression explicit, the model reduces fragmentation and enhances analytical integrity.

Fig. 2. Strategic alignment flow within the SOAR Validation and Measurability Model.

The Alignment Layer therefore introduces a directional verification principle – each dimension must demonstrably support the subsequent one. The integrated alignment logic of the enhanced SOAR framework is presented in Figure 2, illustrating the sequential progression and reinforcement loop that ensure strategic coherence.

This alignment logic strengthens methodological transparency and enhances reproducibility across studies. It also integrates strength-based strategy with performance management literature (Helms & Nixon, 2010).

DISCUSSION

The present study introduced a structured SOAR Validation and Measurability Model designed to address key methodological limitations in strength-based strategic analysis. The discussion section evaluates how the proposed framework contributes to theoretical clarity, analytical rigor, and practical applicability.

Conceptual Advancement

Existing literature positions SOAR as a strength-based and generative strategic framework rooted in Appreciative Inquiry (Cooperrider & Srivastva, 1987; Stavros & Hinrichs, 2009). However, prior applications have frequently relied on workshop-based facilitation without standardized validation and operationalization procedures (Grant & Humphries, 2006; Cole et al., 2022).

By integrating three structured layers – Validation, Measurability, and Alignment – the present model advances SOAR from a primarily dialogical methodology to a performance-aware analytical framework. This conceptual shift enhances its suitability for academic research and institutional strategic planning.

The introduction of explicit validation criteria reduces normative subjectivity, while measurable indicators improve comparability across applications. Consequently, the framework strengthens the methodological robustness of strength-based strategy.

Methodological Contribution

The principal methodological contribution of this article lies in translating aspirational language into operational strategic architecture.

The Result Operationalization Matrix ensures that each aspiration is anchored in measurable performance indicators, baseline values, target levels, defined time horizons, and responsible units. This integration aligns SOAR with established performance management principles (Kaplan & Norton, 1996), thereby reinforcing accountability mechanisms.

From a methodological standpoint, the integration of measurable indicators within qualitative strategic frameworks also resonates with contemporary debates on mixed-methods rigor and performance transparency (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). By structuring aspirational narratives through operational metrics, the enhanced SOAR model contributes to bridging interpretive strategic dialogue with quantitative evaluation logic.

Furthermore, the Alignment Flow model formalizes the logical sequence linking strengths to measurable results. This directional coherence minimizes fragmentation in strategy formation and supports replicability in academic research contexts.

Positioning within Strategic Frameworks

Compared with SWOT and PESTEL, the enhanced SOAR model retains its forward-looking and generative orientation while addressing recurring critiques of insufficient methodological precision (Helms & Nixon, 2010; Gürel & Tat, 2017).

Where SWOT combines positive and negative diagnostic elements and PESTEL focuses on macro-environmental scanning, the present framework positions SOAR as a strength-based model integrated with validation and measurement logic. This positioning strengthens its applicability within governance, sustainability transitions, higher education management, and organizational development research.

IMPLICATIONS

The implications of the proposed model extend across academic, managerial, and educational domains.

Implications for Academic Research

Researchers applying SOAR in empirical studies can utilize the Validation and Measurability framework to improve transparency and methodological consistency. The structured alignment logic enhances comparability between case studies and supports systematic reporting.

The model also provides a replicable template that may facilitate meta-analytical research on strength-based strategic planning.

Implications for Strategic Governance

Public institutions and organizations can employ the proposed model to strengthen accountability in strategic processes. By linking aspirations to measurable results and clearly assigning responsibility, decision-makers can better align strategic vision with performance evaluation mechanisms.

This is particularly relevant in sustainability-oriented governance contexts, where aspirational commitments frequently require operational translation.

In sustainability transitions research, the alignment between strategic ambition and measurable indicators is increasingly recognized as essential for policy credibility and stakeholder trust (Meadowcroft, 2011). Embedding measurable accountability within strength-based strategic processes therefore enhances the governance relevance of SOAR applications beyond organizational contexts.

Implications for Methodological Education

As SOAR is frequently introduced in business education, public administration, and strategic management courses, the proposed framework enhances pedagogical clarity. Students and practitioners gain a structured understanding of how strength-based strategy can transition from conceptual reflection to measurable implementation.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite its contributions, the present study has certain limitations.

First, the proposed model remains conceptual and methodological rather than empirically tested across multiple institutional contexts. Future research should apply the Validation and Measurability Model to case studies in higher education, regional governance, sustainability planning, and organizational development to evaluate its practical robustness.

Second, further quantitative research could explore the integration of weighted scoring systems within SOAR dimensions to enhance prioritization mechanisms.

Third, comparative studies examining performance outcomes of traditional SOAR applications versus the enhanced validation model would provide valuable empirical insights.

CONCLUSION

This article developed a structured SOAR Validation and Measurability Model aimed at strengthening analytical rigor, accountability, and strategic coherence within strength-based strategic analysis. By identifying methodological gaps in existing SOAR applications and proposing a layered validation architecture, the study advances the framework beyond its predominantly facilitative and dialogical origins.

The integration of explicit validation criteria enhances the evidential grounding of strengths and opportunities, reducing normative bias and subjective over-interpretation. Simultaneously, the Result

Operationalization Matrix transforms aspirational statements into measurable, time-bound, and accountable strategic objectives. This operational shift aligns SOAR with contemporary performance management theory and strengthens its compatibility with institutional governance and evaluation systems.

The introduction of a structured alignment flow further reinforces the internal logical coherence of the framework. By formalizing the progression from validated strengths to measurable results, the model reduces fragmentation in strategic analysis and supports methodological replicability across empirical contexts.

Taken together, these contributions reposition SOAR as a performance-aware and validation-integrated analytical instrument. The framework retains its generative, strength-based philosophy while embedding structured mechanisms that enhance transparency, comparability, and academic robustness.

As strategic planning environments continue to evolve under conditions of uncertainty, sustainability transitions, and institutional complexity, methodologies that balance aspirational orientation with measurable accountability become increasingly necessary. The proposed model contributes to this evolution by bridging the gap between visionary strategic discourse and evidence-based performance architecture.

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From Newtonian Economics to Quantum Uncertainty: The Revolution Reshaping Economic Theory

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ABSTRACT

The article explores the transition from “Newtonian Economics,” grounded in deterministic and linear models, toward a new condition referred to in the study as “Quantum Uncertainty.” Drawing upon the quantum revolution, it highlights how the technological, epistemological, and social dynamics of the 21st century are causing a profound rupture in the foundational assumptions of economic theory. The study argues that the quantum shift is not confined to computational power, but conceptually reconstructs the notions of information, uncertainty, risk, and prediction – rejecting the neutrality of observation and the rationality of Homo Economicus. At the same time, it addresses the uneven geopolitical distribution of computational supremacy and the emerging institutional asymmetry. The comparison between the two paradigms underscores the need for a new epistemological framework, an economic thought that embraces radical uncertainty, participatory information (open data, collective intelligence), and open, nonlinear models of economic reality.

Keywords: *Predictability, Collective intelligence, Quantum uncertainty, Technological supremacy, Rationality, Epistemic modelling*

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INTRODUCTION

The title ‘*From Newtonian Economics to Quantum Uncertainty*’ is not merely a poetic metaphor, but rather signifies a deeper conceptual and methodological shift in economic thought, encapsulating the fundamental concern with the nature of economic knowledge in the 21st century. The issue at

stake is not simply whether the new technological era provides more tools, but, more importantly, whether it demands a radical reconfiguration of the theoretical and methodological arsenal of science.

*'Newtonian Economics'*¹ symbolizes the classical scientific paradigm of stability, predictability, and causality. However, this paradigm appears increasingly inadequate in the face of the complexity and indeterminacy of modern markets. Can economic thought remain predictive in a universe of radical uncertainty? This question is not merely technical; it is conceptual and epistemological. It touches the very core of economic theory, as it challenges the capacity to model and control a dynamically unstable and fundamentally unpredictable world. Within this framework, economic agents are assumed to act rationally, to possess full information, and to be guided – through market mechanisms – towards equilibria that can be mathematically described. This paradigm dominated for decades, forming the basis for most macroeconomic models and for mainstream economic thinking.

On the other hand, *'Quantum Uncertainty'*² represents a new ontological and epistemic condition in which uncertainty is endogenous and irreducible. Inspired by quantum physics, this perspective emphasizes indeterminacy, entropy, and the role of observation in the very formation of the phenomenon. Information is neither complete nor objective; it is fragmented, subjective, and at times generates self-fulfilling expectations. Within this new framework, linear relationships and equilibrium points become unstable – or even obsolete (Beinhocker, 2006; Kay & King, 2020).

This study, through a review of the literature, concludes that the quantum revolution of the 21st century – not only as a technology but as a mode of thinking – reconfigures economic theory. Computational superiority, new forms of information, asymmetric flows of power, and the growing entropy of markets³ render the need for a new paradigm not only timely, but imperative. Economic theory is now called upon to abandon the illusion of control and to embrace uncertainty not as an adversary, but as a foundational element of reality.

Through an interdisciplinary and conceptually reflective methodology, this study undertakes a conceptual reconstruction of the foundations of economic thought, drawing upon the history of science, epistemology, the natural sciences, and especially quantum mechanics (Beinhocker, 2006; Kay & King, 2020).

NEWTONIAN ECONOMICS AS A PARADIGM

Newtonian Determinism: Causality, Prediction, and Mechanistic Regularity

Newtonian physics constitutes the foundation of the classical scientific worldview, introducing an ontological and methodological framework grounded in causal determinism. According to Isaac Newton, the universe is a vast, fully predictable machine – provided that we know its initial conditions and the laws governing it. Causality here is not merely a philosophical principle but also a tool for prediction, since every phenomenon has a clear, traceable cause and leads to a predictable outcome (Newton, 1999).

The Newtonian approach formulates nature through mathematical laws that precisely describe the behavior of bodies in space and time. This *'mechanistic regularity'*⁴ is exemplified in Laplace's (1951) famous assertion that, if a mind knew the exact position and velocity of all particles in the universe, it could predict the future with absolute precision.

This deterministic worldview played a decisive role in the development of science as a tool of control and prediction, fostering the belief that the natural world operates with absolute order and that uncertainty is merely the result of ignorance or technical limitations in measurement, rather than an

inherent feature of reality (Popper, 1957). This scientific paradigm, in turn, was transferred as an epistemological model to other disciplines – including economics – shaping the expectation for fully mathematized and equilibrated models of prediction and regularity.

This is exemplified in neoclassical general equilibrium models, where the market is assumed to reach stable equilibria through the interaction of fully informed and rational agents. Furthermore, rational expectations theories (Lucas, 1972) incorporate the assumption that economic actors correctly anticipate the future based on the same models used by analysts, reinforcing the deterministic belief in informational completeness and linear predictability.

The same worldview is embedded in contemporary tools such as Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) models, which – despite their stochastic nature – rely on the assumption of a return to equilibrium and full rationality. It is also reflected in Value at Risk (VaR), where financial risk is represented as a predictable quantity within defined probabilistic bounds.

However, since the early 20th century – and especially with the advent of quantum mechanics – this foundational certainty of classical physics began to be challenged, paving the way for new, non-deterministic interpretations of reality.

Reflections in Economic Theories

The Newtonian deterministic and mechanistic worldview found its theoretical reflection in economic thought through the emergence of Homo Economicus and the development of mathematical equilibrium models. The economic man is depicted as a fully rational agent, with coherent preferences, perfect information, and unlimited computational capacity (Persky, 1995). Within this framework, deviations from equilibrium are considered temporary or exogenous anomalies, rather than endogenous characteristics of the system itself.

The general equilibrium framework (Arrow & Debreu, 1954) and Ramsey-type models (Ramsey, 1928) in macroeconomics embody this particular perspective, aiming to depict the economic system as a closed and predictable whole, wherein prices and quantities move toward equilibrium points according to the rules of the market.

This evolution culminates in the neoclassical synthesis and, later, in the Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) models, which are extensively employed by central banks and policy-oriented economic institutes (Woodford, 2003). These models attempt to incorporate shocks and uncertainties within a deterministic framework, assuming that the economy tends toward an equilibrium point, even if through temporary disturbances and fluctuations.

Although they incorporate stochastic elements, DSGE models typically rely on linear approximations and on the fundamental assumption that the economy stabilizes around a unique equilibrium. This approach often overlooks the unpredictability and multiple instability regimes observed in real economic dynamics. Similarly, tools such as Value at Risk reflect the belief that risk can be quantified within strict statistical frameworks, effectively reducing radical uncertainty to technical volatility.

The mathematization of economics, while it introduced significant rigor and formalism, was accompanied by a detachment from the real, complex, and uncertain nature of economic phenomena. As Mirowski (1989) notes, the influence of physics – particularly classical mechanics, proved decisive in shaping the tools and paradigms of modern economic theory.

Despite its internal limitations and the critiques it has received, the Newtonian influence went beyond mere metaphorical borrowing and became a structural foundation for the way economics is

conceived – as a system that can be analyzed, predicted, and controlled through strict laws. This conception is now being fundamentally challenged in an era defined by uncertainty and complexity.

Economic ‘neutrality’ as an ideology of stability

The diffusion of formalistic and deterministic models in economic science did not remain confined to theory, but fundamentally shaped the way economic policy is practiced and legitimized. Thus, the dominance of the mathematically expressed neoclassical model extended beyond the scientific domain of economic analysis, exerting a decisive influence on public policy and ideology as well. The notion that the economy is a neutral and technically predictable system reinforced the belief that governance can and should be based on ‘*objective*’ economic models, irrespective of social and political conditions (Rodrik, 2015).

Within this framework, economic ‘*neutrality*’ functions as an ideological construct that conceals the value-laden and political nature of economic choices (Fourcade, 2009). The purported independence of economics from ideological contexts is reinforced through the language of mathematics, technocracy (i.e., governance by ‘experts’ based on models), and the depoliticization of the public sphere (Amable, 2011). In this context, the market is portrayed as a natural system that spontaneously gravitates toward equilibrium and stability, provided it is not disrupted by exogenous interventions.

This approach contributed to the consolidation of the ideology of stability: the notion that the primary task of political and institutional actors is to ensure the conditions that allow for the ‘spontaneous’ operation of markets. This ideology found its political expression in the neoliberal turn of the 1980s and 1990s, through the rise of independent central banks, strict fiscal rules, and the deregulation of markets (Harvey, 2005). The function of economic ‘neutrality’ became particularly evident during periods such as the Eurozone debt crisis, when austerity policies were presented as ‘*technically inevitable*’.

However, this purported economic neutrality has proven to be deeply politically charged. As Dani Rodrik (2015) argues, ‘technical’ economic solutions are always embedded in social conflicts and policy choices, even when presented as scientifically necessary. The invocation of stability as a supreme value often serves to preserve existing power structures and to prevent radical changes to the economic or social status quo.

The questioning of the ‘neutrality’ of economic science thus opens the way for a more critical and pluralistic approach, in which economic knowledge is not detached from its historical and political context, but is instead situated within it.

QUANTUM UNCERTAINTY AS AN ONTOLOGICAL RUPTURE

The Philosophy of Indeterminacy

The quantum revolution in the natural sciences – particularly the contributions of Heisenberg, Bohr, and more recent thinkers such as Karen Barad – brought about a radical rupture with the Newtonian worldview (Barad, 2007; Rovelli, 2016; Zohar, 2022). At the heart of this rupture lies the principle of indeterminacy (Heisenberg, 1927), according to which certain physical quantities, such as a particle’s position and momentum, cannot be simultaneously determined with absolute precision, regardless of the instruments of observation.

This uncertainty is not a technical limitation or an indication of incomplete knowledge; it arises from the very structure of reality itself and thus constitutes a fundamental ontological principle. This position stands in stark opposition to the epistemology of Newtonian physics, where prediction is regarded merely as a matter of information (Smolin, 2019; Rovelli, 2021).

If uncertainty is indeed intrinsic, how is the relationship between observer and observed transformed? Bohr introduces the notion of complementarity, according to which phenomena such as light may exhibit contradictory properties - particle or wave - depending on the conditions of observation. Within this framework, the observer is neither external nor neutral; they participate in the very constitution of the phenomenon itself (Bohr, 1934). The notion of prediction, central to the Newtonian worldview, is here transformed into a dialectical process of interaction rather than a passive extraction of rules.

Barad radically extends this position, arguing that knowledge does not merely observe the world but is co-constituted with it through active and material practices of observation. Through the concept of agential realism, she rejects any separation between observer and reality, proposing instead that every act of measurement is simultaneously an act of meaning-making (Barad, 2007).

Within this philosophical framework, uncertainty ceases to be an obstacle to be overcome and becomes a foundation for understanding. Participation in the world is not grounded in predictability but in participatory uncertainty as a condition of existence. If such radical uncertainty characterizes physical reality, then it cannot be disregarded in the understanding of social and economic phenomena, where the observer actively participates in shaping the very field of inquiry.

From Precision to Probability

The shift from the Newtonian demand for precision to the stochastic representation of reality concerns not only the natural sciences but also bears significant implications for economic theory. Traditional macroeconomic thought, particularly in DSGE models, relies on linear causality and the expectation of fully informed rational agents. However, stochastic variables are merely introduced as 'shocks' to an otherwise stable system, rather than as structural features of that system (Kay & King, 2020).

Quantum theory, by contrast, suggests that probability is not a deviation from precision but a fundamental framework for understanding. Just as the collapse of the wave function is non-deterministic, so too economic collapse, the destabilization of trust or of prices, cannot always be explained through a clear causal chain (Peters, 2016; Busemeyer & Bruza, 2016).

At the same time, the concept of entropy finds application in economic systems, particularly in markets characterized by high uncertainty and in algorithmic financial practices. In such environments, the accumulation of information does not reduce uncertainty, on the contrary, it structures and displaces it. Informational entropy is directly linked to financial instability, the multiplicity of narratives, and the failure to predict systemic events (Beinhocker, 2006), such as the 2008 financial crisis or the collapse of Silicon Valley Bank, which eluded explanation through linear models.

Within this framework, the evolution of technology is not merely a matter of application, but operates as an embodied expression of a new epistemological condition. The development of quantum information science is not solely about computational power. It introduces a new paradigm in which complexity and ambiguity are not obstacles but resources for understanding and reconstructing economic reasoning (Orrell, 2020).

The New Epistemology of Information

In digital and post-algorithmic capitalism⁵, information is no longer a static and complete entity to be collected and computed, but a fragmented and fluid assemblage of signals, correlations, and narratives. Contemporary economic knowledge is formed through continuous data flows, partially opaque algorithms, and predictive models that function more as generators of expectations than as mirrors of reality (Mackenzie, 2017). This is evident in financial markets, where risk or valuation models shape investor behavior rather than merely describing the *'real'* state of affairs.

Within this framework, quantum information science is not merely a technological leap but a model of understanding: information is non-clonable, relational, and dependent on the context of measurement (Aaronson, 2013). The principle of indeterminacy intersects with market complexity, nonlinear effects, and the volatility of human expectation.

This new epistemology acknowledges that economic knowledge is contingent, mediated, and politically charged (Rodrik, 2015). Prediction is not a neutral process but a form of performative intervention in the future. The model itself participates in producing the very reality it purports to describe.

As quantum computing accelerates the processing of complex possible states, the need emerges for an interpretive economic theory, one capable of integrating uncertainty as a foundation rather than a flaw. Knowledge is no longer a tool of prediction, but a strategy of adaptation and embodied judgment.

DISCUSSION

The following discussion examines how the quantum rupture in physical thought, centered on indeterminacy, relationality, and non-deterministic dynamics, redefines foundational concepts in economic theory. The notion of radical uncertainty (Knight, 1921; Kay & King, 2020) is no longer treated as a deviant exception, but as a central element of understanding. At the same time, the emergence of quantum computing introduces not only new tools, but also a new mode of thinking about information, modeling, and prediction (Orrell, 2020; Aaronson, 2013).

Quantum thought -as an epistemological and technological shift- opens the way for an economic theory that embraces uncertainty, dynamic complexity, and reflexivity as structural features of reality.

From Newtonian Certainty to Quantum Uncertainty

Classical science, as it was primarily shaped within the framework of Newtonian physics, established a deterministic and predictable model for understanding reality, wherein every phenomenon could be reduced to definitive cause–effect relationships. Nature was conceived as a mechanical system which, under appropriate initial conditions, could be fully described through mathematical equations (Ladyman & Ross, 2007).

This conception profoundly influenced classical economic theory as well, in which economic agents -the Homo Economicus archetype- are assumed to be fully rational, equipped with perfect information and stable preferences, and are led in a predictable manner to equilibria through market mechanisms (Mirowski, 2013). Equilibrium, as the mathematical point of gravity in the models, was established as the analytical ideal.

The quantum revolution of the 20th century radically challenged this worldview. Heisenberg's uncertainty principle introduces the notion that certain physical quantities – such as the position and

momentum of a particle – cannot be simultaneously determined with precision, not due to limitations in measurement, but as an intrinsic feature of nature itself (Heisenberg, 1927). Bohr deepened this rupture through the concept of complementarity, arguing that observation plays a constitutive role in the very formation of the phenomenon (Bohr, 1934).

In contemporary philosophy of science, Karen Barad transforms these ideas into an ontological framework she terms *agential realism*. According to Barad (2007), knowledge is not a neutral representation but a *material-discursive practice*⁶, in which both the observer and the phenomenon are co-constituted through the process of measurement. Uncertainty is no longer treated as an instrumental limitation but as a fundamental condition of reality.

In the realm of economic theory, the adoption of a probabilistic framework as a substitute for determinism is not new. However, even the most advanced stochastic models often retain a deterministic underpinning, where uncertainty is incorporated as an external shock or a technical deviation (Kay & King, 2020). The quantum perspective counters this by proposing that uncertainty is not a deviation from precision, but rather a framework for understanding, a conception that directly challenges the logic of absolute control and predictability in economic thought (Rovelli, 2021).

Thus, the shift from Newtonian certainty to quantum indeterminacy constitutes not only an epistemological rupture but also a critique of the model of economic rationality. Economic phenomena – such as crises of confidence, price collapses, or self-fulfilling expectations, cannot be adequately interpreted through linear causality; rather, they require a new conceptual infrastructure capable of incorporating multiplicity⁷, indeterminacy⁸, and the dynamic feedback loops of reality⁹. Just as the observer in quantum physics actively influences the observed field, so too does the economic analyst or policy-maker shape the domain through their very assumptions.

Quantum Thought in Economic Theory

Uncertainty occupies an increasingly central position in contemporary economic thought – not merely as a statistical deviation or technical vagueness, but as a structural feature of the phenomena themselves. Already in the work of Frank Knight (1921), a clear distinction is drawn between risk, which can be probabilistically calculated, and uncertainty, which pertains to situations lacking known or quantifiable probabilities. Kay and King (2020) introduce the term radical uncertainty to describe a framework in which the unknown is indeterminate – not merely unknown – and thus not amenable to calculation or optimization through traditional models (Farmer & Foley, 2011; Spiegler, 2015).

This idea is closely linked to the dynamics of complexity and nonlinearity, which characterize economic reality to a far greater extent than neoclassical models typically assume. Agent-based models and chaos theory have demonstrated how even simple systems can give rise to unpredictable and unstable equilibria, where small changes in initial conditions lead to dramatically different outcomes (Arthur, 2021). Within this framework, prediction ceases to function as a form of control and is instead reframed as the management of complex interactions under conditions of uncertainty.

A critical element is also the concept of reflexivity, as introduced by George Soros (2013), according to which economic agents do not operate as neutral observers but, through their actions and expectations, actively influence the very evolution of the phenomena they seek to analyze. This relationship – where the model shapes the reality it is purported to describe – is analogous to the quantum principle of participatory observation, and it undermines the possibility of an external, objective interpretation.

Overall, the integration of quantum thought into economic theory does not consist in the mere transfer of concepts, but in a conceptual reconstruction of foundational assumptions: economic reality

is no longer regarded as fully representable or computable. In place of static equilibria and deterministic models, what is required is a framework that acknowledges the dynamic, reflexive, and at times unpredictable nature of economic systems (Maas, 2014; Lawson, 2015; Orrell & Chlupatý, 2016).

Quantum Information and Economic Practice

Quantum computing represents one of the most radical technological developments of recent decades. Its rapid advancement is not merely a technological innovation but an accelerator of a deeper epistemological and economic rupture. Quantum computers, based on the principles of superposition and entanglement, offer computational power exponentially superior to that of classical processors, enabling the processing of problems that are intractable by conventional means (Preskill, 2018). In the field of economics, this translates into radical optimization capabilities in problems such as portfolio selection, real-time arbitrage detection, as well as the excessive processing of data in high-liquidity environments (Egger et al., 2020).

At the same time, the concept of information in quantum theory acquires new characteristics. Information is no longer a copyable or stable entity, but a dynamic and indeterminate one. Measurement itself alters it, while the creation of perfect copies is prohibited (no-cloning theorem) (Wootters & Zurek, 1982). A characteristic example is the use of quantum cryptography in high-sensitivity banking systems, where the very act of reading alters the message and limits the predictability of the exchange.

At the economic level, all this implies a new interpretation of information as fluid, temporary, and dynamically dependent on context and observer. Consequently, economic action – such as forecasting, valuation, or risk management – ceases to rely on a fixed data framework and evolves into a participatory process of informational transformation.

Moreover, the technological transition toward quantum supremacy raises critical issues of unequal access and power. The possession or control of quantum computing infrastructures – currently held by a small number of governments and technological monopolies – already constitutes an emerging geoeconomic allocator of power (Krenn et al., 2023). This may directly affect how governments shape monetary or fiscal policy, or how banks detect asymmetries in capital markets. As contemporary analysis suggests, quantum technology is not a neutral tool but an embodied institutional implementation of strategies of influence, with consequences for security, transparency, and democracy in economic governance (Arute et al., 2019; Mohseni et al., 2022).

It thus becomes evident that quantum information and computation cannot be integrated into the economic framework as merely technical instruments. On the contrary, they constitute a new paradigm of power and epistemic condition, in which the manner by which information is produced, transmitted, and acquired reconfigures the very nature of economic action.

The rise of quantum computing must also be examined in the context of widening inequalities in access, expertise, and computational sovereignty. Just as with 'digital colonialism' (data colonialism), where the concentration of data and computational power by a few global actors produces new forms of dependency and invisibility (Coudry & Mejias, 2019), so too in the quantum era a 'quantum divide' is emerging. This divide is not only technological, but also performative and geopolitical: it concerns who has the capacity to control the infrastructure, to develop algorithms, and to construct economic conditions based on computational supremacy.

Quantum supremacy, both as a term and as a reality, risks becoming a mechanism of technological colonization (Morozov, 2020), with the states or corporations that possess it reframing

even the fundamental frameworks of concepts such as price, value, or market, based on opaque and unaccountable infrastructures. Therefore, the integration of quantum technology into the economy cannot be understood as a neutral advancement, but must be analyzed as a new paradigm of power, asymmetry, and dominance over the very notion of information and decision-making.

The above perspective belongs to a broader theoretical current that understands information and technology not as neutral entities, but as performative and embodied forms of knowledge and power. As Haraway (1988) has argued, all knowledge is locally embodied (*'situated'*) and produced within specific relational frameworks. Similarly, Mirowski (2002, 2011) has shown how the very concept of the market has been constructed through computational metaphors and technical rationality, while Stengers (2005) has emphasized the importance of 'ecologies of practices' that constitute scientific and technological becoming. From this standpoint, quantum computing and informatics do not merely impact economic activity; they reconstitute it, participating in the performative reconstruction of the very condition of the economic.

Towards a New Epistemological Paradigm

The crisis of the neoclassical paradigm in economic thought is not merely empirical – that is, a failure to predict crises or to model collective behavior – but profoundly epistemological. The model of Homo Economicus, of full information and predictability through equilibrium equations, fails to account for the complexity and entropy of modern markets (Colander et al., 2009). As became evident during the 2008 crisis and is continually reaffirmed by increasing instability, economic reality does not obey static, deterministic laws, but evolves dynamically and unpredictably (Aikman, Haldane, Nelson, 2015). A telling example is the collapse of mathematically framed certainty, offered by models such as Value at Risk (VaR), which contributed to the underestimation of systemic instability prior to the crisis.

In this context, a new epistemological perspective is required: knowledge in economics is neither universal nor neutral, but fragmented, situated, and interpretive (Flyvbjerg, 2001; Bronk, 2009). Observation and decision-making actively participate in shaping reality. Information is not a given to be utilized, but a participatory event under continuous negotiation. A characteristic example is price behavior on trading platforms, where the very act of forecasting market trends tends to either fulfill or negate itself, thereby altering the very field it seeks to influence. Rather than clinging to the illusion of control through fixed models, what is needed is the recognition of radical uncertainty as a condition not to be overcome, but to be integrated (Taleb, 2007; Callon, Lascoumes, Barthe, 2009).

The proposed methodological shift is from equilibrium and optimization models toward computational and evolutionary algorithms that incorporate dynamic information, behavioral asymmetries, and the multiple perspectives of agents (Farmer & Geanakoplos, 2009; Arthur, 2021). The integration of principles from complexity theory further supports this transition, suggesting that economic behavior should be analyzed as the emergent outcome of interacting agents within dynamic systems. Instead of closed models, the new economic thinking advocates for open, nonlinear frameworks that combine technological tools with socio-cognitive awareness. This represents a paradigm without an absolute observer – one that abandons the illusion of rational control and turns toward the participatory and uncertain construction of reality (Kahneman, 2011).

This epistemological opening does not negate the need for economic theory. Rather, it reimagines it, not as a tool for prediction, but as a framework for interpretation, situated action, and the management of uncertainty. Instead of the illusion of absolute predictability, it emphasizes the need to comprehend the dynamic and multi-perspective nature of reality, in line with the distinction between *'prediction'* and *'understanding'* highlighted in interpretive and human-centered approaches.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions summarize the need for a radical epistemological and methodological reconsideration of economic thought in light of quantum uncertainty, quantum computing, informational transformation, and technological power:

Uncertainty is a fundamental feature of reality. The shift from a Newtonian to a quantum mode of thought overturns the deterministic and predictable conception of the world. In economic theory, this implies that uncertainty is not a matter of technical insufficiency, but an inherent condition that renders complete prediction and control impossible. This condition is not limited to philosophical reflection, but has immediate implications for policymaking, as it challenges the feasibility of centralized control and static regulation in highly volatile environments.

Knowledge and observation are participatory processes. The observer is not external and neutral. On the contrary, they actively partake in the constitution of economic phenomena. Economic theory must abandon the claim to objectivity and incorporate the situated, interpretive, and interactive nature of knowledge.

Economic practice is dynamic, non-linear, and reflexive. Phenomena such as crises, bubbles, and expectations cannot be explained through static models. A new conceptual infrastructure is needed, one grounded in complexity, feedback, and interdependence. Reflexivity implies that economic agents do not merely respond to data, but actively transform the very context within which they operate, generating circular and unstable dynamics.

Quantum information redefines the notion of information and decision-making. Information is not a fixed, neutral datum, but mutable, non-copyable, and context-dependent – that is, shaped by the environment in which it is produced and interpreted. Decision-making under such conditions becomes participatory and non-computable in terms of traditional optimization logic.

Quantum technology constitutes a new form of power and asymmetry. Unequal access to computational capacity and infrastructure produces new geoeconomic and institutional inequalities. Technology is not neutral; it acts as a political and epistemic vector of domination.

A new epistemological paradigm is required in economics. Emerging economic thought abandons the illusion of predictability and promotes open, non-linear frameworks that integrate technological tools, socio-cognitive awareness, and radical uncertainty.

This new epistemological paradigm does not negate economic theory, but reorients it toward a regime that acknowledges the role of technology, uncertainty, and information as constitutive elements of economic reality. Within this framework, theory becomes not a mechanism of prediction, but a field of continuous interpretation and engagement.

DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The conceptual discussion presented in this study opens several avenues for further research.

- a) Empirical analysis of the performativity of information in highly liquid and volatile markets.
- b) Mapping the unequal distribution of quantum computing power and its geoeconomic implications.
- c) Development of multi-agent simulation models with limited, contextual, and non-replicable information.

- d) Study of the role of infrastructures and protocols as performative agents in economic practice.
- e) Comparative evaluation of classical and participatory methodologies in theoretical and applied economic research.
- f) Philosophical inquiry into uncertainty as the foundation of decision-making, with applications in monetary, technological, and environmental policy.

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¹ The term is used here metaphorically, referring to the deterministic, mechanistic, and predictable model of the universe as formulated by Newton, and is applied by analogy to economic thought.

² Quantum uncertainty refers to the impossibility of simultaneously and precisely determining key properties of a system, highlighting the fact that the very act of observation affects the phenomenon being observed. In economics, it describes the inherent and irreducible uncertainty that governs markets, where the act of prediction or observation itself influences the behavior of economic agents and shapes the very evolution of the phenomenon.

³ It refers to the gradual increase of disorder, complexity, and unpredictable behavior within economic systems as they evolve and interact.

⁴ The view that phenomena unfold in a predictable, linear, and deterministic manner, in accordance with universal laws governing a regulated system.

⁵ In a form of capitalism where information becomes raw material and algorithms shape, rather than merely analyze, economic reality, knowledge ceases to be an objective representation and becomes participatory, interpretive, and continuously in flux. Essentially, it is a system in which algorithms preemptively configure social and economic behavior.

⁶ The relevant formulation—“Practices of knowing are specific material engagements that participate in (re)configuring the world. Knowing is a matter of part of the world making itself intelligible to another part.” (Barad, 2007, p.336)—suggests that we do not come to know the world from a distance, but rather that we are entangled within it, actively participating in its configuration every time we observe, measure, or come to know.

⁷ A system may possess more than one stable state or outcome, which means that it does not necessarily converge to a single point of equilibrium.

⁸ Indeterminacy is not an indication of a lack of knowledge, but a fundamental feature of reality, one that necessitates a rethinking of the very notion of objective prediction.

⁹ A mechanism through which reality itself is shaped and evolves via continuous, active interactions with the perceptions, actions, and consequences of the agents within it.

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Business and Ethics

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ABSTRACT

Business ethics has become a central component of contemporary corporate governance and sustainable development. The present study explores the relationship between ethical principles and business performance, focusing on the challenges companies face in balancing profitability with social responsibility. The paper provides a conceptual analysis of major ethical approaches, including Kantian ethics and utilitarianism, and examines their applicability in modern business environments. The research adopts a theoretical and analytical approach, integrating established models and indicators such as Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) frameworks, sustainability indices, and corruption perception measures. Special attention is given to the role of business ethics indicators as tools for evaluating corporate behavior, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability. The findings suggest that while businesses are primarily profit-oriented entities, the integration of ethical frameworks contributes significantly to reputational stability, stakeholder trust, and sustainable growth. The study highlights that ethical practices are increasingly becoming a strategic necessity rather than a voluntary choice. The paper contributes to the existing literature by systematizing key indicators of business ethics and outlining their role in enhancing corporate performance and governance.

Keywords: *Business performance, Corporate social responsibility (CSR), ESG, Business ethics indicators, Ethical decision-making, Sustainability, Corruption perception index, Stakeholder theory*

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INTRODUCTION

In contemporary economic environments, the relationship between ethics and business has become increasingly complex and significant. Traditionally, business has been associated primarily with profit maximization, while ethics has been perceived as a normative framework governing human behavior. This apparent contradiction has led to ongoing debates regarding the compatibility of ethical principles with corporate objectives.

Early perspectives, influenced by classical economic liberalism, suggested that market mechanisms alone – often described through the concept of the “invisible hand” – are sufficient to ensure efficiency and fairness. However, modern economic realities, including globalization, environmental challenges, and increasing stakeholder awareness, have demonstrated that market forces alone are insufficient to regulate corporate behavior effectively. The emergence of stakeholder-oriented approaches has further emphasized that businesses are accountable not only to shareholders but also to a broader group of stakeholders, including employees, customers, and society at large (R. Edward Freeman, 1984).

The growing importance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has significantly transformed the way companies approach their role in society. According to the well-established CSR framework, businesses are expected to fulfill economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities simultaneously (Archie B. Carroll, 1991). In parallel, the integration of ethical considerations into business strategy has been recognized as a source of competitive advantage, particularly when aligned with social and environmental objectives (Michael E. Porter & Mark R. Kramer, 2006).

In recent years, the concept of sustainability has further expanded the scope of business ethics by linking ethical behavior to long-term corporate performance. Empirical studies have shown that companies adopting sustainable and ethically responsible practices tend to achieve better financial and operational outcomes over time (Robert G. Eccles et al., 2014). This has led to the increasing adoption of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria as key indicators for evaluating corporate behavior and investment decisions.

Despite the expansion of research in the field of business ethics, a key challenge remains: how to effectively measure and evaluate ethical behavior in business practices. While various models and indices have been developed, there is still a need for a more systematic understanding of business ethics indicators and their role in enhancing corporate performance and governance.

Research Aim

The present study aims to explore the theoretical foundations of business ethics, analyze its practical implications, and systematize key indicators used to evaluate ethical behavior in business organizations. Special attention is given to the relationship between ethical frameworks, corporate governance, and long-term sustainability. The main objective of this study is to examine the role of business ethics as a strategic component of modern corporate management and to propose a structured framework for analyzing business ethics indicators. The research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent can ethical principles be applied in profit-oriented organizations?
2. What are the key indicators used to evaluate business ethics?
3. How do these indicators influence corporate performance and sustainability?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of business ethics has been extensively examined in academic literature, particularly in relation to corporate social responsibility (CSR), stakeholder theory, and sustainable business practices. Over time, the understanding of ethical behavior in business has evolved from a normative perspective toward a more strategic and performance-oriented approach.

One of the foundational contributions to the field is the stakeholder theory, which emphasizes that businesses have responsibilities not only to shareholders but also to a broader range of stakeholders (R. Edward Freeman, 1984). This perspective has significantly influenced modern approaches to corporate governance and ethical decision-making.

Corporate social responsibility has also emerged as a central concept in the study of business ethics. The CSR framework developed by Archie B. Carroll (1991) outlines the multidimensional responsibilities of firms, including economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic aspects. More recent studies have expanded this framework by linking CSR practices to firm performance and competitive advantage. Recent studies have further emphasized the complexity of ethical challenges in contemporary management, highlighting the growing tension between economic objectives and moral responsibilities in organizational decision-making (Kicheva-Kirova, 2025). In addition, contemporary literature emphasizes that business ethics should be understood as an integral part of organizational strategy and decision-making processes rather than as a set of abstract principles (Boatright, 2011).

In this context, the integration of ethical considerations into business strategy has been further developed through the concept of shared value, which suggests that companies can create economic value while simultaneously addressing social issues (Michael E. Porter & Mark R. Kramer, 2006). This approach reflects a shift from reactive compliance to proactive strategic engagement with ethical challenges.

Recent empirical research has also focused on the relationship between sustainability practices and corporate performance. Studies indicate that firms adopting environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles tend to demonstrate improved financial stability and long-term value creation (Robert G. Eccles et al., 2014). These findings support the argument that ethical behavior is not only a moral obligation but also a strategic necessity.

Furthermore, contemporary research highlights the importance of measurable indicators in assessing business ethics. Various indices, such as sustainability indices and corruption perception indicators, have been developed to evaluate corporate behavior and institutional integrity. However, there is still a lack of a unified framework that integrates these indicators into a comprehensive model for analyzing business ethics.

Based on the reviewed literature, it can be concluded that business ethics has evolved into a multidimensional concept that combines ethical theory, corporate governance, and performance measurement. Nevertheless, the need for systematization of business ethics indicators remains an open research challenge, which this study aims to address.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BUSINESS ETHICS

The theoretical foundations of business ethics are rooted in classical ethical theories, primarily deontological ethics and consequentialism. These approaches provide different perspectives on how ethical behavior should be evaluated in business contexts.

Deontological ethics, most prominently associated with Immanuel Kant, is based on the principle that actions should be guided by universal moral rules and duties. According to this perspective, ethical behavior is determined not by outcomes but by the intention behind actions and their adherence to moral principles. In the context of business, this raises important questions regarding the compatibility of profit-oriented activities with universal ethical standards.

From a Kantian perspective, businesses may face challenges in aligning their primary objective of profit maximization with moral obligations that require impartiality and respect for all stakeholders. This has led to critical discussions in the literature regarding whether corporations, as legal entities, can genuinely act as moral agents or whether ethical responsibility ultimately lies with individuals within the organization. Furthermore, integrative approaches such as the social contracts theory suggest that ethical business behavior is shaped by both universal moral principles and local cultural norms, highlighting the complexity of ethical decision-making in global business environments (Donaldson & Dunfee, 1999).

In contrast, consequentialism, particularly in its utilitarian form, evaluates actions based on their outcomes. Philosophers such as Jeremy Bentham and John Stuart Mill argued that actions are considered ethical if they produce the greatest good for the greatest number of people. In business practice, this approach is often reflected in decisions that aim to maximize overall benefits for stakeholders, even if certain compromises are required.

However, the utilitarian approach has also been criticized for potentially justifying unethical means if they lead to desirable outcomes. In business environments, this may result in practices that prioritize short-term gains over long-term ethical considerations.

In addition, structured analytical tools such as SWOT analysis have been identified as effective instruments for supporting strategic and ethically informed decision-making by systematically evaluating internal and external business factors (Karadzhov, 2025).

Another influential perspective is associated with economic liberalism, particularly the views of Milton Friedman, who argued that the primary responsibility of business is to increase profits within the boundaries of the law. According to this view, ethical considerations are secondary to economic objectives, provided that companies comply with legal requirements.

Despite these theoretical differences, contemporary business environments increasingly require the integration of ethical principles into corporate decision-making. Modern approaches combine elements from different ethical theories, emphasizing the importance of accountability, transparency, and stakeholder engagement. This shift reflects the growing recognition that ethical behavior is essential for maintaining trust, legitimacy, and long-term sustainability in business operations.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative and conceptual research approach aimed at analyzing the role of business ethics in contemporary corporate environments. The research is based on the systematic review and synthesis of existing theoretical frameworks, academic literature, and international practices related to business ethics, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and sustainability.

The methodological approach combines elements of theoretical analysis and comparative evaluation. Classical ethical theories, including deontological ethics and consequentialism, are examined alongside modern concepts such as stakeholder theory and ESG frameworks. This allows for a comprehensive understanding of the evolution of business ethics from normative principles to strategic management tools.

In addition, the study applies a comparative analysis of key business ethics indicators. These include sustainability indices, corporate social responsibility metrics, and corruption-related indicators used in international practice. The analysis is based on secondary data derived from academic publications, institutional reports, and globally recognized measurement frameworks. Furthermore, a

conceptual framework is developed to systematize business ethics indicators into distinct categories. This framework aims to provide a structured approach for evaluating ethical behavior in business organizations and to identify the relationships between ethical practices, corporate governance, and long-term sustainability.

The application of comprehensive analytical frameworks such as PESTEL analysis further enhances the evaluation of external environmental factors influencing ethical business behavior and strategic decision-making (Karadzhov & Patarchanova, 2025).

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of the study are related to its conceptual nature and reliance on secondary data. Future research may expand the analysis by incorporating empirical data and quantitative methods to validate the proposed framework.

Despite these limitations, the conceptual approach provides valuable insights into the role of business ethics indicators and contributes to the development of a more integrated analytical perspective in the field.

BUSINESS ETHICS INDICATORS AND MEASUREMENT FRAMEWORK

The evaluation of business ethics has increasingly relied on the development and application of measurable indicators. In contemporary business environments, ethical behavior is no longer assessed solely through normative judgments but is supported by structured frameworks and performance metrics.

Business ethics indicators serve as tools for assessing corporate behavior, governance quality, and social responsibility. These indicators are typically integrated into broader analytical models that combine financial, social, and environmental dimensions of performance.

One of the widely recognized approaches is the use of sustainability indices, such as the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI), which evaluates companies based on economic, environmental, and social criteria. These indices are grounded in the concept of the “triple bottom line,” which emphasizes the balanced consideration of profit, people, and the planet. Companies that perform well across these dimensions are considered more sustainable and ethically responsible.

Similarly, the FTSE4Good Index provides a framework for assessing companies based on their adherence to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards. It excludes industries associated with significant ethical concerns, such as tobacco production and weapons manufacturing, and evaluates firms based on criteria related to human rights, environmental impact, and anti-corruption practices. International institutional frameworks, such as those developed by the OECD, also play a key role in defining standards for corporate governance, transparency, and ethical conduct in business practices (OECD, 2015).

In addition to sustainability indices, corruption-related indicators play a significant role in the assessment of business ethics. The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), developed by Transparency International, measures perceived levels of public sector corruption and provides a comparative perspective across countries. High levels of corruption are associated with increased business risks, reduced investment attractiveness, and weakened institutional trust.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) metrics also contribute to the evaluation of business ethics. These metrics assess the extent to which companies engage in socially responsible activities,

including environmental protection, employee welfare, and community development. CSR reporting has become a standard practice for many organizations, enhancing transparency and accountability.

Furthermore, internal governance indicators are essential for understanding ethical behavior within organizations. These include compliance systems, ethical codes, internal audit mechanisms, and performance evaluation tools. Effective corporate governance structures contribute to the prevention of unethical practices and support long-term organizational sustainability.

Proposed Framework for Business Ethics Evaluation

Based on the analysis of existing models and indicators, this study proposes a structured framework for evaluating business ethics, consisting of three main dimensions:

Internal Ethical Governance

This dimension includes internal organizational mechanisms that regulate ethical behavior, such as corporate governance structures, codes of ethics, compliance systems, and employee-related practices. These elements ensure that ethical principles are embedded within the organization's operational processes.

External Social Responsibility and Sustainability

This dimension focuses on the organization's impact on society and the environment. It includes CSR initiatives, environmental management practices, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability strategies. Companies that actively address social and environmental challenges are more likely to build trust and long-term value.

Institutional and Market Integrity

This dimension reflects the external environment in which the company operates, including regulatory compliance, exposure to corruption, and transparency standards. Indicators such as the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) and ESG ratings are relevant in this context, as they provide insights into the broader ethical ecosystem.

These three dimensions are interconnected and collectively determine the ethical profile of a business organization. The proposed framework contributes to the systematization of business ethics indicators and provides a practical tool for analyzing corporate behavior in a comprehensive and structured manner.

As illustrated in Figure 1, business ethics can be conceptualized as a multidimensional construct composed of three interrelated dimensions: internal ethical governance, external social responsibility and sustainability, and institutional and market integrity. Each of these dimensions encompasses a set of specific components that collectively define the ethical profile and long-term performance of business organizations.

The first dimension, **internal ethical governance**, refers to the internal structures and mechanisms that regulate ethical behavior within the organization. It includes corporate governance systems, clearly defined codes of ethics, compliance procedures, internal audit practices, and human resource policies aimed at promoting fairness, accountability, and transparency. These elements ensure that ethical principles are embedded in daily operations and decision-making processes, reducing the likelihood of unethical behavior and enhancing organizational integrity.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework for Evaluating Business Ethics through Governance, Sustainability, and Market Integrity Dimensions

The second dimension, **external social responsibility and sustainability**, reflects the organization’s broader impact on society and the natural environment. It includes corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives, environmental management practices, stakeholder engagement strategies, and long-term sustainability policies. Within this dimension, companies are evaluated based on their ability to balance economic objectives with social and environmental considerations, thereby contributing to sustainable development and strengthening their legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders.

The third dimension, **institutional and market integrity**, captures the external conditions that influence ethical business conduct. It encompasses regulatory compliance, transparency standards, exposure to corruption, and alignment with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria. Indicators such as the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) and ESG ratings are particularly relevant in this context, as they provide measurable insights into the ethical environment in which companies operate and their ability to maintain trust in competitive markets.

These three dimensions are not independent but dynamically interconnected. Strong internal governance supports responsible external behavior, while transparent and well-regulated market environments reinforce ethical decision-making within organizations. As a result, business ethics should be understood not as a static set of principles, but as an integrated system of practices, indicators, and institutional conditions that collectively shape corporate behavior and sustainability.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirm that business ethics has evolved from a purely normative concept into a strategic component of modern corporate management. The analysis of theoretical frameworks and business ethics indicators demonstrates that ethical behavior is increasingly

embedded in organizational structures and performance evaluation systems, rather than being treated as an external or optional consideration.

The integration of stakeholder-oriented approaches (R. Edward Freeman, 1984) and corporate social responsibility models (Archie B. Carroll, 1991) highlights a shift from shareholder-centric to stakeholder-inclusive business practices. This transformation is further reinforced by the concept of shared value (Michael E. Porter & Mark R. Kramer, 2006), which positions ethical engagement as a driver of competitive advantage rather than a constraint on profitability.

The results also support the growing body of empirical evidence suggesting that sustainability and ethical practices contribute positively to corporate performance. As indicated by Robert G. Eccles et al. (2014), companies that integrate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles into their strategies tend to achieve greater financial stability and long-term value creation. This finding aligns with the argument that ethical behavior is increasingly becoming a strategic necessity in contemporary business environments.

A key contribution of this study lies in the systematization of business ethics indicators into a structured framework consisting of three interrelated dimensions: internal ethical governance, external social responsibility and sustainability, and institutional and market integrity. This framework provides a more comprehensive perspective on how ethical behavior can be evaluated and managed within organizations. Unlike fragmented approaches that focus on isolated indicators, the proposed model emphasizes the interconnected nature of ethical practices and their cumulative impact on organizational performance.

An additional important aspect of the proposed framework is its potential applicability across different industries and institutional contexts. While the relative importance of specific indicators may vary depending on sectoral characteristics and regulatory environments, the three-dimensional structure of internal governance, external responsibility, and institutional integrity provides a flexible and adaptable model. This enhances the practical relevance of the framework and supports its use as a tool for comparative analysis and strategic evaluation in diverse business settings.

This trend is also supported by recent research on digitalization and innovation, which demonstrates that the integration of technology and sustainability considerations further strengthens the role of ethical decision-making in contemporary business environments (Lile et al., 2025).

At the same time, the analysis reveals several challenges associated with the implementation and measurement of business ethics. One of the main difficulties lies in the potential gap between formal compliance and actual ethical behavior. Organizations may adopt codes of ethics and CSR policies without fully integrating them into their operational culture. Additionally, the reliance on external indicators, such as ESG ratings and corruption indices, may not always accurately reflect internal ethical practices.

From a practical perspective, the findings suggest that businesses should move beyond symbolic adoption of ethical standards and focus on their effective implementation. This includes strengthening internal governance mechanisms, enhancing transparency, and actively engaging with stakeholders. For policymakers and institutions, the results underline the importance of creating regulatory environments that promote accountability and reduce opportunities for unethical behavior.

Finally, the study highlights the need for further research in the field of business ethics, particularly in relation to empirical validation of conceptual models and the development of more precise measurement tools. Future studies may explore the application of quantitative methods and

case-based analyses to assess the effectiveness of business ethics frameworks in different economic and cultural contexts.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study have several important implications for business practitioners and organizational leaders. First, companies should integrate ethical considerations directly into their strategic planning processes rather than treating them as separate or secondary activities. This includes the development of internal governance mechanisms such as clear codes of ethics, compliance systems, and performance evaluation criteria that incorporate ethical indicators.

Second, organizations should adopt a proactive approach to corporate social responsibility and sustainability. Instead of focusing solely on regulatory compliance, businesses should actively engage with stakeholders and invest in long-term social and environmental initiatives that enhance corporate reputation and trust.

Third, the use of structured analytical tools and measurable indicators, including ESG metrics and sustainability indices, can support more informed decision-making and improve transparency. Managers should utilize these tools not only for reporting purposes but also as part of internal strategic analysis.

Finally, companies operating in environments with higher levels of institutional risk should place greater emphasis on transparency, anti-corruption measures, and accountability. Strengthening these aspects can significantly reduce operational risks and improve long-term business performance.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the role of business ethics as a fundamental component of contemporary corporate governance and sustainable development. The analysis demonstrated that ethical principles are no longer perceived solely as normative guidelines but have evolved into strategic instruments that influence business performance, stakeholder relationships, and long-term organizational success.

The findings confirm that the integration of ethical frameworks, including corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria, contributes to enhanced transparency, reduced reputational risks, and improved competitiveness. In this context, business ethics should be understood as a necessary condition for sustainable growth rather than a voluntary or supplementary practice.

A key contribution of the study is the proposed framework for evaluating business ethics, which organizes relevant indicators into three interconnected dimensions: internal ethical governance, external social responsibility and sustainability, and institutional and market integrity. This framework provides a structured approach for analyzing ethical behavior and offers practical value for both researchers and practitioners.

At the same time, the study acknowledges that the effective implementation of ethical principles remains a significant challenge. The gap between formal adoption of ethical standards and their practical application continues to be a critical issue for many organizations. Therefore, future efforts should focus on strengthening the alignment between ethical policies and organizational culture.

Future research may further develop the proposed framework through empirical validation, comparative studies across industries, and the integration of quantitative measurement techniques.

Such efforts would contribute to a deeper understanding of how business ethics can be effectively operationalized in diverse economic and institutional contexts.

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Agri-Environmental Policy and Rural Development in Bulgaria

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ABSTRACT

This article examines key aspects of agri-environmental policy and sustainable rural development in Bulgaria within the framework of the Strategic Plan for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas 2023–2027 (CAP 2023–2027). The analysis focuses on major interventions related to agri-environmental measures, organic farming, biodiversity conservation, and eco-schemes. Particular attention is given to recent policy developments, including expanded support mechanisms, revised eligibility criteria, and improved administrative procedures aimed at facilitating farmer participation. The article highlights the importance of sustainable land management practices, preservation of local plant varieties and animal breeds, and the enhancement of ecosystem services such as pollination and soil fertility. At the same time, key challenges are identified, including administrative complexity, uneven participation across regions, and the need for stronger institutional coordination. The findings suggest that agri-environmental policy plays a crucial role in shaping the future of rural areas in Bulgaria, not only as a tool for environmental protection but also as a driver of economic resilience and regional development. The study contributes to the existing literature by integrating agri-environmental policy analysis with sustainability transition theory and the ecosystem services framework, offering a multidimensional perspective on rural development. It further advances the understanding of CAP implementation in Eastern European contexts by highlighting the interaction between institutional capacity, environmental objectives, and technological transformation.

Keywords: Agri-environmental policy; Rural development; Sustainability; Eco-schemes; Organic farming; Biodiversity; CAP 2023–2027; Bulgaria

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INTRODUCTION

Rural areas in Bulgaria play a fundamental role in the national economy, particularly as primary producers of agricultural goods and raw materials. Despite ongoing processes of economic diversification, these regions remain highly dependent on agriculture and natural resources. In recent years, climate change, environmental degradation, and demographic decline have introduced new challenges that require adaptive and sustainable development strategies.

The European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027 provides a comprehensive framework for addressing these challenges through targeted interventions in agri-environmental management, climate adaptation, and biodiversity conservation. Bulgaria's Strategic Plan for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas (2023–2027) represents a key instrument for implementing these priorities at the national level.

This article aims to analyze the main aspects of agri-environmental policy and their implications for sustainable rural development in Bulgaria. The focus is placed on key measures such as organic farming, conservation of local genetic resources, and eco-schemes designed to improve environmental performance in agriculture. In addition, the article explores the challenges associated with policy implementation and the effectiveness of current support mechanisms.

POLICY FRAMEWORK FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN BULGARIA

The Strategic Plan for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas (2023–2027) represents the main policy instrument for implementing the objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in Bulgaria. It builds upon previous programming periods, particularly the Rural Development Programme 2014–2020, while introducing new priorities aligned with the European Green Deal, climate neutrality targets, and sustainable resource management.

A central component of the policy framework is the implementation of agri-environmental and climate measures aimed at promoting sustainable land use and reducing environmental pressures. These measures provide compensatory payments to farmers who voluntarily adopt environmentally friendly practices, such as maintaining high nature value grasslands, preserving endangered local breeds, and applying soil conservation techniques.

In addition to these measures, the policy places strong emphasis on the development of organic farming, which includes plant production, livestock breeding, and beekeeping. The updated framework introduces more flexible conditions for extending existing commitments, revised payment levels, and reduced administrative burdens, thereby encouraging broader participation among agricultural producers.

Eco-schemes represent another key instrument within the CAP 2023–2027, providing financial incentives for practices that contribute to climate mitigation and environmental sustainability. These include actions related to reducing pesticide use, improving soil health, increasing carbon sequestration, and enhancing biodiversity. Their introduction marks a shift toward more result-oriented agricultural policy, linking financial support to measurable environmental outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of agri-environmental policy and sustainable rural development has been widely examined in the academic literature, particularly in the context of the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Previous studies emphasize the growing importance of

integrating environmental objectives into agricultural policy frameworks, highlighting the transition from production-oriented models toward sustainability-driven approaches.

Research has shown that agri-environmental measures play a key role in promoting biodiversity conservation, sustainable land use, and climate change mitigation (European Commission, 2021). These measures are particularly relevant in regions characterized by high nature value farming systems, where traditional agricultural practices contribute significantly to ecosystem preservation.

In the Bulgarian context, rural development has been strongly influenced by structural economic factors, demographic trends, and regional disparities. Earlier studies have emphasized the importance of access to financing, administrative efficiency, and institutional capacity in shaping rural development outcomes (Karadzhov, 2015). These factors remain relevant in the current policy framework, particularly in relation to the implementation of agri-environmental measures. Recent geographical studies also emphasize the importance of spatial characteristics and regional disparities in shaping development processes in Bulgaria. In this context, Patarchanov (2023) highlights the role of territorial structure, cross-border dynamics, and local economic conditions as key factors influencing regional development patterns.

At the same time, several authors have pointed out the challenges associated with the implementation of such policies, including administrative complexity, limited farmer participation, and insufficient institutional coordination. In this regard, recent analyses highlight the need for policy instruments that simultaneously address economic viability and environmental sustainability in rural areas (Pandurski, 2024).

Recent research also emphasizes the importance of applying structured strategic frameworks in the evaluation of rural development policies. In this context, SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) offers a comprehensive tool for assessing both internal capacities and external environmental conditions affecting policy performance. By identifying strengths and opportunities alongside existing limitations and risks, SWOT-based approaches support more informed decision-making and contribute to the development of more effective and adaptive rural policies (Karadzhov, 2025).

Furthermore, broader discussions on sustainability and environmental impact in related fields, such as tourism and regional development, underline the importance of balancing economic growth with ecological preservation. These insights are directly applicable to agri-environmental policy, where similar trade-offs between economic and environmental objectives are observed. In addition, research in related sectors such as tourism highlights the importance of adapting economic activities to changing global trends and sustainability requirements. In this regard, Kirov (2019) emphasizes the evolving characteristics of modern consumers and the need for more flexible and sustainable development models, which are also relevant in the context of rural and agri-environmental policy.

Overall, the literature suggests that while agri-environmental policy has significant potential to contribute to sustainable rural development, its effectiveness depends on the successful integration of multiple policy dimensions, institutional capacity, and the adaptability of implementation mechanisms at the regional level. Recent international research further emphasizes the increasing importance of performance-based agricultural policies and ecosystem service valuation within the CAP framework. Studies indicate that the transition toward eco-schemes and result-oriented payments enhances environmental outcomes but requires robust monitoring systems and farmer engagement (Pe'er et al., 2020; European Environment Agency, 2023).

In addition, the concept of ecosystem services has become central to evaluating the effectiveness of agri-environmental measures, particularly in relation to soil health, water regulation, and biodiversity conservation (Power, 2010). This perspective shifts the focus from purely agricultural productivity toward multifunctional land use systems.

Furthermore, digitalization and precision agriculture are increasingly recognized as key enablers of sustainable rural development. Technologies such as satellite monitoring, GIS-based land management, and smart farming tools support more efficient resource use and improve compliance with environmental standards (Wolfert et al., 2017). These developments are particularly relevant for countries like Bulgaria, where structural challenges require innovative and adaptive policy approaches.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This article adopts a qualitative research design based on policy analysis of agri-environmental measures and rural development strategies in Bulgaria within the framework of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027. The study applies a descriptive and analytical approach, focusing on the evaluation of policy documents, strategic frameworks, and regulatory instruments relevant to sustainable rural development.

The primary sources of information include official documents such as the Strategic Plan for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas (2023–2027), reports of the European Commission, and national policy guidelines. These sources are complemented by secondary data derived from academic publications and previous research studies in the fields of rural development, environmental policy, and regional analysis.

The methodological framework is based on document analysis and comparative evaluation of policy instruments, allowing for the identification of key interventions, structural challenges, and implementation gaps. In addition, elements of strategic analysis are applied to assess the effectiveness of policy measures and their contribution to sustainable rural development.

The approach enables a systematic interpretation of the interactions between environmental objectives, economic factors, and institutional conditions. Particular attention is given to the role of policy instruments in promoting sustainable land use, biodiversity conservation, and climate adaptation.

It should be noted that the study is limited by its reliance on secondary data and policy documents, without the inclusion of primary empirical data or quantitative modeling. Nevertheless, the analytical framework provides a comprehensive overview of the current policy environment and its implications for rural development in Bulgaria.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: PESTEL-BASED MODEL OF AGRICULTURAL ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

To better understand the complexity of agri-environmental policy and its impact on sustainable rural development, this study proposes a conceptual framework based on the PESTEL model (see Figure 1). This approach enables a structured analysis of the external factors influencing policy design, implementation, and outcomes.

From a political perspective, agri-environmental policy is shaped by the strategic priorities of the European Union, including the European Green Deal and CAP 2023–2027. These policies define the regulatory and financial framework within which national strategies operate.

Economic factors relate to the financial viability of agricultural practices, availability of subsidies, market access, and income stability of farmers. Agri-environmental measures must balance environmental objectives with economic sustainability to ensure long-term participation.

Social dimensions include demographic trends, rural depopulation, education levels, and the willingness of farmers to adopt sustainable practices. Social acceptance and awareness are critical for the successful implementation of policy measures.

Technological factors are increasingly important, particularly in the context of digital agriculture, precision farming, and data-driven monitoring systems. These technologies enhance efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and support compliance with policy requirements.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the interaction between political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal dimensions forms a dynamic system that shapes both policy effectiveness and rural development outcomes.

Figure 1. PESTEL Framework of Agri-Environmental Policy in Bulgaria.

Environmental factors represent the core focus of agri-environmental policy, including biodiversity conservation, soil health, water management, and climate change mitigation. These elements define the ultimate objectives of sustainability-oriented interventions.

Legal factors encompass the regulatory framework governing agricultural practices, environmental standards, and compliance mechanisms. Clear and accessible legal requirements are essential for reducing administrative burdens and improving policy effectiveness.

The interaction between these six dimensions highlights the complexity of agri-environmental policy and underscores the need for integrated and adaptive approaches to rural development.

KEY INTERVENTIONS AND MEASURES FOR SUSTAINABLE RURAL DEVELOPMENT

The implementation of agri-environmental policy in Bulgaria is operationalized through a set of targeted interventions that address both environmental protection and rural economic development. These interventions are designed to support sustainable agricultural practices while ensuring the long-term viability of rural communities.

One of the primary interventions focuses on agri-environmental and climate commitments, which aim to preserve biodiversity and maintain ecosystems with high natural value. These include measures for the protection of traditional agricultural landscapes, conservation of rare plant varieties, and support for local animal breeds. Such initiatives contribute not only to environmental sustainability but also to the preservation of cultural and agricultural heritage.

Another important area is the promotion of organic farming, which has gained increasing attention as a sustainable alternative to conventional agricultural practices. Support mechanisms are provided for both conversion to organic farming and maintenance of existing organic production systems. These measures cover a wide range of activities, including crop production, livestock farming, and beekeeping, thus reflecting the multifunctional nature of rural economies.

Special attention is also given to the conservation of genetic resources in agriculture. This includes targeted support for endangered local breeds and plant varieties, which are essential for maintaining biodiversity and ensuring resilience in the face of climate change. The preservation of these resources is closely linked to sustainable land management practices and the protection of ecosystem services.

Furthermore, eco-schemes play a crucial role in encouraging environmentally friendly farming practices. These schemes promote reduced use of chemical inputs, improved soil management, and increased biodiversity on agricultural land. By linking financial incentives to environmental performance, eco-schemes contribute to a more sustainable and resilient agricultural sector.

The overall effectiveness of these interventions depends on their accessibility, administrative feasibility, and alignment with the needs of local farmers. In this context, previous research has emphasized the importance of integrating environmental and economic objectives in rural development policies, as well as the need for adaptive management approaches that respond to regional specificities.

RESULTS

The results of the analysis indicate that agri-environmental policy in Bulgaria under the CAP 2023–2027 is structured around a comprehensive set of measures aimed at promoting sustainable agricultural practices and environmental protection. Key interventions include agri-environmental and climate commitments, support for organic farming, conservation of genetic resources, and the implementation of eco-schemes.

The findings show that these policy instruments contribute to the preservation of biodiversity, improvement of soil quality, and enhancement of ecosystem services. At the same time, they support

the economic sustainability of rural areas by providing financial incentives for environmentally friendly practices.

However, the results also reveal significant challenges related to policy implementation, including administrative complexity, uneven regional participation, and limited access to advisory support. These factors influence the overall effectiveness of the policy framework and highlight the need for further improvements in institutional coordination and policy design.

The results also suggest that the integration of digital tools and precision agriculture practices can enhance the effectiveness of agri-environmental measures by improving monitoring, compliance, and resource efficiency. However, their adoption remains uneven and dependent on regional capacities and access to technological infrastructure.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF AGRI-ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Despite the significant progress in the development of agri-environmental policy frameworks, several challenges continue to limit the effectiveness of their implementation in Bulgaria. These challenges are both structural and administrative in nature and reflect broader issues related to rural development and governance.

One of the primary challenges is the administrative complexity associated with participation in agri-environmental measures and eco-schemes. Farmers are often required to comply with detailed regulatory requirements, which may discourage participation, particularly among small and medium-sized agricultural producers. The complexity of application procedures, reporting obligations, and monitoring mechanisms creates barriers that reduce the overall accessibility of these policy instruments.

Another important limitation is the uneven territorial distribution of participation. Certain regions demonstrate higher levels of engagement in agri-environmental schemes, while others remain underrepresented. This disparity is influenced by differences in institutional capacity, availability of information, and local economic conditions. As a result, the intended environmental and socio-economic benefits of the policy are not evenly distributed across rural areas.

In addition, limited awareness and insufficient advisory support further constrain the effectiveness of policy measures. Many farmers lack adequate access to information regarding available funding opportunities, eligibility criteria, and long-term benefits of sustainable agricultural practices. This highlights the need for improved communication strategies and stronger extension services.

From an environmental perspective, the effectiveness of certain measures remains difficult to assess due to the lack of consistent monitoring and evaluation systems. While eco-schemes and agri-environmental commitments are designed to produce measurable outcomes, the absence of standardized indicators and reliable data limits the ability to evaluate their real impact on biodiversity, soil quality, and ecosystem services.

These challenges are consistent with broader findings in the literature, which emphasize the need for integrated and adaptive policy approaches in rural development (Yuleva-Chuchulayna & Karadzhov, 2025). In addition, previous studies have highlighted the importance of balancing environmental objectives with economic sustainability, particularly in regions where agriculture remains the primary source of income.

Overall, addressing these limitations requires a combination of administrative simplification, improved institutional coordination, enhanced advisory support, and the development of more effective monitoring frameworks. Without such improvements, the long-term impact of agri-environmental policy on sustainable rural development may remain limited.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight that agri-environmental policy in Bulgaria, within the framework of the CAP 2023–2027, is increasingly aligned with the broader paradigm of sustainable development and the European Green Deal. This transition reflects a shift from productivist agricultural models toward multifunctional and sustainability-oriented approaches, where environmental performance, climate resilience, and ecosystem services play a central role.

From a theoretical perspective, the results can be interpreted through the lens of sustainability transition theory, which emphasizes the transformation of socio-technical systems toward more sustainable configurations. In this context, agri-environmental measures and eco-schemes function as policy instruments that aim to reconfigure agricultural practices by incentivizing environmentally responsible behavior. However, the effectiveness of these instruments depends not only on their design but also on the institutional, economic, and social contexts in which they are implemented.

The study also confirms the relevance of the ecosystem services framework in understanding the role of agriculture in rural development. Agricultural systems in Bulgaria, particularly those characterized by high nature value, provide essential services such as biodiversity conservation, soil fertility, and landscape maintenance. The incorporation of these services into policy design represents a significant advancement in aligning agricultural policy with environmental sustainability objectives.

At the same time, the results reveal a persistent gap between policy formulation and implementation. Despite the availability of financial incentives and structured interventions, barriers such as administrative complexity, limited advisory support, and uneven regional participation constrain policy effectiveness. This finding is consistent with broader research indicating that governance capacity and institutional coordination are critical determinants of successful policy outcomes.

Furthermore, the analysis underscores the importance of integrating digitalization into agri-environmental policy frameworks. Precision agriculture, remote sensing technologies, and data-driven monitoring systems have the potential to enhance both the efficiency and accountability of policy implementation. However, the uneven distribution of digital infrastructure and skills may exacerbate regional disparities, suggesting the need for targeted policy interventions that support digital inclusion.

From a policy analysis perspective, the findings support the application of integrated frameworks, such as PESTEL or systems-based approaches, in evaluating rural development strategies. Agri-environmental policy operates within a complex environment shaped by political priorities, economic conditions, social dynamics, technological developments, environmental constraints, and legal regulations. A holistic understanding of these interdependencies is essential for designing adaptive and resilient policy instruments.

Overall, the discussion suggests that while the CAP 2023–2027 provides a robust strategic framework for sustainable rural development, its success in the Bulgarian context depends on the

effective integration of environmental objectives with socio-economic realities, institutional capacity, and technological innovation.

The theoretical contribution of this study lies in the integration of agri-environmental policy analysis with sustainability transition theory and the ecosystem services framework, providing a multidimensional interpretation of rural development processes. By conceptualizing agri-environmental policy as part of a broader socio-technical system, the study extends existing research on CAP implementation, particularly in the context of Eastern European countries. In addition, it highlights the role of institutional capacity and digital transformation as critical mediating factors between policy design and environmental outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the key aspects of agri-environmental policy and sustainable rural development in Bulgaria within the framework of the CAP 2023–2027. The analysis demonstrates that contemporary policy instruments, including agri-environmental measures, eco-schemes, and support for organic farming, represent a significant step toward integrating environmental sustainability into agricultural policy.

The findings confirm that agri-environmental policy plays a dual role: it contributes to environmental protection through biodiversity conservation, soil management, and climate mitigation, while simultaneously supporting the economic resilience of rural areas. This dual function highlights the growing importance of agriculture as a multifunctional sector that extends beyond food production to include ecosystem services and regional development.

However, the study also identifies critical challenges that limit the overall effectiveness of policy implementation. Administrative complexity, uneven regional participation, insufficient advisory support, and limited monitoring capacity continue to hinder the full realization of policy objectives. These challenges indicate that the success of agri-environmental policy depends not only on financial support mechanisms but also on governance quality, institutional coordination, and stakeholder engagement.

From a theoretical standpoint, the study contributes to the literature by linking agri-environmental policy with broader conceptual frameworks, including sustainability transitions, ecosystem services, and integrated policy analysis. This approach provides a more comprehensive understanding of rural development processes and highlights the need for multidimensional evaluation models.

In practical terms, the results suggest several policy implications. First, there is a need for simplification of administrative procedures and improved accessibility of policy instruments, particularly for small and medium-sized farmers. Second, strengthening advisory services and knowledge transfer mechanisms is essential for increasing farmer participation and improving environmental outcomes. Third, the integration of digital technologies should be prioritized as a key driver of efficiency, transparency, and sustainability in agricultural systems.

Future research should focus on the empirical evaluation of agri-environmental measures using quantitative indicators and spatial analysis, as well as on comparative studies across regions and EU member states. In addition, further investigation is needed into the role of digital transformation and innovation in enhancing the effectiveness of rural development policies.

In conclusion, while the CAP 2023–2027 provides a comprehensive framework for sustainable rural development, its long-term success in Bulgaria will depend on the ability to integrate environmental, economic, technological, and institutional dimensions into a coherent and adaptive policy system.

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Infrastructure as a Key Determinant of Rural Development in Petrich Municipality (Bulgaria)

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ABSTRACT

This study examines infrastructure as a key determinant of socio-economic development in rural areas within Petrich Municipality (Bulgaria), in the context of the Integrated Development Plan (2021–2027). The analysis is based on official strategic and statistical data, focusing on transport, water supply and sewerage, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure. The findings demonstrate that infrastructure provision is directly linked to quality of life, accessibility of services, economic activity, and demographic dynamics in rural areas. Insufficient or deteriorated infrastructure contributes to depopulation, economic stagnation, and limited investment potential, while targeted infrastructure investments support economic diversification, including agriculture, tourism, and small enterprises. The study identifies significant territorial disparities between the municipal center and rural settlements, particularly in terms of accessibility, connectivity, and technical condition of infrastructure networks. The results highlight the need for an integrated policy approach combining infrastructural, social, and economic measures. It is concluded that infrastructure represents a strategic instrument for achieving sustainable and balanced rural development and for enhancing the competitiveness of rural areas at both regional and national levels.

Keywords: Rural infrastructure, Socio-economic development, Rural areas, Petrich Municipality, Territorial development

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INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure occupies a key place in the theories and practices of regional and territorial development, as it forms the material, functional, and institutional basis for economic activity, social integration, and spatial cohesion. The quality, accessibility, and even territorial distribution of infrastructure networks are among the leading factors determining the competitiveness and sustainable development of regions.

In conditions of deepening territorial imbalances, especially between urban and rural areas, the importance of infrastructure provision increases significantly. Rural areas in Bulgaria face a complex set of long-term structural problems, including persistent demographic depopulation, population ageing, limited access to basic public services, and weak economic diversification.

These processes lead to worsening of the quality of life and deepening of the socio-economic differences within the framework of the national space. In this context, infrastructure should not be considered solely as a supporting element of territorial development, but as an active instrument capable of stimulating or hindering the development of a given territory. The insufficient or unevenly developed transport, social and digital infrastructure limits the mobility of the population, deepens social isolation and hinders economic activity, especially in the peripheral and sparsely populated areas.

Petrich Municipality represents a particularly suitable object for study of these processes, as it combines a strategic geographical location in the southwestern part of the country, relatively good connectivity along main national and cross-border transport corridors, and a significant number of rural settlements with different degree of infrastructural and socio-economic development. This creates an opportunity for analysis of the intra-municipal territorial differences and for assessment of the role of infrastructure as a key factor for the sustainable development of the rural areas.

The methodological framework of the study includes an analysis of strategic documents and official statistical data sources. The results of the conducted research show that underdeveloped infrastructure emerges as one of the main factors determining the processes of depopulation in rural areas. At the same time, targeted investments and improved transport and communication connectivity create preconditions for sustainable development and for the socio-economic revitalization of rural communities.

Recent studies further emphasize that infrastructure should be understood not only as a physical system but also as a multidimensional driver of regional competitiveness and resilience. According to Karadzhov and Kirilov (2023), contemporary development models increasingly integrate infrastructure with environmental sustainability and digital transformation, highlighting its role in shaping long-term territorial dynamics. Similarly, European policy frameworks stress the importance of integrated infrastructure planning as a prerequisite for balanced regional development and cohesion (European Commission, 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of rural areas and the impact of infrastructure on them have been widely examined in international and Bulgarian academic literature.

Transport Infrastructure:

According to World Bank (2009), transport networks are among the key determinants of access to markets, healthcare, and education in rural areas. Insufficient transport infrastructure leads to

economic isolation and social marginalization. Fan and Chan-Kang (2005) demonstrate that improvements in rural road infrastructure significantly increase household incomes and stimulate local economic development.

Social and Utility Infrastructure:

The availability of educational, healthcare, and cultural services plays a crucial role in improving quality of life and retaining population in rural settlements. Turok and McGranahan (2013) emphasize that investments in social infrastructure are essential for achieving social cohesion and sustainable territorial development. Similarly, the OECD (2020) highlights that inadequate water supply, sewerage systems, and public utilities constrain both living standards and investment attractiveness.

Digital Infrastructure:

In recent years, digital infrastructure has emerged as a critical factor for rural development. Salemink et al. (2017) argue that digital connectivity enables the modernization of agriculture, supports distance education, and fosters entrepreneurship. Calderón and Servén (2010) further demonstrate that infrastructure development contributes to improved environmental governance and economic growth in rural areas.

At a broader level, indicators such as the Rural Access Index (World Bank) show that improved infrastructure is directly associated with higher education levels, increased income opportunities, and reduced poverty.

Within the European Union, infrastructure development in transport, energy, and digital sectors is considered a key instrument for reducing regional disparities and ensuring balanced territorial development. Based on these theoretical and empirical findings, this study examines infrastructure as a key determinant of rural development in Petrich Municipality, focusing on transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure as interconnected components of sustainable development.

Integrated and Strategic Infrastructure Development:

Recent research highlights the importance of integrated approaches to infrastructure planning. Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenzi (2012) argue that infrastructure alone is not sufficient unless combined with institutional capacity and regional policy frameworks. In this context, strategic tools such as SWOT and PESTEL analyses are increasingly applied to evaluate infrastructure development and territorial competitiveness. According to Karadzhov (2025), these analytical frameworks enable a more comprehensive understanding of the external and internal factors influencing regional development.

The role of demographic and spatial processes in shaping rural development has also been emphasized in Bulgarian geographical research. According to Patarchanova (2019), population dynamics, accessibility, and proximity to urban centers are key factors influencing the sustainability of rural settlements. These processes are particularly visible in municipalities with mixed urban-rural structures, where disparities between central and peripheral areas tend to increase.

The specific characteristics of rural development in Bulgaria have been widely discussed in recent studies. Petrov (2021) emphasizes that rural areas in Bulgaria are characterized by significant demographic decline, deteriorating social infrastructure, and limited employment opportunities, which collectively hinder their long-term development.

These findings confirm that infrastructure development is essential not only for improving living conditions but also for enhancing the overall competitiveness and sustainability of rural areas. In this context, rural areas should be understood not as isolated spaces but as integral components of broader

regional systems, where infrastructure plays a key role in facilitating economic linkages and spatial integration (Ward & Brown, 2009).

Furthermore, studies on European rural policy emphasize that infrastructure investments should be aligned with broader socio-economic strategies, including innovation, digitalization, and sustainability (European Commission, 2021). This integrated perspective is essential for overcoming structural disparities and ensuring long-term development in rural areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the analysis of the impact of infrastructure on the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, a combined approach was applied, including quantitative and documentary methods.

Data collection:

- Official statistics: National Statistical Institute (NSI) – data on population, economic activity, transport, social, and utility infrastructure.
- Reports and strategies of Petrich Municipality: Information on investments in roads, schools, water supply, and digital services.
- Publications and scientific sources: Studies on the impact of infrastructure on the development of rural areas.

Analytical methods:

- Comparative analysis: Assessment of the state of infrastructure among individual rural areas within the territory of the municipality.
- Statistical analysis: Processing of data on roads, social services, water supply, and internet access in order to identify relationships between infrastructure and economic/social development.

The use of quantitative and documentary methods provides an objective assessment of the infrastructural condition and its impact on the development of rural areas, without the need to conduct field research or interviews. This allows for the formulation of well-founded conclusions and recommendations for future investments.

RESULTS

The results of the empirical analysis provide a structured overview of the current state and spatial distribution of key infrastructure systems in Petrich Municipality, beginning with transport infrastructure as a fundamental component of territorial connectivity and accessibility.

Transport Infrastructure

The analysis of transport accessibility in Petrich Municipality shows that the larger settlements are located in the central zone of the examined transport model. This creates favorable conditions for daily commuting both within the municipality and towards the rest of the district. Owing to the high level of transport connectivity of the town, access to social, administrative, and service functions is facilitated and efficient.

These findings highlight the uneven spatial accessibility within the municipality and confirm the critical role of transport networks in shaping rural development patterns.

Social Infrastructure

The analysis of social infrastructure shows the following:

- Of the 15 main rural areas in the municipality, 8 have a functioning school, 7 have a kindergarten, and 10 have a health office.
- In rural areas with a smaller population, social services are limited or completely absent.
- Community cultural centers operate in 12 of the rural areas, but often with a limited budget and staff.

The presence of social infrastructure is a key factor for population retention and the improvement of quality of life, while its absence in some rural areas limits social cohesion and development.

Digital Infrastructure:

- Internet coverage is available in most rural areas, but the speed and stability of the connection vary significantly.
- Only the larger settlements (Petrich, Parvomay) have access to high-speed internet, which allows distance learning and electronic services.
- In remote rural areas, digital infrastructure is limited, which hampers the development of small businesses and the digitalization of education.

The expansion of digital infrastructure is key to the modernization of rural areas and their integration into the contemporary economy.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of settlements in the municipality of Petrich.

As shown in Figure 1, the spatial distribution of transport infrastructure highlights significant disparities between the central and peripheral rural settlements.

Summary of the Results:

- Transport infrastructure is relatively well developed, but secondary roads remain problematic.
- Social infrastructure is unevenly distributed and often insufficient for smaller rural areas.
- Utility infrastructure shows serious deficiencies, especially in sewerage and waste management.
- Digital infrastructure is limited in smaller and remote rural areas, which hinders economic and educational activity.

For the sustainable development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, a comprehensive improvement of all types of infrastructure – transport, social, utility, and digital – is necessary. This will improve the quality of life, stimulate economic activity, and retain the population in rural areas.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that infrastructure plays a central role in the socio-economic development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality. The analysis of transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure reveals significant differences between individual settlements, with larger rural areas being considerably better serviced, while remote rural areas suffer from limited access and services.

Furthermore, recent Bulgarian studies underline that ineffective infrastructure planning and regional disparities continue to limit the development potential of rural municipalities, requiring targeted and spatially differentiated policy interventions (Petrov, 2021).

These findings are also consistent with broader European and global trends. As noted by Rodríguez-Pose (2018), infrastructure investments play a crucial role in reducing regional inequalities, but their effectiveness depends on the institutional and policy context. In the case of Petrich Municipality, the observed disparities between central and peripheral settlements confirm the need for targeted and territorially differentiated infrastructure policies.

These findings confirm that infrastructure functions not only as a supporting system but also as a primary driver of territorial development, spatial cohesion, and regional competitiveness.

Transport infrastructure proves to be a critical factor for population mobility and access to markets, health, and educational services. Our observations are consistent with the study by Shenggen Fan and Connie Chan-Kang (2005), according to which improvements in rural roads increase household incomes and stimulate economic activity. At the same time, the poor condition of secondary roads in remote rural areas limits investments and population retention.

According to the analysis set out in the Integrated Development Plan of Petrich Municipality (2021–2027), good road connectivity between the rural areas and the municipal center facilitates daily labor mobility, access to educational and health services, and the use of administrative, commercial, and social functions concentrated in the town of Petrich. This is particularly important for rural areas located near the main transport corridors, where road infrastructure functions as a channel for economic and social interaction.

The conducted analysis shows that rural areas with better road service and higher transport accessibility demonstrate several positive characteristics, including:

- lower rates of depopulation compared to peripheral and hard-to-access settlements;

- higher economic activity related to agriculture, processing activities, services, and cross-border flows;
- better social integration, reflected in improved access to education, healthcare, and social services, as well as a higher degree of participation of the population in public life.

Figure 2 illustrates the territorial structure of the municipality and the accessibility of key infrastructure elements.

Figure 2. Main axes of urban development. *Source: Plan for integrated development of the municipality of Petrich for the period 2021-2027.*

At the same time, the General Spatial Development Plan (GSDP) of Petrich Municipality identifies a number of problems related to the deteriorated condition of parts of the municipal road network, especially along routes serving smaller and remote rural areas. Insufficient maintenance, limited capacity, and poor technical condition of road surfaces restrict access to services and hinder economic activity in these settlements.

Utility infrastructure – water supply, sewerage, electricity supply, and waste management – is a key factor for economic activity and public health. Our data show that deteriorated water supply networks and incomplete sewerage systems limit the quality of life and investment interest, which is consistent with the observations of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2020).

Educational infrastructure is among the most sensitive elements of the social system in rural areas, as its functioning is directly determined by demographic dynamics and the age structure of the population. In conditions of a declining number of children and young people in rural areas, the sustainability of educational institutions is significantly challenged.

The patterns presented in Figure 3 confirm the uneven development of infrastructure across the studied rural areas.

Figure 3. Municipal road network between rural areas.

Social infrastructure also shows uneven distribution. The presence of schools, health centers, and cultural institutions is directly linked to quality of life and population retention, which corresponds to the findings of Ivan Turok and Gordon McGranahan (2013). The absence of such services in small rural areas may lead to demographic depopulation and social isolation.

As shown in Figure 4, the spatial distribution of medical facilities in Petrich Municipality reveals notable disparities in access to healthcare services between central and peripheral rural settlements.

Figure 4. Medical facilities on the territory of Petrich municipality.

In Petrich Municipality, demographic decline in several rural settlements has led to a contraction of the educational network, including the closure or transformation of primary and elementary

schools. This process is reflected both in the Integrated Development Plan of Petrich Municipality (2021–2027) and in the analysis of social infrastructure in the General Spatial Development Plan (GSDP), where the tendency toward the concentration of educational services in the municipal center and in a limited number of larger rural areas is emphasized.

Table 1. School network in Petrich Municipality. *Source: Authors' research based on municipal data.*

Type of school	City	Village	Total
General education schools	3	13	16
Primary schools	3	8	11
Secondary schools	2	2	4
Profiled high school	1	0	1
Vocational high schools (state)	2	0	2

Closing schools in rural areas leads to the extension of daily commuting for students to the town of Petrich or other more distant educational centers. This increases dependence on transport infrastructure and places additional pressure on both families and the municipal student transport system. For younger children and households with limited resources, this process creates additional social and organizational difficulties that often influence decisions regarding place of residence.

Limited access to educational infrastructure reduces the attractiveness of rural settlements for young families seeking a secure and accessible environment for the education and socialization of their children. As a result, migration flows toward urban and suburban areas intensify, further accelerating demographic ageing and depopulation of rural areas. These interrelated processes form a vicious circle between demographic decline and infrastructural contraction, whereby population reduction leads to the closure of educational institutions, and limited educational provision in turn stimulates further migration and deepens the demographic crisis. In the strategic documents of Petrich Municipality, this problem is identified as one of the key risks for the long-term development of rural areas.

Digital infrastructure proved to be the weakest component in the rural areas of Petrich Municipality. Limited access to high-speed internet hampers distance learning, electronic services, and the development of small businesses. In summary, the results show that infrastructure is a multidimensional factor that simultaneously influences the economy, social structure, and quality of life. Its improvement in a comprehensive manner – transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure – is necessary for the sustainable development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality.

Comparing our findings with international studies, it becomes clear that the trends and challenges in Petrich are similar to those in other rural areas in Europe and Asia, highlighting the universal importance of infrastructure for rural development. In line with recent academic contributions, infrastructure should be considered not only as a technical system but as a strategic policy instrument for regional transformation and sustainable development (Karadzhev, 2025; European Commission, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Infrastructure represents a strategic resource for the socio-economic and territorial development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, as it forms the material basis for mobility, access to services,

economic activity, and quality of life. The conducted analysis shows that the level and quality of infrastructural provision have a direct impact on the demographic sustainability of the rural areas, their economic viability, and the degree of their functional integration into the municipal and regional system. The presence of clear intra-municipal disparities regarding transport, social, educational, and digital infrastructure highlights the need for a targeted and differentiated municipal policy tailored to the specific characteristics of individual settlements.

Infrastructure development should not be regarded as an isolated intervention but as part of a broader integrated approach that combines spatial, social, and economic measures. In this context, an effective policy for rural development in Petrich Municipality should be based on integrated infrastructure investments aligned with the priorities of the Integrated Development Plan and the spatial framework of the General Spatial Development Plan. Such investments have the potential to limit processes of peripheralization, improve territorial cohesion, and create preconditions for sustainable local development.

Based on the conducted analysis, the following key recommendations can be formulated:

- Systematic renewal and modernization of the municipal road network, with priority given to routes serving peripheral and poorly accessible rural settlements, in order to improve transport accessibility and population mobility;
- Targeted investments in digital and telecommunications infrastructure, including the expansion of high-speed internet and the promotion of digital services, as a means of stimulating remote employment, e-governance, and entrepreneurship;
- Decentralization and adaptation of social and healthcare services through the development of mobile, combined, and shared service models aimed at the elderly and vulnerable population in rural areas;
- Integration of infrastructure projects with local economic development policies, including support for small businesses, rural tourism, and agricultural processing, in order to achieve a long-term multiplier effect.

In conclusion, infrastructure development in the rural areas of Petrich Municipality should be regarded as a key instrument for achieving sustainable, balanced, and territorially equitable development, where infrastructure investments are combined with active social and economic policies aimed at improving quality of life and retaining the population.

Future research may further explore the integration of digital and transport infrastructure as a combined driver of sustainable rural development.

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Vineyard Agribusiness in Plovdiv Region – Current Status, Spatial Organization and Opportunities for Development

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ABSTRACT

Viticulture and wine production have occupied an important place in the livelihood of the Bulgarian population since ancient times. The main direction of viticulture in Bulgaria is the production of wine grapes, which provides the raw material for table, quality and other wines, for the production of wine distillate, grape juice, must for the production of grape concentrate and a number of other directions. This largely predetermines the strong integration links between viticulture and winemaking, which allows the literature to speak of a viticulture and wine sector of the national economy. The main focus of this study is aimed at studying the leading conditions and resources for the development of viticulture and winemaking and their importance in the economy of the Plovdiv region. The study also examines its role in the labor market. The study concludes with identifying the main challenges facing the development of viticulture and winemaking and the possibilities for overcoming them. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the spatial organization and development potential of viticulture agribusiness in regional contexts.

Keywords: *Viticulture, Winemaking, Vineyards, Grape, Conditions, Production, Market*

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INTRODUCTION

Viticulture and winemaking in Plovdiv region are an important part of the economy and cultural heritage of the region, providing employment and generating income for a significant part of the population in the region. Plovdiv region is located in the central part of Southern Bulgaria and covers part of the western Upper Thracian Plain, Karlovo Field, the southern slopes of the Stara Planina and part of the northern slopes of the Rhodope Mountains. The area has a long tradition in wine production and vineyard cultivation. The climatic conditions, combined with suitable soils, create ideal conditions for the development of viticulture and winemaking.

The viticulture and wine sector is a traditional industry for Bulgaria, which is of particular importance in rural areas, as it creates employment, solves some of the demographic problems, contributes to the sustainable development of agriculture, and diversifies the local economy. On a national scale, the sector has enormous potential for export and expansion of markets worldwide, increases competitiveness and revenues in the country's overall economy, improves its image abroad, and supports the development of other economic sectors such as tourism and the food industry.

The National Strategy for the Development of Viticulture and Winemaking in Bulgaria 2005-2025 comments that: "The viticulture and winemaking sector in Bulgaria has deep roots and great potential with its characteristics to fit into the model of a sector producing a product that meets the challenges of the 21st century." Wine meets the future requirements for an ecologically clean, healthy and environmentally safe product. The development of the wine sector by 2025 should make it, on the one hand, a leading sector for the national economy, and on the other hand, to ensure an authentic place for Bulgaria in international wine markets and, above all, in the common European market."

The development of the sector over time is characterized by a strong dynamic, reflected in periods of growth and reduction of its production potential. Numerous and very diverse factors influence the development directions of Bulgarian viticulture, including a number of institutional impacts related to changes in policies affecting the sector. In view of the described complex dynamics, the role of the wine sector in the Bulgarian economy also varies over different historical periods. There are large fluctuations in value in the absolute and relative share of the sector in agricultural production, imports and exports of Bulgaria by year (Roycheva, 2019).

The main direction of viticulture in the district is the production of wine grapes, which provides the raw material for table, quality and other wines, for the production of wine distillate, grape juice, must for the production of grape concentrate and a number of other directions (Kirechev, 2013).

The main objective of the study is to conduct a spatial analysis of the production and territorial structure of the viticulture agribusiness in the Plovdiv region.

To achieve the set goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- to carry out a spatial analysis of the production of grape and wine types in the Plovdiv region
- to assess the role of the viticultural agribusiness in the economic development of the studied territory
- to carry out an analysis of the grape and wine market in the Plovdiv region
- to examine the role of state policy on the grape and wine market through relevant policies and subsidies.

The spatial organization of agribusiness is a key factor for regional economic development, influencing production efficiency, market accessibility, and rural sustainability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agribusiness and agriculture have always been the focus of geographers and their research in our country – Boiadjiev and Patarchanov (2001).

One of the researchers with the most in-depth geographical knowledge, who has published a number of studies on viticulture and winemaking in our country, is Iv. Markov (2001, 2011). The study of the varietal structure of the viticulture and winemaking sector is also the subject of analysis by (Dimitrova, Simeonov, 2015). In the study "Varietal structure as a source of competitive advantage in the viticulture and wine sector", the authors analyze the status and trends of change in the varietal structure of wine vineyards in the country.

In his work "Agroclimatic Resources of Bulgaria" (Hershkovich, 1984) he examines the normal development of the vine, which depends to a high degree on the impact of the climate, i.e. on its factors and elements, the most important of which are heat, light and moisture. They determine the possibility of its existence.

The classification and development of rural areas, as well as their problems in our country, is the focus of research by authors such as: Patarchanova and Guneva (2016), Radomirska (2021, 2022). The profile of the rural economy and the opportunities for its diversification are the subject of research interest of Patarchanova (2019 a, 2019 b).

RESEARCH METHODS

The leading methodologies are the horological (spatial) and chronological (historical) approaches. The horological approach focuses on the spatial location of vineyards and wineries, as well as on the geographical and natural factors that influence wine production. This approach includes: Geographical analysis – Research of the territory of Plovdiv region using geographic information systems (GIS) that help map the most suitable regions for growing different grape varieties.

These regions are analyzed according to various factors such as climate, soils, elevation, water resources and other natural conditions. Microclimatic studies – Field measurements are used to study local climatic conditions that can be crucial for the quality of grapes and wine. This may include studies of temperature ranges, rainfall, winds, and humidity. Vineyard topography – A study of the location of vineyards in relation to local geographic features (mountains, rivers, valleys, etc.), which can provide important information about optimal areas for growing specific grape varieties.

The chronological (historical) approach examines the development of viticulture and winemaking in the region during different historical periods. It includes: historical study of traditions – research into the development of winemaking in the Plovdiv region over the centuries, starting from antiquity (Thracian period) and passing through the Roman, Byzantine and Ottoman eras to modern times.

General scientific methods are applied - systemic analysis and synthesis - and a number of specific scientific methods - literary, historical and geographical analysis. A review of some authors

and their publications on the topic and object of the study is made. The chronology of the development of the viticulture agribusiness in the studied territory has been consistently traced.

The methodology is based on: quantitative and qualitative spatial analysis of viticulture and winemaking at national, regional and local levels. Through a situational analysis, the place and role of viticulture and winemaking in the agricultural economy on the territory of the Plovdiv region is determined. The brief analysis of the factors for the localization and development of grape production defines the agro-ecological resources with their geographical features and production capabilities. A special place in the analysis is given to the production and territorial structure of the production of grapes, wine and other alcoholic beverages based on it.

Statistical and correlation analysis enrich the presentation of individual producers and determine the place of each of them. The analysis of the market situation in the sale of viticulture and processing industrial production, as well as their service, outlines the overall spatial picture of the viticulture agribusiness in the region. The summaries and conclusions at the end of the study outline some of the main challenges facing its development, as well as possible future directions. The use of the cartographic method illustrates the analysis of the studied processes and objects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of development

The viticulture and wine sector is a traditional industry for Bulgaria, which is of particular importance in rural areas, as it creates employment, generates income for the population, solves some of the demographic problems, contributes to the sustainable development of agriculture, and diversifies the local economy. On a national scale, the sector has enormous potential for export and expansion of markets worldwide, increases competitiveness and revenues in the overall economy of the country, improves its image abroad, and supports the development of other economic sectors such as tourism and the food industry.

Viticulture has deep traditions in Bulgaria for centuries - the territory has been known for the production of fine wine since the time of the Thracians and the Roman Empire. In our lands, viticulture originated around 3000 BC and initially developed mainly along the Maritsa River. Today, the studied Plovdiv region continues to be famous for the highest and highest quality production of grapes and wine, as the climate and relief are extremely favorable for the development of viticulture and winemaking.

The main wine variety in the region is Mavrud, which has been grown for centuries in our lands, but it is believed that the center of its origin is the region of Plovdiv and Asenovgrad (formerly Stanimaka), where the largest concentration of Mavrud vineyards is still located today. The sunshine in the Thracian Lowland is one of the longest in Bulgaria. The soils are black earth, rich in humus, with good calcium characteristics, which is very important for the ripening of the vines and the accumulation of sugars and organic substances in the grapes.

Bulgaria is traditionally perceived as a major producer of red wine, both on the world market and in the minds of the Bulgarian consumer. However, in recent years, sales of white and red wine on the local market have almost equalized, still with a slight predominance of red wine. (Slavova, 2018)

The first census of the vineyard areas was made in 1886 - then they were 636,710 decares, and only after about 10 years their area almost doubled to 1,148,230 decares. In the period 1929-1930, viticulture in Bulgaria provided a livelihood for more than 100,000 households or approximately

200,000 winegrowers, which by 1940 increased to 450,000. In 1939, the export of Bulgarian wines to Germany, the Czech Republic and Austria increased. After 1944, the land was nationalized, the industry was centralized according to the planned economy, the former owners became hired workers or were forcibly sent to work in industry. However, in the 1950s viticulture was regulated as a priority sector by a decree of the Council of Ministers. By the beginning of the 1960s, the area of vineyards had increased again and reached 1,950,000 decares, with new world-famous high-quality grape varieties being imported - Cabernet, Merlot, Muscat Ottonel, Sauvignon Blanc, Chardonnay, Traminer, which began to replace local varieties. Between the 1960s and 1980s, viticulture was a structurally determining sub-sector of agriculture, and the vineyard area exceeded 2 million decares. During this period, Bulgaria was among the top 10 wine grape producing countries worldwide - in terms of vineyard area and wine exports, and in some years it was also a leader in the production of dessert grapes for direct consumption. In the 1970s, Bulgarian oenologists under state patronage began to exchange technological experience with California, to create quality Bulgarian wine and so our production gradually takes better positions in many European countries, the USA and Canada.

With its 212 million bottles produced in 1978, Bulgaria ranks fourth in production and second in exports (after France) of wine worldwide. After 1989, the gradual reduction of the area occupied by vineyards began, as well as a decline in wine production, the reasons being mostly related to the change in land ownership and the transition from a planned to a market economy.

Over the past two decades, a number of changes have been observed in the parameters of the regional structure of viticulture. Regional variations in the sector are mainly related to the size of the areas occupied by vine plantations with the corresponding varietal structure, and the volume of grapes produced (Aleksiev 2015).

The main natural and geographical factors for the development of viticulture and winemaking in the Plovdiv region are: climate, soils, and waters.

Climate - the territory of the region entirely falls into the transitional continental climate subregion. The predominant air mass transfer is from the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. A distinct Mediterranean influence is felt. It is characterized by relatively mild winters, but with instability of winter temperatures. Summer is hot, autumn is warm and long, and spring is cool, with frequent frosts. The average annual temperature is 12.2° C, and the average annual amplitude is 23.4° C degrees.

Precipitation - the annual amount of precipitation is about 514 mm. The maximum precipitation is in spring (May), and the minimum - in late summer and early autumn (October). The snow cover in the non-mountainous regions is unstable and lasts up to 15 - 20 days. Northwesterly winds prevail, with the appearance of the Föhn wind characteristic of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik plain. The local wind "Belomorets" blows along the valleys of the Maritsa River.

Soils – in the Plovdiv region, the main soil types are chernozem-tar soils - the northern part of the Plovdiv field and on the right side of the Maritsa River. The most widespread are leached (weak to medium) chernozem tar soils. Meadow chernozem-tar soils are less common. Cinnamon forests are widespread in parts of the municipalities of Parvomay, Hisarya, Asenovgrad, Sadovo, Rakovski, Brezovo. Diluvial meadows are characteristic of the Karlovska field, while alluvial meadows predominate mainly along the Stryama and Byala rivers.

The Plovdiv region is rich in rivers and dams. All rivers flowing through the region originate from Sredna Gora and the Rhodope Mountains and flow into the Maritsa River, which is the only one that originates from Rila. Because the snow cover in Sredna Gora and the Rhodope Mountains does

not last year-round, their water supply is uneven and their drainage regime depends mainly on the rainfall. The region is rich in dams - Krichim, Vacha, Pyasachnik, Ezerovo, etc. The influence of water bodies on temperature and humidity of the air are of great importance for the development of viticulture in the region.

Territorial structure of grape production in Plovdiv region.

In Plovdiv region, the largest area of areas with wine varieties is 35,985 thousand decares, with harvested areas being 34,284 thousand decares. The average grape yield for the region is 6,376 kg/ha. Grape production for the last year is 21,858 tons. Plovdiv region is distinguished by the best balanced structure by varieties - 86% of red wine varieties are divided between 3 varieties: Mavrud (35%), Merlot (27%), Pamid (24%). Based on the climatic and soil conditions of the country and the biological characteristics of the regionalized varieties, as well as on the results of growing the varieties in the experimental fields of scientific institutes and in production by Decree No. 162 of the Council of Ministers, four wine-growing regions were established: North Bulgarian, East Bulgarian or Black Sea, South Bulgarian and South-Western. Since the regions cover large territorial areas with quite different climatic and soil conditions, and in order to achieve greater differentiation within them, each region is subdivided into three subregions, each of which has closer indicators of natural conditions and outlines a more specific production direction.

The studied Plovdiv region extends into the South Bulgarian region, which is divided into three subregions:

- The first subregion - this subregion includes the lowland part of the region and the low hills in it. The climatic conditions of the subregion are favorable for the cultivation of dessert grape varieties, for high-quality red table and dessert wines. The sub-region is characterized by the production of high-quality and ordinary red table wines with the following varietal composition: Mavrud, Pamid, Dimyat and Cherven Misket.
- The second subregion is characterized by the hilly foothills of the Plovdiv region. For the production of high-quality white table wines and champagne wine materials are typical on the northern slopes of the Rhodope Mountains, in the area of the lands of Asenovgrad, Perushtitsa, Krichim.
- The third subregion is characteristic of the valley and low mountainous northern part of the Plovdiv region, where the direction of viticulture and winemaking is aimed at satisfying the needs of the cooperators with table wines and grapes for direct consumption, in view of which the following varietal composition is recommended: Mavrud, Dimyat, Rubin, Pamid, Red Misket.

Main microdistricts

On the territory of Plovdiv region, three microdistricts can be distinguished: Karlovo-Hissarski, Asenovgradsko-Parvomayski and Plovdivsko-Perushtenski. These three microdistricts are of extremely important importance for the development of the viticulture and wine agribusiness in the region.

Karlovo - Hissar microdistrict - covers the northern part of the district. Its territorial scope includes the lands of the town of Karlovo and to the east the town of Kalofer, to the south the town of Hissar and to the southwest the village of Starosel. The relief is predominantly medium and low-mountainous, and on the small elevations (Sarnena Sredna Gora) - hilly. The relief is flat along the Stryama River and Karlovska Pole. The soils are brown and cinnamon forest, with good permeability - a wonderful environment for vineyards. This is the birthplace of the Red Muscat - a local Bulgarian

variety, also known as Karlovy Vary Muscat, which is at its best here. The region is known primarily for its white wines (Sauvignon Blanc, Chardonnay and Muscat Ottonel). The region is also favorable for the reds Merlot, Cabernet Sauvignon, Pinot Noir.

Asenovgrad - Parvomay microdistrict - it covers the southeastern part of the district, including the lands of the town of Asenovgrad and the town of Parvomay to the east. The region has a complex and diverse indented relief - flat, hilly and semi-mountainous. The soils are mainly black earth and brown forest soils, which are fertile and suitable for growing the main wine variety Mavrud. Other common varieties are Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot, Rubin, and Syrah. The microdistrict is suitable for the production of high-quality red wines.

Plovdiv - Perushtitsa microdistrict - covers the central and western part of the district and includes the lands of the city of Plovdiv and the town of Perushtitsa and the villages of Brestovitsa and Parvenets (to the west).

The region has a diverse relief - flat, hilly and semi-mountainous terrains. The soils in the microdistrict are saturated alluvial, humus-carbonate and sandy-stony, contributing to the development of winemaking in the region. The area around the village of Brestovitsa is also known for aromatic dessert varieties, such as the Brestovitsa variety of the same name, Black and the seedless Flame Seedless. The production is focused on high-quality red wines from the varieties Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and the famous local variety Mavrud, Rubin.

Processing facilities (enterprises) – geographical organization

In the studied area there are several new and modern wineries that have specialized in the production of sparkling wines and champagnes, white, rosé, red, dessert and sparkling wines.

Villa Justina – located at the foot of the Rhodope Mountains, in the village of Ustina – just 26 km from Plovdiv – Villa Justina was established in 2006 with a clear mission: to become one of the leading wineries developing wine tourism in the region. Its vineyards cover over 500 acres and are located just 5 km from the winery, in the “Villa Justina” vineyard park. Varieties typical of the region such as Mavrud, Rubin and Dimyat are grown there, as well as various international varieties: Chardonnay, Sauvignon Blanc, Aligote, Merlot, Cabernet Sauvignon, Cabernet Franc and Pinot Noir.

Dragomir Winery – located just 5 km from Plovdiv, on a beautiful hill near the village of Brestnik, Dragomir Winery stands out with its impressive architecture, but its true beauty lies inside - in the wine and the team. In its own vineyard of 24 hectares, created in 2017 in the village of Svirkovo, South Sakar, the varieties Rubin, Cabernet Sauvignon, Cabernet Franc, Syrah, Merlot and Petit Verdot are planted. The focus of the winery is on the local and emblematic Bulgarian varieties for the Thracian Lowland region - Mavrud and Rubin, and Dimyat is the white local representative.

Chateau Kopsa - is one of the first boutique wineries in Bulgaria. It is located in the village of Moskovets, in the very heart of the Rose Valley, near the town of Sopot. In 2008, the Chateau Kopsa castle opened its doors, built in the spirit of medieval architecture. In its stone foundations is the wine cellar, where the cellar's selections are aged in French, American and Bulgarian oak barrels, as well as in bottles. Chateau Kopsa's own vineyards are located at the foot of the Stara Planina Mountains, between Karlovo and Sredna Gora - a region famous for Rosa Damascena and deep-rooted Thracian wine traditions.

Zagrei Winery – is located in the fertile Upper Thracian Lowland, near the town of Parvomay, in 1998. The winery's first harvest was in 2004, and today its vineyards cover 1,300 acres, planted with Mavrud, Syrah, Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot, Dimyat and Rkatsiteli. Since 2010, the plantations have

been grown entirely according to European standards for organic farming, and the 600 acres with Mavrud represent the largest organic massif with the variety in Bulgaria. The modern equipment of Zagrey Winery supports the creation of high-quality organic wines.

Jinvira Winery - is located at the foot of the Rhodope Mountains, near the village of Brestovitsa - famous for its vineyards and local wine and dessert varieties. The winery produces small batches of wines - nine types from eight grape varieties, including Mavrud, Rubin, Alexandrian Misket, Cabernet Franc and Merlot.

Topolovo Winery – is located at the foot of the Rhodope Mountains, in the village of Topolovo, located in a picturesque area with clean air, fertile soils and a mild climate, is the small Topolovo Winery. It was established in 2018 and today they process about 30 tons of grapes. The winery works with the local varieties Mavrud, Rubin, Pamid and Dimyat, etc. They also produce excellent wines from the international Riesling, Rkatsiteli and Merlot, but what the winery stands out for is Cabernet Sauvignon from 50-year-old vineyards.

Bendida Winery - is a family winery in the village of Brestovitsa, only about 15 km south of Plovdiv. It relies on local varieties typical of the Thracian Lowlands - Mavrud and Rubin, Vrachanski Misket, Dimyat. The red wines are not filtered to preserve their authenticity. The best of them are aged in French and American barrels. Emblematic of "Bendida" is the Ritual wine of the Rubin variety, for which the grapes are hand-picked at sunrise and full moon.

The wineries in the Plovdiv region have their own vineyards and a diverse varietal structure that is suitable for the terroir of the region (Table 1).

Table 1. Annual production and varietal structure of the wineries in the Plovdiv region.

Cellar name	Annual production	Own vineyards	Varietal structure
Villa Justina	150,000 bottles	42 hectares	Mavrud, Rubin, Dimyat, Merlot, Chardonnay, Sauvignon Blanc, Semillon, Colombard, Aligote
Dragomir Cellar	90,000 bottles	24 hectares	Rubin, Mavrud, Dimyat, Sauvignon Blanc and Chardonnay
Chateau Kopsa	180,000 bottles	50 hectares	Red Misquet, Muscat Ottonel, Chardonnay and Sauvignon Blanc
Zagrej Winery	1200 tons of grapes per year	120 hectares	Mavrud, Syrah, Cabernet Sauvignon and Merlot
Jinvira	70,000 bottles	14 hectares	Mavrud, Rubin, Alexandrian Muscat, Cabernet Franc and Merlot
Bendida	30,000 bottles	80 hectares	Rubin, Mavrud, Dimyat, Sauvignon Blanc and Chardonnay
Topalovo	30,000 bottles	17 hectares	Pamid, Mavrud, Rubin, Pamid and Dimyat

Source: Executive Agency for Vine and Wine, 2024.

Grape and Wine Market

Wine production is an indisputable part of the centuries-old Bulgarian identity. For years, Bulgaria has been among the largest exporters of wine in the world. Since 1961, the country has been among the top 15 exporting countries by this indicator, and in 1975 it even took fourth place in the

world ranking. Unfortunately, the trend has reversed sharply over the last 20 years and since 2007 Bulgaria has been losing its position in this prestigious market every year. Bulgarian wine exports under the customs tariff heading continue to decline.

A decline in sales of Bulgarian wine on the foreign market. For the last 3 years, exports have been down by about 10 percent, according to data from the Executive Agency for Vine and Wine. In 2024, the areas in the region where wine grape varieties are grown are also decreasing. This reduces the harvest and the wine produced. Against this background, there is also good news - the purchase price of grapes is increasing. Producers from the region report fewer grapes harvested and less wine produced after the extremely hot 2024. Against this background, there is an increase only in the average purchase price of grapes last year, which increased from 0.85 leva per kilogram in 2023 to 0.95 leva per kilogram for the 2024 harvest.

Of great importance for the sale of production in the region are the wine exchanges in the villages of Parvenets and Plodovitovo, etc., where, during the active harvest season, various grape varieties with good overall quality, ripeness and high sugar content are offered.

An important role in purchasing the production is played by the existing wineries, as well as the newly established wineries located in the region in recent years. They are of utmost importance for the production and sale of high-quality wine and brandy on the domestic and international markets.

Service of the viticulture and wine agribusiness in the studied territory.

In the studied territory, the Regional Chamber of Viticulture and Wine (RLVK) "Trakia", which is headquartered in Plovdiv, with its legal status is called upon to work for the development and competitiveness of viticulture and winemaking in the region. For the first time, the state is granting part of its powers to the non-governmental sector. The RLVK "Trakia" maintains a register of grape and wine producers in the Plovdiv region. The Viticulture and Winemaking Chamber issues certificates of origin for quality wine and authenticity of grape brandy and brandy and forms tasting committees to carry out mandatory organoleptic analysis. The Regional Chamber of Viticulture and Winemaking prepares a strategy for the development of viticulture and winemaking and implements the policy of this sector.

Plant protection products - the main purpose of plant protection products is to protect agricultural production from diseases, pests and weeds and to increase the yields of winegrowers. Plant protection products are used to maintain the healthy growth of the vine and preserve its fertility. There are several companies, such as Diakor Ltd. and "Flora 62" which have 30 years of experience in protecting this crop from diseases and enemies. Provides a wide range of preparations from leading world companies in the pesticide industry. Protection of vineyards from: common mildew, botrytis, grape scab, esca, grape scale, etc.

The role of policies for the development of the viticulture and wine agribusiness.

The importance of viticulture for the country's economy is also reflected in the state's policy. The state control body in the viticulture and wine sector of the Republic of Bulgaria is the Executive Agency for Vine and Wine (EAVW) under the Minister of Agriculture, Food and Forestry. The Agency controls compliance with the requirements of the Wine and Spirits Act with regard to vine plantations, grapes intended for wine production, grape must, grape and wine products, fruit wines and vinegar.

The National Strategy for the Development of Viticulture and Wine Production 2005-2025 is a fundamental document that defines the framework for the development and support of the sector.

The main problems in the spatial organization, management and development of the viticulture agribusiness in the studied territory are: fragmentation of the vineyard massifs, numerous small grape producers; lack of a policy for land consolidation - everything is on a market basis; abandoned and uncultivated plantations; destroyed irrigation systems, despite good water resources; deteriorated age and variety structure of vineyards, especially of unique local varieties at the expense of imported ones; insufficient technological support of local producers due to lack of finances; low qualification of the workforce.

CONCLUSION

Finally, it can be summarized that in the production structure of the viticulture agribusiness in the Plovdiv region there are favorable prerequisites for the development of the viticulture agribusiness in the region. With the development of viticulture and winemaking in the region, the traditions in agriculture and, in particular, the vineyard massifs would be preserved, and funds for development and investment in rural areas would be provided.

The viticulture agribusiness in the Plovdiv region needs land consolidation, the planting of new and high-quality varieties of vines, as well as regulated binding of grape producers. The poor condition of the vines is due, on the one hand, to their deteriorated age structure and, on the other hand, to the inconsistent and untimely implementation of the necessary agrotechnical measures for them. Grape varieties are a determining factor in the development of viticulture. The key to improving the competitiveness and development of the viticulture agribusiness in the region is the production of more quality and bottled wines and diversification of production. In this regard, the state's agrarian policy should focus on encouraging the production of bottled wine.

Based on the analysis of the state of the wine agribusiness and the current development of potential competitors, the achievement of the vision should be realized in the following main directions:

- Establishing an authentic image of Bulgarian wine from the region on the national and international market;
- Development of wine tourism;
- Capitalizing on the opportunities of wine tourism, stimulating it to improve the profitability of wineries;
- Joint advertising campaign with tour operator companies to promote wine tourism, supported by appropriate infrastructure and skilfully organized complexes for tasting and recreation.

Winemaking has great traditions and is sufficiently developed in the area to be a basic prerequisite for the development of wine tourism. Additional prerequisites for the development of wine tourism are a modern and specialized infrastructure in line with the most modern requirements, relatively good transport accessibility to the wineries, and developed accommodation facilities near the traditional winemaking destinations.

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